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Declaration

I, Akoche Veronica Egeh, affirm that this work is entirely my own original creation. To the best of my knowledge, it has not been presented for attaining any degree elsewhere. Any referenced material is duly acknowledged, and there is no inclusion of previously published content by any other author.

Dedication

This work is dedicated to the memory of my late father, Bawa David Entonu, a staunch advocate for education whose life was cut short before reaping its full benefits. May his soul rest in peace.

I extend this dedication to my husband, Godwin Ejeh, whose substantial support marked the beginning of this journey, and to my elder sister, Mrs. Catherine Ada Otene, a lifelong mentor. To My beloved daughter, Praise Ochanya Ejeh, your patience during my absence is deeply appreciated.

Above all, I am grateful to Almighty God, whose boundless mercy and love made this journey possible.

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God bless you the most. And, to you, my beautiful Ochanya, I fondly call you my small boss.

You are indeed a gift from heaven. I give you a big cuddle for enduring with me all through. I am sorry I never had enough time for you because of my studies. You came into our life when I had just started this beautiful journey.

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Thank you for all your love and prayers. God bless you all. And to all my friends, I can't start putting all the names down, but I am sure you all know yourselves and as many as I have. You all are special to me. Thank you all for the support and love. God bless you all. I appreciate all the MTN Nigeria and Nigeria Communication Commission staff members' support in the research materials.

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Abstract

Over the past two decades, sustainability has garnered attention in business and academia. However, more is needed to know about how telecommunication benefits from sustainable development. This thesis investigates sustainability practices in telecommunications, focusing on MTN Nigeria. The study analyses the factors influencing best practices using qualitative methods, structured and semi-structured interviews with MTN Nigeria and Nigeria Communication Commission, and sustainability report data. Findings reveal challenges hindering adoption, including industrial constraints and energy shortages. The study underscores the need for enhanced sustainability practices in Nigerian telecommunication, providing insights for industry improvement. A unique sustainability model for the telecommunication sector is proposed, contributing to the broader sustainability literature. The study emphasizes the Triple Bottom Line and its impact on best practices in Nigeria's telecommunication, offering a valuable model for industry enhancement and guiding future research.

Chapter One Introduction

This study aims to evaluate effective sustainability practices within Nigeria's mobile telecommunications sector, specifically assessing and identifying industry best practices. The chapter is organized into eight sections for clarity. Section one provides the research background and problem statement, while section two delineates the study's aims, objectives, and research questions. Section three elucidates the rationale for the research, and section four presents an overview of the research methodology. The study itself is outlined in section five, with section six defining key terms and section seven defining the study scope; section eight summarizes the chapter.

1.1 Research Background

The research background delves into sustainability rooted in environmental systems, emphasizing adaptability (Sarkis, 2011). Literature highlights sustainability's potential to enhance business economic advantages, emphasizing a Triple Bottom Line (TBL) approach that integrates economic, environmental, and social considerations. Sustainable development prioritizes present needs without compromising future generations' capabilities, making TBL an essential framework for corporate sustainability goals. Telecommunications must adopt innovative sustainability practices to endure, necessitating shifts in business plans and procedures. The growing interest in understanding organizational sustainability practices is evident in recent literature (Akhtar et al., 2017; Carayannis et al., 2014; Carmeli et al., 2017; Lozano, 2015; Shoham et al., 2017; Strauss & Wood, 2017). Recognizing this backdrop, the study explores how organizations implement sustainability, contributing valuable insights to the evolving discourse on sustainable practices within the telecommunications sector.

This research establishes the backdrop for the current inquiry, recognizing the dynamic nature of the business world and the myriad challenges companies face. Uncertainty about the future, regulatory compliance, and performance monitoring are common hurdles, impacting companies' appraisal capabilities. Many companies struggle to achieve their business goals, leading to the collapse of some in extreme circumstances. As the world rapidly evolves into a global village, communication, particularly in telecommunications, emerges as a pivotal tool for this transformation. This chapter delves into the telecommunications theory, where the term is derived from the Greek "tele," meaning within

a space, coupled with "communications," denoting the knowledge and methods of conveying information. Telecommunications is critical in global trade, becoming a recognized prerequisite in developed countries. Wireless services significantly influence the development of telecommunication systems, marking a transformative phase in the industry's evolution.

In developed nations, mobile business communications increasingly rely on telecommunications systems. These systems, governed by specific rules, deliver essential services to customers. Services entail a series of integrated systems involving both the originator and end-users. The facilities operate in a tiered structure, with each tier performing a distinct function, enhancing controllability, and facilitating stakeholder interoperability. The telecommunications industry, spanning mobile phones, cyberspace, radio waves, and cables, enables global communication. Sustainability is a burgeoning topic among contemporary business executives, experts, shareholders, and clients. Globalization and mergers further intensify the focus on sustainability. Rooted in environmental and ecological structures, sustainability is the capacity to endure or adapt to a changing environment. The industry's discussion and emphasis on sustainability underscore its importance in navigating the complexities of the modern business landscape.

1.1.2 Problem Statement.

Sustainability revolves around decision-making that avoids negative impacts on both current and future generations, influencing diverse ecological and human issues. This study delves into how sustainability management is ingrained in corporate structures and governance. Authors like Epstein & Buhovac (2010), Brooke et al. (2012), and Giunipero et al. (2012) highlight common challenges faced by businesses in implementing sustainability schemes. As posited by Epstein and Buhovac (2010), conventional management systems often encounter barriers. Growing stakeholder pressure compels businesses to address social and environmental concerns, pushing for positive actions and improvements. Frostenson (2013) underscores the emerging significance of the link between sustainability and managerial success, with a focus on a company's validity and reputation regarding social and environmental sustainability.

Patterson (2016) notes that assembling the right stakeholders at the right time and place is a significant challenge in sustainability implementation. Tools such as environmental reporting and communication aid companies in corporate sustainability. The Dow Jones sustainability

index, widely used in developed countries like the United Kingdom, evaluates sustainability practices. This study recognizes the evolving landscape of sustainability and aims to contribute insights into how companies navigate and implement sustainability practices within their structures and governance frameworks.

While developed countries lead in sustainable practices, developing nations face the challenge of surpassing them. In Nigeria, prior research focused on sustainable practices in the banking sector. bank (Babajide Oyewo, 2014) This study uniquely examines best sustainability practices within the telecommunication industry, emphasizing the need for developing countries to surpass established benchmarks.

Aims and Objectives of Research.

1.2 Research Aim

This study assesses sustainability in the Nigerian telecommunications industry, analyzing global factors influencing sustainability practices. It focuses on MTN Nigeria to identify the critical determinants of best practices. The study culminates in developing the NSPM model to enhance sustainability practices within the Nigerian telecommunications sector.

1.2.1 Research Objectives

The research goals are achieved through the following objectives:

1. Critically review the literature on sustainability practices in the telecommunications industry.
2. Investigate factors hindering sustainability practices in Nigerian telecommunications.
3. Analyse the potential benefits of enhancing sustainability practices in Nigeria.
4. Empirically investigate a proposed sustainability model, aiming to improve current practices in Nigeria, focusing on MTN Nigeria.

1.2.2 Research Questions

1. What constitutes the definition of sustainability?
2. How is sustainability currently practiced in Nigeria's telecommunications sector?
3. What factors hinder existing sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry?

4. To what degree do implemented practices affect sustainability levels in the Nigerian telecommunications sector?
5. To what extent are significant benefits derived from enhanced sustainability practices in Nigeria's telecommunications industry?
6. What model can be formulated to enhance sustainability practices, specifically focusing on MTN Nigeria?

1.3 The rationale of the study

In recent times, organizational sustainability practices have become a significant topic, posing challenges and complexities that transcend mere profit-making. This research explores how organizations can achieve profitability while remaining sustainable and responsive to environmental concerns, particularly within the Nigerian telecommunications industry. As defined by Deloitte and Touche (1992), business sustainability involves implementing corporate policies and actions that align current business demands with shareholder interests while safeguarding and improving natural and human assets for the future (Varsei et al., 2014).

The assessment of sustainability components traditionally focuses on economic, environmental, and social aspects related to telecommunications. However, the United Nations has introduced an additional institutional component for evaluating sustainability performances (Labuschagne et al., 2005). The study emphasizes a holistic approach, considering these diverse dimensions to evaluate sustainability practices comprehensively.

The research justification stems from the existing literature on sustainability, emphasizing the need for improvements in supply chains, especially in developing countries. Previous studies on telecommunications sustainability reveal that environmental, social, and economic aspects indicate sustainability performance. Despite numerous studies on sustainability, a gap exists in the literature regarding sustainability measurement outcomes for future implementation ideas. This study addresses this gap by exploring sustainability practices in MTN Nigeria and developing a model to enhance sustainability practices in the telecommunications industry.

The discourse on sustainability and sustainable development has been ongoing since the publication of the Brundtland Statement in 1987, influencing businesses, academics, and the

media. However, the specific impact of improved sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry remains largely unexplored. This research argues for replicating innovative intervention strategies, proven successful in developed economies, within emerging economies like Nigeria. The current energy mix, combining self-powered electricity from diesel generators and the national grid, increases greenhouse gas emissions and energy costs.

Drawing inspiration from successful interventions like Vodafone's MPESA partnership in Kenya, which facilitated microfinance, this study focuses on sustainability analysis within the telecommunications industry. The argument for selecting Nigeria as a case study is strengthened by gaps in the existing literature and the potential for cross-comparative, ethnographic sustainability research. The research approach aligns with the specific perspective of academic expertise, aiming to develop a model tailored to Nigeria's sustainability practice and address inhibiting factors for adopting best practices in the telecommunications industry.

In conclusion, this research contributes to the evolving discourse on sustainability practices, particularly within the Nigerian telecommunications sector. By delving into the intricacies of sustainability components and proposing a model, the study seeks to bridge gaps in existing literature and provide valuable insights for academia and industry practitioners.

1.4 Overview of Research Methodology.

The foundation of this research lies in pragmatism, driven by a philosophy that prioritizes practical results while adhering to principles guiding qualitative methods. A flexible approach is adopted, blending grounded theory for rich data acquisition (Glaser & Strauss, 1967) with the Framework Analysis method for systematic analytical processes. Inductive reasoning forms the research methodology, commencing with specific observations to derive generalized philosophies and conclusions, aligning with the dynamic background of the study. This approach proves apt for a small-sample, qualitative data-oriented study, offering a comprehensive understanding of the trends under examination.

Content analysis is employed to gather data on sustainability practices in MTN, utilizing annual company reports for 2017. The Nigerian telecommunications industry, encompassing MTN, Airtel, Globacom, and Etisalat, is explored, with MTN chosen as the central case study due to data accessibility. Structured interviews with twelve executive teams from the Nigerian

Communication Commission and MTN provide in-depth information on sustainability practices. Thematic analysis is applied to scrutinize the collected interview data, categorizing themes before coding and sorting.

Thematic analysis ensures the validity and reliability of the study, aligning with qualitative methods and interviews. Ethical considerations, including independence, informed consent, confidentiality, and privacy, were prioritized throughout data collection. Qualitative research, leaning towards dependability over objectivity, is evaluated against four criteria: trustworthiness, transferability, constancy, and confirmability (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). This research upholds these criteria, particularly regarding reliability, as information is meticulously collected, transcribed, and presented in a thematic style. The unique contribution of this study lies in developing a sustainability practice model, corroborated by the presented case study, rendering the findings dependable and valuable.

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1.5 Outline of the thesis

The study is organized into six themed chapters, as presented in the table below for the Nigerian telecommunications industry.

Table 1 Outline of Chapters

Chapters	Outline
Chapter one - introduction	This chapter serves as an introduction and background to the study, meticulously exploring the research problem, the primary aim, research questions, and objectives. Additionally, the chapter delineates the scope and outlines the research process, providing explicit definitions of key terms. Finally, the chapter identifies and discusses the limitations inherent in the study.
Chapter two – Literature Review	The chapter initiates by presenting the theoretical components of the study, delving into the concept of sustainability within the existing literature. It further scrutinizes sustainability practices, specifically within the contextual framework of Nigeria, seamlessly integrating diverse aspects of the study.
Chapter three Methodology	The chapter intricately details the methodology applied in this research, providing a comprehensive overview of the chosen research design and methods. It offers justification for the philosophical stance embraced and thoroughly

	explores the diverse research methods, shedding light on the intricacies of data collection and analytical techniques employed in the study.
Chapter Four Analysis of Findings	This chapter centres on the analysis of the collected data. It systematically addresses each research question, unravelling themes that will be further discussed in the subsequent chapter.
Chapter Five Discussion of Findings	In this chapter, the outcomes of interviews and fieldwork data are deliberated. The emphasis is placed on the four pivotal themes identified in Chapter Four through the analysed results.
Chapter six Conclusions, implications, and recommendations.	This is the last chapter of this thesis. It presents an initial literature review, highlighting the gaps and the need for the study. The research questions aim, and objectives are then revisited. Furthermore, it presents a discussion of the implications of the findings to future research, and it identifies the contribution the study makes to knowledge. It offers recommendations for the Nigerian telecommunications industry.

source Author

1.6 Definition of terms

Climate change capitalism is defined as the age of climate change.

Corporate omnipotence. A considerable company might appear to have supremacy because of the regulatory control it has over its staff, the power it exerts on government, and any cartel it might be linked to,

Carbon assets: This refers to greenhouse gas emissions generated by a project, such as offsets, certified emissions reductions, and allowances, which are all considered carbon assets.

Double dividend occurs when there is more than the optimal amount of pollution and a budget deficit. Pollution taxes are a policy option.

Best practice: A style or method recognized as superior to any substitutes because it generates results greater than other means. The best practice is a standard way of doing things.

Creative self-destruction: talks about locking humanity into a process of creative self-destruction, which is about the climate crises.

Climate Keynesianism: This is the global change that occurs in the climate.

Solow residual; is an amount explaining practical output increase in a country yearly and from decades.

1.7 Scope of the study.

The research focuses on Nigeria's mobile telecommunications industry and emphasizes MTN Nigeria's communication. This study aims to review the degree to which sustainability is practiced in the Nigerian telecommunications industry by critically exploring and analyzing the factors driving sustainability practices globally. It also sets out to identify the determinants of best practices for sustainability using MTN Nigeria as a focal point to develop a model for Nigerian telecommunications sustainability called NSPM. MTN Nigeria Communication is part of the MTN Group, one of Africa's leading mobile telecommunications businesses. The MTN sustainability report shows that the company has existing sustainability practices that focus on the three pillars of sustainability: economic, social, and environmental (United Nations, 2017).

This study provides information on sustainability practices in the telecommunications sector relevant to developed countries like the United Kingdom. MTN Nigeria was chosen as the case study since it has structured sustainability practices in place. However, sustainability practices in Nigerian telecommunications are of a low standard compared to global comparators. In developed countries like the United Kingdom, sustainability indicators are used to measure the performance of companies. The researcher has considered this study within the Nigerian context. The study aims to create a model to improve sustainability practices so that telecommunications companies can adopt best practices for sustainability in Nigeria.

1.8 Summary of the Chapter

This introductory chapter overviews sustainability in Nigeria's mobile telecommunications industry. It highlights the research problem and justifies the aims of the study. It establishes the research aim and objectives and identifies the research questions to be answered. It identifies the study's contribution to the literature and introduces the ensuing chapters in the study.

The following section, Chapter Two, presents a comprehensive analysis of Nigeria's mobile telecommunications industry sustainability practices. It focuses on global development based on a case study of MTN Nigeria, which serves as the context within which sustainability practices are undertaken.

2.0 Introduction to Literature Review

This chapter analyses the literature on sustainability practices in the mobile telecommunications industry. It discusses the fuel for sustainability driven by countries, private organizations, and the United Nations over the years. Stakeholder theory is used as a theoretical basis to describe current sustainability practices. This chapter is partitioned into five main sections with subsections. Section 2.1 discusses the theoretical underpinning, and the next section, 2.2, explores the concept of sustainability, followed by section 2.3, which sets out the conceptual underpinning of the study. Also, the subsequent section, 2.4, presents the contextual components of the study. The concluding section, 2.5, highlights the conceptual framework and concludes the chapter.

Figure 1: Literature review framework.

Source Author

2.1 Theoretical underpinning study.

Audra (2018) outlines various sustainability-related theories, a crucial concept for understanding a flourishing society and organizational dynamics. This section provides a concise overview of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and delves into stakeholder theory, a subset of CSR. Emphasis is placed on the political-economic context surrounding the publication of Freeman's seminal work on stakeholder theory. The study briefly explores stakeholder theory applications in marketing, accounting, and strategy, highlighting its multifaceted impact. Additionally, shareholder theory, critiquing stakeholder theory per Milton Friedman's perspective, is summarized. Criticisms of stakeholder theory are acknowledged, with a subsequent defence that draws from diverse fields like strategy, accounting, marketing, and ethics. However, ethical philosophy is acknowledged as beyond the scope of current research. The upcoming section will elucidate the foundational theories guiding this study.

2.1.2 Corporate Social Responsibility

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) requires businesses to voluntarily access and take accountability for the impact of their activities on diverse groups called stakeholders towards attaining a positive net effect on society (Davis, 1973; Carroll, 1999; Cheng et al., 2014). CSR has become a conventional study in management with an impact on policy, professionals practicing distinct aspects of this field, and many books, specialized journals, blogs, magazines, and websites are published on this subject area, although with varying extent of adoption from one continent to the other (Matten & Moon, 2008). A specific indicator of the rise of CSR is that in the past decade, there have been over five thousand businesses that have subscribed to the UN Global Compact calls for businesses to engage in self-regulation to address the regulatory vacuum due to the process of globalization (Scherer & Palazzo, 2011). Another pointer to the progress of CSR is the proliferation of different ethical certifications and standards. For example, fair trade, an investor in people, ISO 26000, SA8000, the Global Compact, and the Global Reporting Initiative (Wood, 2010). Others are the rise of code of conduct on websites and company reports, with many CEOs mentioning stakeholder issues in their cover page introduction (Agle et al., 2008).

Additionally, academic scholars appear to have established a link between the outcomes of stakeholder-related projects. Articles on corporate social responsibility (corporate social performance) and financial performance (Olitzky et al., 2003; Margolis et al., 2007), even

though there are methodological issues. Nevertheless, CSR has also had a critical strand, where scholars have uncovered cases of organizations in their quest for profitability. This has put such scholars accused of unethical and socially irresponsible corporate behavior. Such as misleading customers, deceiving investors, abusing and sometimes assaulting employees, putting consumers at risk, degrading the environment, and cheating the government. (Campbell, 2007; Yusuf and Omoteso, 2015); other scholars have argued that CSR is aspirational and hypocritical as there is a difference between what organizations claim to do and their actual actions (Christensen, Morsing, and Thyssen, 2013). Albert (1993), Crouch and Streeck (1997), Dore (2000), Roe (2003), and Campbell (2007) contend that firms act socially responsibly only when strong institutions are present in their operating environment. Other scholars argue that organizations sometimes use flashy CSR initiatives to hide corporate social irresponsibility (Lange & Washburn, 2012; Pedersen & Gwozdz, 2014). A vital approach to the CSR inquiry is captured in the question: 'what are the limits of corporate social responsibility?' (Fooks et al., 2013). Fooks et al. (2013) used two Tobacco companies should establish how CSR could be used to lessen government inquiry and hide negative outwardness.

Beyond Fooks et al.'s (2013) question, another significant inquiry not yet addressed in the literature that this thesis addresses since Multinational telecommunication companies and Corporate Social Irresponsibility is covered in the academic literature on CSR (e.g., Cordeiro, 2003; Banerjee & Prasad, 2008; Tan, 2009): 'what are the examples of social irresponsibility of other stakeholder groups, and how could their social irresponsibility be addressed? CSR findings in academic literature could be integrated into three critical research areas, although not exclusive: stakeholder theory, corporate social performance, and motivation for CSR (Basu & Palazzo, 2008). Firstly, some CSR investigations explore the influence of stakeholders on managerial decisions in response to external stakeholder pressures (e.g., civil societies and in the hope of government policies).

Stakeholder demands could include the reduction of poverty (Jenkins, 2005), creating more awareness of AIDS (Walsh, 2005), mitigating environmental impact (Frynas, 2005), or reducing global warming (Van Marrewijk, 2003). CSR study on stakeholders also includes concepts such as descriptive, normative, and instrumental strands (Donaldson & Preston, 1995) and stakeholder attributes of power, legitimacy, and urgency, which determine the salience of a stakeholder from the manager's perspective (Mitchell et al., 1997; Carroll, 1979;

Wood, 1991, 2010). Thirdly, CSR studies have also explored organizations' motivations for adopting CSR. Some of the studies on business' drive for CSR revealed that businesses engage in CSR to attain legitimacy (Suchman, 1995; Bansal and Roth, 2000; Weaver, Trevino, and Cochran, 1999; Zheng, Luo, and Maksimov, 2014); for risk management purposes, (Bekefi, Jenkins, Kytte, 2006, Fombrun, Gardberg and Barnett, 2000; Husted, 2005), to develop niche customer loyalty (Sen & Bhattacharya, 2001), and to attain competitive advantage (Porter & Kramer, 2002). The fourth area of CSR studies related to the three listed above is the focus on the political responsibility of corporations (Arnold, 2010; Valente & Crane, 2010; Banerjee, 2011; Mäkinen & Kourula, 2012; Rahim & Alam, 2014). For this research, the aspect of CSR explored is stakeholder theory.

2.1.3 Stakeholder Theory

A stakeholder theory can be described as a strategic management theory that deals with organizational management and ethics (Phillips et al., 2003). Much of the study in stakeholder theory has looked at which stakeholders' merit or need management attention (Mitchell et al., 1997) discussed stakeholder salience. Methods to this question have concentrated on stakeholder-organization associations based on power reliance, lawfulness claims, and urgency (Donaldson & Preston, 1995; Mitchell et al., 1997). The stakeholder theory presumes that values are a part of doing business and argues the division thesis (Freeman et al., 2004, p. 364), which contends that ethics, and for that issue CSR, and economics are jointly limited. Freeman's (1984) stakeholder theory is a prescriptive theory with contributory and descriptive factors. It tells managers and companies how to deal with stakeholders' interests in a moral and applicable way. Donaldson and Preston (1995) analyzed and explained the stakeholder theory from the subservient, explanatory, and standardizing view goals. They established that though the three methodologies are various, they are complementary and that the normative approach is the "critical" base for the theory. Studies on stakeholders' theory have offered the following four central themes of stakeholder theory:

According to Uwakonye O. et al. (2017), Stakeholder Theory is explanatory as it provides a framework illustrating the interactions and relationships within a given context. A Stakeholder Theory is descriptive in that it offers a model of the corporation as a merger of cooperative and competitive interests. It describes how managers deal with stakeholders and how their interests are represented. A description of corporate characteristics and behaviors has been accomplished using the stakeholder theory. Furthermore, it describes how board members

think about the interests of corporate constituencies, including the mode of management of some businesses (Donaldson & Preston, 1995). The descriptive/empirical approach is justified by showing that the concepts involved in the theory correspond to reality.

Stakeholder Theory is instrumental, providing a framework for analysing the link between stakeholder management and achieving corporate performance goals. Some instrumental studies of CSR concerning stakeholder perspectives use statistical methods or qualitatively direct observations and interviews (Donaldson & Preston, 1995). The study observed that successful firms like Hewlett-Packard and Walmart have a stakeholder approach (Kotter & Heskett, 1992). Subservient explanations are based on stakeholder management and corporate implementation (Donaldson & Preston, 1995, p. 74).

Even though Stakeholder Theory is descriptive and instrumental, it is normative. All stakeholders are fundamentally significant; that is, all classes of shareholders are worthy of consideration. Their pursuits in the business recognize stakeholders if the business has a "resultant functional interest in them" (Donaldson & Preston, 1995). Normative explanations are based on a person or group's rights and utilitarianism (Donaldson & Preston, 1995, p. 74).

Stakeholder Theory is organizational in that it proposes approaches, forms, and practices that represent stakeholder management. It challenges immediate attention to be given to the legal interests of all applicable stakeholders. The theory suggests and regulates how managers work (Freeman et al., 2004). Regardless of which facet of stakeholder theory a company holds, the power and impact of the suitable stakeholders want to be well understood to efficiently achieve their future effect on the project (Bourne and Walker, 2006). A business with a stakeholder viewpoint outlines its approach centered on moral responsibilities to its stakeholders. Examples of this are a reasonable contracts method (Freeman, 1994), property rights (Donaldson & Preston, 1995), and feminist ethics (Wicks et al., 1994).

These are instances of moral tenets that can form the normative basis for stakeholders focused on management. It is not remarkable that some claim that moral responsibilities or ethics that are tactically employed are immoral in themselves (Zawaideh, 2006; Redman, 1995). However, the most significant point Stakeholder management is reaching a win-win position for all stakeholders, regardless of the reason. This guarantees the continued commitment of stakeholders to participate in the company to improve the lot of all members.

(Donaldson and Preston, 1995) emphasized the discrepancies between the stakeholder idea and the traditional input-output theory. In the traditional model, shareholders, dealers, and workers give input to the business, which is converted into client productivity. The feedback providers do, however, assume to get marketplace competitive reasonable. The stakeholder theory is established on the philosophy that all business stakeholders do so to gain advantages. No set of benefits and advantages takes precedence over the other.

According to Freeman et al. (2004), the basis of stakeholder theory is conveyed in two main questions: "What is the objective of the company?" and "What accountability does management have to stakeholders?" The first question causes managers to convey the collective value generated and what makes their stakeholders one. The second question induces the managers to connect with the stakeholders to achieve their purpose (Freeman et al., 2004). The fundamental issue crucial to the stakeholder theory is that "managers must encourage relationships, stimulate stakeholders and build societies where people try to give their finest to make good on the company's promises" (Freeman et al., 2004, p. 364).

Numerous theories about the business have been advocated in this study. However, the stakeholder theory is distinct because it is supposed to "describe and manage the shape and function of the company" (Donaldson & Preston, 1995, p. 70). The stakeholder theory sees the company as an individual through which "different members" attain multiple targets (Donaldson & Preston, 1995, p. 70). As anticipated, there will be differences in stakeholder benefits, but they must be solved so stakeholders stay in the relationship (Freeman et al., 2004).

2.1.4 Social Contract Theory.

The debate has rotated around associations between humans in their collaboration, even preceding contemporary societies. The theory has been going on for a few centuries, erasing all the collected incidents, which confirms its effectiveness (Thompson & Hart, 2006). The theory has been selected to discover the effect of the type of contract various stakeholders sign up for at the start or later in the relationship. Researchers have defined the social contract in diverse ways, such as Binmore's (1994) definition, which suggests that it is a contract by single group members to guarantee some degree of uniformity in life's game. By this, he suggests that the social contract further performs as a check or restriction on persons' activities, interests, and preferences as they will want to respect the game's guidelines.

In asking to do this, there are computations of the other party's decision, which facilitates the averting of any communal harm to members of the society. Debates regarding the existence and functioning of a social contract have persisted since the 15th century, with scholars like Hobbes, Locke, Rousseau, Rawls, Buchanan, and Hume making significant contributions to the discourse.

Several explanations are given for requiring the social contract, such as behaving as a facilitator of the benefits of individuals (Hobbes, 1651) and calculating the disparity among members of society (Rousseau, 1762). However, Locke (1690) disagrees that companies can have contracts and yet be in a state of nature if they do not respect contracts, noting that once parties enter any contract, they are all obliged by such terms and should keep to them. Donaldson and Dunfee (2002) refer to such acts of disrespect for the terms of the agreement as suggesting moral blindness on the part of the evading party. This point makes it essential to look at the unique features considered subservient by these writers to both the formation and care of the social contract, with the parties keeping to its terms.

2.1.5 Resource Dependency Theory.

The theory examines the significance of the resources being exchanged by the different stakeholders to the stability of their associations. From the theory studied above, aside from those who engaged in connections that have been examined, there are other significant things. The agreement is more significant than the members of the society that are parties to it, as, without it, there would be no connections between the different players concerned. Contracts are instituted to protect the diverse interests of stakeholders claiming resources exchanged in their relationships. Freeman and Murrell (2005) believe that stakeholder relations should be examined, focusing on the associations and not the stakeholders themselves.

This theory was applied to stakeholder debates where the stakeholders have been deemed owners of resources crucial to the company's existence (Kreiner & Bhambari, 1991; Agle et al., 1999; Freeman, 1999; Jawahar & McLaughlin, 2001). The theory primarily focuses on business's dependence on the environment for crucial resources, leading to uncertainties (Chin et al., 2004). Emerson (1962) and Pfeffer and Salancik (1978) significantly contributed to its development. Emerson (1962) explored power and dependence, establishing a foundation for understanding their interconnectedness and laying the groundwork for the

theory's evolution. However, Pfeffer and Salancik (1978) claimed that for any company to be productive and continue the challenges of modern business.

The environment must face its 117 external environments to retain the vital resources needed to keep it going. The environment must navigate its 117 external factors to secure essential resources for sustainability. Chin et al. (2004) suggest that sponsors have long emphasized the responsibility of businesses to proactively ensure the management of vital resources in their pursuit of organizational effectiveness.

It's noteworthy that many works on RDT adopt a business-business approach in a competitive environment, as businesses possess resources sought by other companies Froelich (1999) encapsulates the theory by citing Pfeffer and Salancik's (1978) assertion that a company's survival hinges on its ability to acquire and retain essential resources. guarantees any company's existence is its capacity to get and keep vital resources. This suggests that while a company can obtain resources, the possibility of losing them also stands. Jawahar and McLaughlin (2001) concur but emphasize that the level of significance attached to these resources can result in the company's dependence on the controller or possessor of those resources. Therefore, the firm must retain such resources once acquired to mitigate dependency risks.

Froelich (1999) cautions that this responsibility is challenging due to the volatile and uncertain external environment. In a competitive landscape, where other firms are vying for the same resources, the firm must navigate this complexity by actively engaging with those who control such resources. This interaction becomes essential to secure and sustain access to vital resources, acknowledging the dynamic and competitive nature of the external environment.

Firms employ stakeholder relationship management as the primary strategy to sustain essential resources, recognizing stakeholders as crucial contributors to organizational goals. According to Jawahar and McLaughlin (2001), the extent of dependence influences strategic choices. Firms adopt Reaction, Defence, Accommodation, and proaction strategies to navigate varying levels of dependence in managing these relationships. They further argued that the strategy to be applied to a stakeholder would be based on the importance and attention the stakeholder attracts because of its dependence on it given the dynamic nature of the firm's requirements, the significance of these levels of attention may shift over time.

Consequently, the firm may adapt and employ different strategies aligned with its evolving needs. Freeman and Murrell (2005) argued that for managers of firms to manage their relationships with their stakeholders professionally, they need to be aware of the strategies or options available to such stakeholders. Freeman (1999) had earlier generated four types of stakeholder influence strategies (as discussed in Section 3.3.5, p. 75) that stakeholders and firms could use in their relationships with others: Withholding Usage and Direct and Indirect strategies. Stakeholders may opt to withhold or utilize resources against the firm, directly or through allies with direct connections to the firm or other stakeholders. This strategic choice can significantly impact the firm's access to essential resources and relationships. He further indicated that the varied degree of mutual dependence among stakeholders in a relationship leads to different types of firms assuming control based on the power each wields through resource control. This dynamic interplay underscores the importance of power dynamics in shaping relationships between stakeholders and firms.

Stakeholder relationships, shaped by resource dependence, encompass Resource-dependent stakeholder relationships manifest in Stakeholder Power, Firm Power, High Interdependence, and Low Interdependence categories (Freeman, 1999; Freeman & Murrell, 2005). These categories encapsulate the diverse power dynamics and levels of interdependence characterizing the relationships between stakeholders and firms, providing a comprehensive framework for understanding the complexities within these dynamics. These classifications highlight the varying power dynamics and levels of interdependence characterizing relationships between stakeholders and firms.

Beyond the theory's emphasis on resources as the relationship focal point, the alternative perspective considers the options available to stakeholders or firms for crucial resource sourcing (Casciaro & Piskorski, 2005). This dimension explores the strategic alternatives in acquiring vital resources, adding depth to the theory's understanding of relationships regarding resource dynamics and sourcing possibilities.

These authors further emphasized that to understand the theory, two concepts must be examined: Power Imbalance and Mutual Dependence. Power Imbalance refers to the influence the different actors have on each other in the relationship and how those tilt in Favor. Meanwhile, Mutual Dependence signifies the extent of dependencies between the actors, irrespective of whether these dependencies are symmetrical or balanced. This suggests that

the level of dependence between the several actors will either affect or be impacted by the power level employed in the relationship.

The dependence caused by the scarcity of resources leads to ambiguity. It takes decision-making a little out of the firm's control (Chin et al., 2004), and that is precisely what the businesses want to prevent, which is why they pursue approaches that can be employed. Despite the discussion of Power Imbalance and Mutual Dependence above, it is noteworthy that this does not have anything to do with equality or inequality. However, it is about the importance of a stakeholder to another stakeholder with resources. This underscores that firms are not self-contained entities; instead, they rely on external entities to achieve their objectives, supported by Emerson's (1962) exploration of dependence. The interconnected nature of firms emphasizes the collaborative reliance on external factors to realize organizational goals. Hence, a corporation's dependency on another business or group is determined by the resources needed by the dependent firm from the latter. This dynamic establishes a power balance favoring the entity holding the crucial resources, illustrating the critical role of resource interdependence in shaping the relationships between organizations. This underscores the significance of the firm or stakeholder adeptly managing its relationships with others, recognizing that such management is pivotal in preserving access to essential resources. The ability to effectively navigate and cultivate these relationships becomes imperative for sustaining a reliable source of critical resources.

2.1.6 Justification for Theory Employed

A Stakeholder theory has been a well-recognized heuristic for describing the management environment for years; stakeholders have one or more of three relationship attributes: power, legitimacy, and urgency. Stakeholder theory development emphasizes explaining and predicting how an organization functions for the relationships and influences existing in its environment. Resource-dependence theory is an organizational theory that aims to elucidate the behaviors of organizations, both intra- and inter-organizationally, concerning essential resources necessary for sustainability and functionality.

This theory delves into how organizations strategically manage their dependencies on external entities to secure the vital resources crucial for their existence and operation. It provides insights into the dynamics of organizational behaviour shaped by the pursuit and maintenance of these critical resources within the broader framework of resource

interdependence. The theory concentrates on the following: the flow or swap of resources between organizations, those dependencies and power differentials created because of unequal resource exchange, the

Constraining effects such dependence has on organizational action and the efforts by organizational leaders to manage dependence. With its emphasis on resource exchange, resource dependence represents a political-economy organizational and inter-organizational behaviour model. In 1999, Donaldson and Dunfee crafted the Integrated Social Contracts Theory, offering managers a framework for ethical decision-making. This theory serves as a guide for navigating ethical considerations in managerial choices, emphasizing the integration of social contracts to form a cohesive ethical foundation. It provides a structured approach for managers to align decisions with societal expectations, fostering a harmonious balance between organizational objectives and ethical responsibilities within the broader social context.

The theory implies that managers must realize that by providing for their employees' welfare through the mini-social contract, they are indirectly taking care of society because hazards to an employee doing their duty sometimes affect the family and extend to the community. In contrast, the Stakeholder Theory of an organization is used to manage those groups to whom a company should be held responsible. As Freeman (1984) agreed, the company can be seen as a chain of links of stakeholders that the executives of the firm attempt to manage.

Corporate social responsibility considers just one aspect of a business, its orientation in terms of society in general. That is the social understanding of any business task. At the same time, the stakeholder is concerned with the basics of a business, mainly with building relationships and creating value for shareholders.

Freeman (1984), one of those investigating the stakeholder's method, defines the theory as any faction or persons that can change or is influenced by the success of the company's goals. This theory is a viewpoint of private enterprise that emphasizes the interrelated connections between a firm and its clients, dealers, workers, shareholders, societies, and others. Numerous ideas regarding sustainability are in the works. This is now an essential subject for insight, and these ideas relating to sustainability have been reviewed above. Stakeholder theory believes that companies can only be deemed productive when they give importance to most investors. That implies that turnover alone cannot be measured as the

only degree of enterprise achievement; there are economic advantages to using stakeholder theory in an association. They comprise 1) higher efficiency via worker contentment, 2) increased retention/recommendations from a pleased client, and 3) enhanced savings from happy investors. Yes, employing stakeholder theory can assist in making revenues for the company. Nonetheless, there are more minor consequences of employing stakeholder theory than the advantages of the philosophy itself. Thus, electing this theory, this study focuses on the sustainability of Nigeria's telecommunication.

2.2 Conceptual Underpinning Study

Below are the foundations that are used to support the conceptual framework of this thesis.

2.2.1 Sustainability

Sustainability is a commonly used word with different interpretations. Hence it is often subject to ambiguity. According to the United Kingdom government, the recognized universal definition of sustainability was defined by Brundtland (1984) as a kind of philosophy that sees the necessity of the current situation without compromising the chances of forthcoming generations to look after their wants. Regarding sustainability values, corporations in general and telecommunications companies expressly have a personal stake in how they view the commensuration process. (Kolk et al.,2008) while telecommunication companies are themselves stakeholders, their response and intentions can be classified as corporate ventures in a capitalist environment with a hint of; climate capitalism, organizational ecology, corporate citizenship, or corporate authority, depending on whose views prevail.

(Newel &Paterson, 2010, Jayant & Gowda, 2014, Wright and Nyberg, realist and pragmatic aspects of corporate entities are best captured via their utilitarian and instrumentalist approaches to solutions involving moral persuasion to become more sustainable in business, leading to increased costs and organizational survival. Jayant and Gowda (2014) best capture this by conceptualizing corporations' sustainability and financial performance dilemmas (Jayant & Gowda, 2014). They postulated that "visionary corporations" embed sustainability programs of development into their strategy and experience. Exceptional proceeds from investments in sustainable ventures, while the "license to operate merchant" view of sustainable development programs look at the financial performance. It assesses economic viability before any investments are made.

The "social contract corporations" consider themselves to contract with society and the "suboptimal corporations." This may be underperforming financially due to other issues they might fail to cope with, such as the cost of the sustainability program. Thus, they underperform in both aspects. This links to the critical issues of how corporates deal with the contentious duality and plurality of generating exemplary financial performance and the expectation of excellent sustainability performance. However, without detracting, some organizations have attained best practices in sustainability and are financially performing at an exceptional level. This study focuses on comprehending the concept of best practices rather than resolving the challenges posed by duality and plurality.

2.2.2 Definition of sustainability

Ecological, human, and economic health and vitality. Sustainability holds that finite resources should be utilized judiciously, considering long-term implications and consequences. Emphasizing prudent and conscientious use, sustainability is oriented toward future generations and the world they inherit (UCLA Sustainability, 2015). It underscores the responsibility to leave a positive and enduring impact, recognizing the interdependence between current actions and the well-being of subsequent generations and the environment they inherit.

Another definition by Morelli (2011) also defines sustainability as a socio-ecological progression known with the quest for a standard view. An idyllic is inaccessible in each minute and room. However, the procedure ends in a sustainable structure by determinedly and energetically advancing it. From the ecological perspective, sustainability is the property of a biological system that stays varied and functional indefinitely. Instances of a sustainable natural structure benefit marshlands, and forest sustainability is the system's strength and process. The standard for sustainability is organized and called sustainable development, with iv areas, biology, finances, policy, and society. In contrast, sustainability knowledge studies sustainable development and environmental science. Sustainability can seem like humankind's goal of human-ecology balance (homeostasis) Bosselmann, (2016).

However, sustainable progression means the complete approach and progressive process, which can lead to the endpoint of sustainability, even with the rise in recognition of sustainability. The chances that human societies will attain environmental sustainability have been. Considering environmental destruction, weather change, overconsumption, populace

growth, and societies' chase of limitless economic development in a shutdown approach, they will continue to be examined. Shifting towards sustainability is a societal task that involves global and state rule municipal preparation and transport, native and individual routine, and decent consumerism. Sustainability is developing as one of the numerous vital measures for accessing the quality of corporations and their leaders among stakeholders, supply chain partners, and gifted young people entering the labor force. The idea of sustainability goes beyond environmental effects. However, this thought naturally appears significant for most industrial and extraction businesses. In the business world today.

Sustainability valuations include environmental and social practices and linked governance (ESG). Standard ESG reporting yardsticks, including the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) ethics, are developing to support those pursuing sustainable leadership. Hence, there has been a slight direction on where to concentrate regarding shareholders or bring sustainability into corporate strategy and brand communications. Current research on sustainability focuses on developed economies where prominent levels of regulation already exist, and corporate actors apply various coping mechanisms to deal with environmental regulations. While climate change is an emerging 38 global phenomenon, all countries have their energy mix configuration and different starting points in the race towards a carbon-constrained global economy.

Furthermore, this presents opportunities for sustainable alternatives in the form of innovative intervention strategies, leading to savings in energy costs and carbon emissions (Schaltegger & Burritt, 2005). Wright and Nyberg (2014) propose an awareness-based approach to exploring the current meaning of existing myths. Newell's and Paterson's climate Keynesianism as an "only way" falls short of empirical evidence. Rama and Gowda provide grounding to the debate by indicating that companies facing challenges play a role in justifying climate change and sustainability. Paavola (2008) proposes that one discipline alone cannot offer legal solutions from a social justice point of view. GHG targets and market instruments (such as carbon tax) are necessary, while researchers from an interdisciplinary approach generate legitimate practical solutions (Paavola, 2008). Most companies now play active roles in decreasing sustainability burdens and preserving resources for future use due to climate change. Developed countries have stringent environmental regulations while developing countries face the dilemma of mass urbanization, which affects the standard of living and threatens environmental health. Developing countries are behind developed

countries in environmental stewardship. Wyeth (2013) believes sustainability managers in developing economies take bootstrap tactics by starting small and scaling. This can be addressed via identification, critical analysis, and evaluation of "best practice."

Figure 2: Sustainable development goal

2.2.3 Overview of sustainability

Sustainability is a term with multiple meanings. In recent years, increasing fears of environmental and weather change, the rise of poverty, growing inequality among cultures, and pressures brought by societal disparities have put sustainable development as a firm into focus. Hopwood (2009) proposes that we should advance the discussion of sustainability to chase a definitive search for sustainable development. He suggests that giving a clear meaning of this theory and understanding its scope is required. We must adopt a joined tactic towards sustainability; indeed, sustainable development cannot be realized through initiatives. Instead, it requires an integrated effort at several levels, covering social,

environmental, and economic aspects. Gray (2010) emphasizes the importance of sustainability, citing a scenario where it must come about naturally.

The Brundtland Commission report, issued in 1987 by the United Nations, characterizes sustainable development as progress that addresses current necessities while safeguarding. Underscores the essence of sustainable development. Balancing present necessities with a focus on resource conservation is paramount to securing a sustainable and thriving future for the coming generations. This global perspective unites nations in delineating the entitlements of the human family to a healthy and productive life.

Emphasizing an intergenerational perspective, the concept underscores responsible resource usage to ensure longevity and prosperity for all. It signifies a collaborative commitment to harmonizing developmental endeavors with environmental and social considerations for the collective well-being of humanity and the planet. In 1972, the United Conference on the Human Environment held in Stockholm brought the industrializing and developing nations together to delaminate the right of the human family to health and productivity; at the united conference in 1997, John Elkington introduced the Triple Bottom Line concept, asserting that business objectives are intrinsically linked to society and the environment. This approach advocates for a comprehensive evaluation of business goals, considering their impact on society and the environment as integral factors in decision-making and analysis.

In reaction to the growing stresses arising from national and international regulations and society in general, companies are slowly adopting ethical, social, and environmental responsibility within their policies, structures, and management. An instance is the Sustainable Development Solutions Network—SDSN—of the United Nations, commissioned in 2012. Physicians, for example, (KPMG 2015) and researchers (Joseph, 2012) have augmented emphasis on international social and environmental sustainability. As Gond et al. (2012) claimed, in some cases, this rhetoric has been used to restructure the wrinkled lawfulness of businesses. Furthermore, this has not mostly considered the central operational aspect of sustainable development. Such dynamic execution and input would require establishments to modify their prevailing practices and allow for a solid, planned move toward sustainability.

This idea has supported recent findings on the honest kind of sustainability. Many arguments show that "any predictable, sustainable state will be the outcome of interactions between organizations, individuals, societies, and states." From this viewpoint, a unified method regarding sustainability would involve recognizing the capacities of its essentials. (Economic, social, and environmental) concurrently, the tensions, trade-offs, and synergies between these dimensions must also be managed (the researcher defines this method as 'unified sustainability'). More crucially, in coping with the tension of sustainability, a crucial part can be performed by ad hoc governance structures, business models, management, measurement, and writing on the systems, which could be firmly designed according to an integrated approach.

In this perspective, the current argument about joint reporting will likely play a significant role. Sustainability development is an answer to quantitative environmental and economic data showing that the present economic development drifts could be more stable. Sustainability, from the ecological perspective, belongs to a biological system. An excellent example of sustainable biological classification is healthy wetlands and forest sustainability based on policy and process strength. Among these concepts (CSR) are corporate nationality, persons, planet, profit (PPP), social and organizational performance, and many others (Doyle, 2008).

The concept of corporate sustainability mimics the fundamentals of four recognized perceptions: 1) sustainable growth; 2) CSR, which plays the part of a business in the community; 3) shareholder theory; and 4) corporate responsibility. 41 An elementary code for stakeholder theory is the tighter associations with other parties. Achieving a corporate company makes achieving corporate aims faster; equally, if the contacts are weekly, it is more challenging to attain firm purposes (Wilson, 2003). Stakeholder theory aims to assist companies in reinforcing their associations with outside groups to grow a good advantage. Corporate sustainability in businesses gives development and productivity, whereas, during the same period, following sustainable growth aims (i.e., societal and environmental impartiality and economic advantage) (Wilson, 2003). This development has two contributions to corporate sustainability:" It supports to set out the parts that firms should concentrate on environmental, social and economic performance" (Wilson, 2003, p. 2).

Two, to deliver environmental, social, and economic sustainability aims for companies, management, and free society to work to (Wilson, 2003), a significant effort on the part of sustainability does not recognize the value of financial performance as a substantial fragment

of sustainability (Aras & Crowther, 2008). United Nations conferences have consistently addressed issues related to sustainable development. The 1992 United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development paved the way for subsequent dedicated initiatives. In 2012, the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development produced a significant political outcome document titled "The Future We Want." This document outlines explicit and practical measures for achieving sustainable development. It serves as a comprehensive framework, emphasizing clear strategies to realize sustainability goals. The commitment to actionable measures reflects a global effort to implement tangible steps, fostering collaboration and progress toward a sustainable future. Member States agree to present a procedure to formulate a set of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Based upon the Millennium Development Goals. Furthermore, it converges with the post-2015 development agenda of the United Nations. (Griggs, 2013). In 2015, the United Nations Sustainable Development Summit presented a plan of action for people, the planet, and prosperity while also striving to enhance global peace and, more significantly, liberty. In this report, the most substantial task is eliminating abject poverty, a vital necessity for sustainable development. They engage in building the Millennium Development Goals and achieve what these still need to accomplish. They are unified and united and equilibrium the three aspects of sustainable development: the economic, social, and environmental United Nations (2015). In 1997 the

The theory of TBL by Elkington (1997) suggested that corporate objectives are inseparable from the society and environments within which they operate. Sustainability is a multidimensional model divided into three area scopes: economic, environmental, and social, often mentioned as the TBL. According to (Luqmani et al, 2017), a sustainable business creates a reasonable return for its dealers. However, it restricts environmental damage and improves the survival of the individuals with whom it has interacted. In other words, its four surpluses, economic, environmental, and societal interests, give the organization its 'license to practice.

2.2.4 Triple bottom line

The triple bottom line is a business theory that suggests businesses should evaluate their social and environmental effect—in addition to their economic performance—instead of merely concentrating on creating profit, or the traditional "bottom line" concept can be

deconstructed into the "three Ps": profit, people, and the planet. This framework underscores the interconnected considerations of financial gain, societal well-being, and environmental impact in evaluating an organization or business's overall performance and sustainability.

Profit In an entrepreneurial economy, a business's success depends on its economic performance or the profit it makes for shareholders. Strategic planning projects and critical business decisions are carefully constructed to boost profits while lowering costs and lessening risk. In the past, many firms' targets have closed there. Objective-focused leaders realize they could use their firms to achieve helpful change in the world without impeding financial performance. In many cases, embracing sustainability initiatives has proven to make the business successful.

People The next element of the triple bottom line focuses on a business's societal effect or its dedication to people. Making a difference between a firm's shareholders and stakeholders is crucial. Conventionally, businesses have preferred shareholder value as a sign of success, meaning they attempt to create value for those who own company shares. As firms have progressively accepted sustainability, they have moved their attention toward generating value for all stakeholders affected by business decisions, including clients, workers, and community members. Some straightforward ways businesses can serve society include guaranteeing fair contracting practices and supporting volunteerism in the workplace. They can also look outwardly to make a change on a larger scale. For instance, many companies have formed successful strategic relationships with non-profit corporations with a common idea-driven goal.

The Planet

The last element of the triple bottom line deals with positively affecting the planet. Ever since the birth of the Industrial Transformation, and big companies have added an unbelievable amount of pollution to the environment, which has been a major teamster in climate change. Hundreds of companies in the energy sector are responsible for 71% of all industrial emissions. While firms have traditionally been the most prominent suppliers of climate change, they also hold on to the key to driving.

Positive change. Many business leaders now realize their obligation to do so. This attempt is not merely on the shoulders of the world's largest companies—all businesses have prospects to make differences that decrease their carbon footprint. Modifications like using

properly obtained materials, cutting energy utilization, and simplifying shipping practices are steps in the right direction.

Why is the triple bottom line important?

To some, embracing a triple-bottom-line method may seem idealistic in a world emphasizing profit over aim. Modern firms, however, have repeatedly shown that it is possible to do well by doing good. The triple bottom line prioritizes social and environmental impact alongside financial gain. Contrary to sacrificing financial profits, many companies have achieved economic success by dedicating themselves to sustainable business practices, demonstrating the compatibility of financial prosperity with a commitment to social and environmental responsibility.

Figure 3 Triple bottom line

2.2.5 Pillars of Sustainability

Social Sustainability

This is the smallest well-defined and known aspect of imminent Sustainability and sustainable growth. Hence, social group supplies and prospects for specific independence and understanding of non-communal probable, Contribution in power and law establishing, nationality to others, Fairness, the broadcast of info, and resource allocations all influence the power society to flourish over time. The Sustainability of humans is inherently a human process. Humans live and thrive in the natural, built, and cultural surroundings resulting from generations of social collaboration with their surroundings. The rules that any gathering develops to designate relation values to such things as technological change, scientific investigation, economic action, gains and rates, risk, nature, humankind, and brutalized life significantly alter the options for those teams to take. These are, consequently, the prospects that are given to potential generations.

Economic Sustainability

Economic Sustainability is the theory that a company or nation uses its reserves expeditiously and conscientiously to create an operating profit reliably. It is considered that if a firm cannot maintain its pursuits, not acting correctly and ruining its funds promptly, a corporation will not be able to sustain its ventures over a long time. Economics is the study of fundamental conditions of deficiency or others with limitations. Some writers have indicated that economics is the research of persons and associations and how they choose to use limited resources, which may have various uses to deliver products and facilities and disseminate them over the short or long between varied persons and assemblies in society. 'Economic Sustainability suggests a system of manufacture that pleases gift intake level without compromising future creation. The 'sustainability' that 'economic Sustainability pursues the 'Sustainability of the nationwide economy itself. Conventionally, economists propose that the supply of natural possessions is limitless, which has placed unnecessary pressure on the ability of the market to assign supplies expeditiously. Some imagine that such a system would bring about the technical capacity to provide for natural reserves damaged inside the assembly. Now, however, a consciousness has appeared that natural remedies do not exist to be limitless. The increasing size of the national financial system has hindered the growth

of natural reserves. This has triggered many observers (Goodland, 1995) to question the practicability of emotional development and exponential consumption.

Cultural Sustainability

Cultural Sustainability relates to property development and the maintenance of cultural principles, traditions, legacy preservation, and culture as its body tries to determine whether any given customs will exist over time. A culture is a group of principles, ethics, techniques, and a horde of Personal information is consumed with the conduction of these traits to newer creations. Acreage is made open because of the need to maintain or remain. The researcher interlinked the two ideas with various social and political territories, and in and of itself, everyone plays a significant part in Sustainability. As first stated in 1995, cultural acreage offers feasible choices in the scope of the strategy, offering answers to estate development matters.

Cultural property is considered a significant matter, even a necessity to be met on the route for property development. Nevertheless, the theoretical and conceptual comprehension of cultural property remains incomprehensible. As a result, the position of culture is inadequately implemented in the symposium of the interludes of the environment. Moreover, as politics and strategy define the effect of cultural property, the idea of culture from the perspective of sustainable development is a complicated proposal. It provides help to investigate best practices in providing the thorough rule. This is especially true as shrewd areas and expansion are markers for evaluating culture's effects on sustainability development. Cultural Sustainability has always been categorized beneath the social pillar of the three elements of the property. Nevertheless, with the latest advancements in this area, cultural property is its pillar, thanks to its increasing significance in the social, political, environmental, and economic areas.

The significance of cultural capital lives in its esteemed capacity. Therefore, a choice is formed from the perspective of a society strongly swayed by an institute's values. Environmental Sustainability Environmental Sustainability entails staying contained in our way and that our nature reserves gauge actual environmental property. Human Beings tend to use an irresistible need for our natural reserves, supplies, energy fuels, land, and water. Some resources are used more than others, so material weakness and environmental damage from mining those resources have developed into a problem. The environmental

property must not be mystified with the entire property, which should stabilize economic and social factors.

2.3 Contextual Underpinning Study

Nigeria is a developing country that has recently experienced negative experiences due to several events in which the development process was impeded. Nigeria witnessed environmental disasters and instability, which is still ongoing. Nigeria gained its independence in 1960. The largest resource in this respect is the petroleum industry. Keeping the measures in mind, the Nigerian government has emphasized the economic and profitability aspects of the petroleum industry, neglecting environmental and sustainability considerations. Chikaire et al. (2015) posited one perspective. Conversely, Busnaina and Woodall (2015: p. 786) contended that Nigeria's economic reform has advanced, emphasizing the country's concerted efforts to re-engage with the global business community.

Nigeria's stakeholder theory and CSR can only be discussed in isolation, referring to oil's strategic role in the Nigerian market. The Niger Delta is where oil is found in Nigeria and has five big international oil companies. Generate most of the nation's oil; looking at Nigeria as the context of this study with emphasis on telecommunication is the study's primary objective. This section gives an overview that sets the context of the study, which is Nigeria, considering the pillars of social, economic, and cultural sustainability concepts to understand the extent of sustainability practice in Nigeria in the telecommunication sector, emphasizing the application of stakeholder theory.

2.3.1 Sustainability in Nigeria's context

Sustainability is considered eco-centric, with "Eco" signifying environmental friendliness or sensitivity. Oxford Dictionaries (2014) defines ecology as "the branch of biology dealing with the relationship of organisms to each other and their physical environments." Sustainability, derived from the Latin "sustainer," meaning to sustain, is rooted in ecological principles. It emphasizes harmonious coexistence between organisms and their environments, reflecting a commitment to enduring practices that preserve ecological balance. This interplay between ecological awareness and the etymology of sustainability underscores its core principles in maintaining environmental health and balance. Various synonyms such as "to keep," "maintain," and "sustain" (The Free Dictionary) are presented, revealing nuanced distinctions

among the terms, with some being complementary. According to Mensah et al. (2012), the ongoing discourse revolves around what could be termed as *sustinere-eco*, essentially signifying the act of preserving or maintaining the environment. This linguistic exploration emphasizes the multifaceted nature of environmental stewardship, where different words convey subtle differences in the approach to and understanding of the responsible and careful treatment of the environment.

Adams (2006) stated that sustainable development is familiar and can be traced back to a conference three eras ago. It is argued that sustainability began at the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment when poverty was the primary concern (UNEP, 1972).

2.3.2 Nigeria Telecommunication Industry

Telecommunications have not exclusively become an essential need for human life, but they play a crucial role in connecting businesses and business data around the globe. It presents the most vital sectors of the world economy. The telecommunications trade is one of the most necessary areas of the world economy. The industry includes a share of all the challenges attributable to compelling rivalries from competitors. It uses over four of the total world's energies for its operations. The frequencies for communicating with the US vary in step with Federal Communication Commission reports. In the rest of the world, where mobile penetration is high, a similar has been noted Foretold. As mobile and net technologies unit gift, the image is extraordinarily transparent. There is little doubt that the telecommunications sector is in command of the emission of heaps of oxide and produces plenty of noise and unwanted radiation, both directly and indirectly. Radiation pollution is attributable to this sector.

The expansion rate of telecommunications remains high. Indeed, telecommunications is the fastest-growing sector in some developing countries. Carbon emissions from the global data and communications technologies (ICTs) sectors represent two percent of Internet emissions. This is identical to the average for the worldwide aviation sector. The world is fast becoming a universal hamlet and an essential instrument for communications. Telecommunication is, therefore, a player. Developments in the telecommunications sector worldwide occur rapidly, and innovation occurs at an incredible pace. The fundamental revolution is the mobile telephone system and static wireless telephone lines. Global System

of Mobile Communications (GSM). Communication is a key associated technology, a central thrust to any country. Developing drifts in socio-economic growth emphasize information and communication technology (ICT) in homes, associations, and countries like Nigeria. A significant reform policy in Nigerian telecommunications was introducing the supervisory authority body called the Nigerian Communication Commission (NCC) in 1992. The growth and increase of Nigerian telecommunications networks are influenced by the regulatory plan put in place by the supervisory authority, the Nigerian Communication Commission (NCC), to supervise the development of systems. This protects newcomers from violence from executives and guards the public against large companies.

They use their market influence to overcharge for poor services and hardware. Other reform policies have influenced competition, promotion, pricing structure, connectivity, flexibility, safety, and dependability. The National Regulatory Authority governing the telecommunications industry in Nigeria is called Nigeria Communication Commission Decree 75. It was created in 1992 by NCC and was also intended to loosen the communications sector in Nigeria, introducing private competition. The Commission has the following aims:

- 1.The formation of a supervisory setting for the supply of telecommunications tools: The entities
- 2.Enabling entry into the market by private businesspersons
- 3.Advertising of Enabling Valley's well-organized market

Under the supplies of the NCC Decree, the essential Certifying and Regulatory Agent Conditions for issuing licenses for the source of telecommunications facilities. Operational Licences and Certifications are issued to the following groups of telecommunications - trade dealings and fitting of station or other client buildings. Telephone telex and fax technologies. Delivery and process of a free payphone. They provide and procedure personal network connections, hiring cable, transistor communications, or cable, in Nigeria. There have been some trends in the sector. Universally the telecommunications sector has experienced swift development and invention over the past three decades. Telecommunications is a significant feature of globalization and internationalization. It can facilitate transactions over long distances and through national boundaries. The significance of telecommunications currently is undeniable. Such technology facilitates business activities, and collaboration offers significant support to federal revenues and creates many new jobs.

A Report by Frans-Man (2001) suggests the telecommunications sector can be grouped into three segments. The first is the tools segment, where the network components (switched broadcast systems) lie. Client sites kit is manufactured within the system. The second segment contains the circuit-switched 59 system, whereas the third segment is where telecom facilities – voice, fax, and improved facilities such as toll-free services are delivered. He further claims that because telecommunication awareness has been historically low, a cartel network has traditionally controlled the network segment of the telecommunications sector. In some countries, there was also a good amalgamation of network operations and tool construction. Other countries saw just quasi-vertical incorporation. In terms of growth, the nation's telecommunication sector began as far back as 1886 with the initial telegraphic submarine cable installed by the British company Cable & Wireless Ltd. The time between this installation and Nigerian independence in 1960 saw 18,724 fixed telephone lines installed (Okonji, 2013.)

Nigeria Telecommunication Limited (NITEL), a government-owned operator, monopolised the industry and came to dominate the telecommunications sector. (Mawoli, 2009). The services delivered by NITEL included the supply of fixed telephones, Telegraphy (Gentex), and Payphone. Its principal aim was to complement the organization's internal and external telecommunications and streamline telecommunications growth funds. Another objective is to offer easy marketplace entrees, as well as organized and cheap facilities. Ndukwe (2003) claims that between 1987 and 1992, there was no extraordinary progress documented in the presentation of NITEL, and customer demands were primarily unmet. This compelled the Federal Government to focus on improvements by partly giving some free hand to the telecommunications industry. The need to attract investment to develop a national ICT structure has preceded rule and functional changes leading to the liberalization of the telecommunication industry.

2.3.3 Framework and Governance Structure of the Nigerian Mobile telecommunication industry.

According to Popoola et al. (2009), the leading Key stakeholders in the Nigerian telecommunications sector encompass. The Nigerian telecommunications sector involves the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN), the Ministry of Communications, and the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) are vital entities in shaping and overseeing the

telecommunications sector. The federal government shapes sectoral development through policies, with the Ministry of Communications responsible for policy implementation.

As the independent regulatory body, the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) oversees and regulates telecommunications service providers or licensees, ensuring their activities align with government policies and regulations. The Commission consistently takes pride in achieving its objectives, regularly issuing quarterly Compliance Monitoring and Enforcement reports. The NCC communicates its regulatory activities to the public through these reports, showcasing its commitment to transparency and accountability.

The Federal Government is at the helm of affairs within Nigerian telecommunications and is effectively the overall director of telecom development. The Ministry of Communication gives policy advice to the telecommunications sector and the global director for telecom development. The relevant law that applies is the Nigerian Communication Commission law. The Ministry of Communication formulates broad policy goals and policy implementations, while the Nigerian Communications Commission has regulatory oversight. The Nigerian telecommunications industry is structured in the following ways. The Federal Government of Nigeria, Ministry of Communications, Nigerian Communications Commission, Nigerian Telecommunication Limited (NITEL), The Second National Operator – Globacom, and Other Licensed private telecommunication Operators and services. Table 2 below shows the roles of the government in Nigeria's telecommunication industry.

Table 2 Roles of government in Nigeria's telecommunication industry.

Entities	Duties
NITEL	Provide a technological foundation for societal interactions and a vast range of information-transmitting technology,
Federal Government of Nigeria	The role of government in the telecommunications sector is to provide overall direction for telecommunications development and to ensure consistency of policy around telecommunications and

	<p>other national systems, and it also enacts the necessary laws. It takes additional measures to support the national telecommunications policy.</p>
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Two factors account for phenomenal developments and rapid advances in technology. The Prepaid wireless billing IP technology Market Liberalization/Competition presents a democratic government policy. That improves services by eradicating the misuse of monopoly power to increase sector efficiency through competition, encourage innovation, and introduce advanced services. Attracting local and foreign investment enhances consumers' value through improved range and pricing and extends services to underserved areas. A new telecom policy was released in the year 2000, the hallmark of which was the blueprint for the full liberalization of the telecommunication sector. The implementation of the plan has resulted in some measures highlighted below. Incentives.

The constraint in the degree of overseas fairness partaking was removed. There was a decrease in the degree of importation taxes on telecommunication kits from 25% to 5% for the first two years—simplification of procedures for importing telecommunications equipment and developing related software. We are granting pioneer status to qualify and develop similar software and give pioneer status to qualified investors—fiscal incentives to encourage local manufacturing. Policy and Regulatory Intervention Growth of range plan for the Nigerian commercial spectrum management transported to the NCC Interconnection regulations and rules available landmark resolve of interconnecting disputes Settlement of Interconnection Rates Development of various laws n Establishment of Consumer Affair Bureau. Establishment of the Consumer Parliament. Tariff and Charges The decrease in purchase rates of new wires installed telephone lines retailed for a median end of 1999.

Nevertheless, low-end fixed lines sell for twenty thousand naira or lower. Analog mobile lines were slashed by 65% over the same time, from sixty thousand naira in 1999 to seven hundred and ninety-naira in 2003. Internet usage fees in cybercafé now vary between one hundred naira to one hundred and fifty naira for each hour, compared to six hundred naira to seven hundred and fifty naira for an hour in 1997. This signifies a 500% decrease in use costs over time. (Adopted by Nigeria 62 Communication Commission Report, 2014) Balogun (2000), the

development of telecommunication simplifies economic growth by offering efficient and straightforward interaction required to promote and boost business between Nigerian and its overseas associates globally. Tella et al. (2007) also agree that telecommunication has begun as an essential and crucial element of the

The philosophy and life of Nigerians had played a substantial role in communication and supported venture capital. (Ndukwe 2005) concurred that in Nigeria, the telecommunications business had faced exponential development in recent years, with about 113 million telephone lines linked to date. Nigeria has been termed one of the world's swiftest-growing telecommunications markets. The success can be attributed to the Nigerian government's goodwill and the enabling and conducive government policy and regulatory regimes environment. Nigeria's telecommunication industry has a growth pathway in the global telecommunication business. It started as just a monopoly business, rose to liberalization to a feeble competition, then developed and then the game and is presently grown to service invention. Among infrastructure is telecommunication, which contributes to every nation's development. Norton (1992) proposes that support within ICT is responsible for both the fixed cost of purchase of information and variable value in the marketplace (Roller,2001) and believes that infrastructure that belongs to ICT needs improvement. Hence, operation costs are reduced, and output rises for companies in every sector of any country. The world is fast growing, and there is an increase in the use and knowledge of mobile phones in all emerging economies.

The telecommunication business, particularly mobile, is performing a substantial part in the growth of the Nigerian financial system, despite expanding from a thirty-thousand-line subscriber center at the start of 2000 to 105.2 million links at the end of 2012 (Oketola, 2012). GSM has added many other aspects to the development of the Nigerian financial system, particularly in the fields of employing the generation, Foreign Direct Investment, and private investment. The latest Nigerian telecommunications changes have led to considerable capability investing, supporting service development and new technologies. Lee (2003) stated that the current innovations in telecommunications equipment had been an essential tool in enabling knowledge swaps to build a valuable product for shifting the nation into post-manufacturing and info-based fiscal increases.

In this present-day world, a contemporary telecommunication infrastructural expansion is necessary for local monetary improvement. Still, it is a requirement to participate in the

progressively driven world—markets and draw new ventures. World Bank (1995) stated that telecommunication infrastructural growth should be a crucial example of economic growth. Ajayi (2012) suggested that the telecom industry's biggest challenge is the issue of multiple taxation and various regulations.

According to him, the fundamental dilemma is the uncertainty of tax policy. Different faces include hurdles in gaining entry to the best way needed to fix some structure, destruction of kit, inadequate public electricity supply, and no availability of appropriate spectrum for the network rollout. According to the chairman of the Association of Licensed Telecom Operators in Nigeria, Adebayo (2012), telecommunication workers' disputes include epileptic power supply, insufficient telecommunication infrastructure, numerous taxes, and a corrupt system of roads.

2.3.4 Issues of Governance in the Nigerian Mobile Telecommunications Industry

Various researchers have considered the different methods by which the Nigerian government has affected the growth of telecommunications in the nation over the years. These scholars have meticulously scrutinized the various actions and decisions undertaken by the government in telecommunications, tracing back to 1960 when the government assumed complete control of the industry. Onwumechili (2001) underscored the self-centric priorities of government officials upon regaining power from the British colony. He elucidated that the initial focus on furnishing telephone services for administrative purposes could have helped realize citizens' aspirations for universal access to telecommunications. Examining historical developments by these researchers provides valuable insights into the evolution of government involvement in the telecommunications sector and its impact on accessibility for the general populace. He further analysed the government's development strategies to extend telephone services to the major commercial cities across the country.

He explained that the government should have released more funds budgeted for developing telecommunications in the country. He asserted that the government should have disbursed more funds designated for telecommunications development in the country. Consequently, the execution of development plans faced delays or was abandoned. In the 1970s, the Federal Government of Nigeria aimed to augment the number of available telephone lines; however, funding allocation challenges impeded this goal.

Nonetheless, according to Akwule (1991), the shortcomings of the initial national development plan were attributed to the military coup and civil war in the country. Onwumechili (2001) argued that the program's failure to achieve its objectives was primarily caused by the misallocation of funds by the federal government. Akwule (1991) believed it was feasible because the government had all the relevant resources. Akwule (1991) explained that the country, one of the world's leading oil producers, was financially capable of adding the proposed 700,000 new 64 telephone lines to the 50,000 already existing at the time. The oil boom and subsequent rise in oil prices experienced during the early 1970s further proved that this telephone expansion project could not have come at a better time for the country.

This project was not actualized like many other proposed government projects before it. According to Onwumechili (2001), the government's failure to perform the primary tasks of allocating a realistic budget and acquiring the necessary workforce for the execution of the proposed project brought this telecommunications development initiative to a halt. Ultimately, only 240,000 new telephone lines were fitted in the country. In 1985, the Nigerian government established the state-owned Nigerian Telecommunications Limited (NITEL) to provide better telecommunications services. However, Onwumechili (2001) explained that all these government establishments succeeded.

This creates the problem of unaffordability for telecommunications services. NITEL, the government monopoly, increased its tariffs for local and international calls throughout the country, making it almost impossible for the few with access to telecommunications facilities to afford communication services. As for those who resided in rural communities with no form of access to these facilities, life was unbearable.

According to Adomi (2005), citizens who lived in rural communities had to travel down to the cities to make calls and connect with relatives whenever needed. This system made communication almost impossible for most Nigerians, as most of the country's population did not reside in the urban cities. In considering the government's negative influence on the growth of communications within Nigeria, Onwumechili (2001) recommended that the government open the telecommunications market to other service providers. With the introduction of new market players, Onwumechili (2001) expected that the issue of costly call rates would be addressed. He also proposes that the government set up a national policy to ensure its commitment to extending telephone services to rural communities within the

country. Ajiboye et al. (2007) conducted a study on the impact of mobile telecommunications on the Nigerian rural economy. The descriptive research survey for the study selected a random sample of 1000 Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM) subscribers.

All of them were from ten different rural communities in the Western Nigerian state of Oyo. These respondents ranged from 25 to 50 years of age and comprised teachers, police officers, unemployed graduates, drivers, and itinerant traders. The result from the study evidence that the introduction of GSM to Nigeria had a significant impact on the country's rural economy. According to Ajiboye et al. (2007), GSM 65 created employment opportunities for the unemployed. Youth in rural areas, as the mobile communications operators and their various distribution chain components, hired individuals to support the running of their businesses.

The study also showed that the crime rate in rural areas had diminished because of mobile communications technology. Since more individuals possessed mobile phones, criminal activities were easily and quickly reported to the relevant authorities, who handled these activities accordingly. The earlier studies by Akwule (1991) and Onwumechili (2001) considered historical facts in determining the Nigerian government's overall contribution to the growth of the country's telecommunications industry. Onwumechili (2001) made an analysis that concluded that the growth of the communications industry in the years following the country's independence was stunted because of the government's actions and, in some cases, inaction. He believed that the government should have shown more interest in and commitment to ensuring the progress of this industry. As a result, very few Nigerians had access to telecommunications facilities, and even fewer could afford to use these.

Facilities. In contrast, a more current study conducted by Ajiboye et al. (2007) posed a different conclusion. By considering the country's current reality (i.e., the government's introduction of GSM to the country), as opposed to historical facts, Ajiboye et al. (2007) proved that the government had indeed done more to enhance the growth of telecommunications in the country. The study by Ajiboye et al. (2007) not only rendered the findings of Onwumechili (2001) for telecommunications access in Nigerian rural communities obsolete but also went on to prove that the government's active role in introducing the GSM single-handedly improved the welfare of citizens within these rural communities. When the study by Ajiboye et al. (2007) was conducted, government policies had been set up to ensure that telephone services were made available in the rural communities of Nigeria, and the

telecoms market had already been opened to accommodate other GSM service providers. The changing reality and facts of the Nigerian telecommunications environment rendered the recommendations put forth by earlier studies obsolete and inapplicable. This style will continue if the country's telecommunications industry grows and expands.

2.3.5 Challenges of sustainability practice in the Nigeria telecommunication industry

There have been several pieces of finding sustainable development. Edward (1987) used a Venn illustration to demonstrate that sustainable development has many styles, such as economic, environmental, and social sustainability. However, Pearce and Markandya (1989) argued that the Venn diagram approach is due to the complexity of operating separate economic, social, and ecological sustainability indices. They stated that the Venn methodology was incompatible with the Brundtland Commission Report, which underlined the connection surrounding the economic development, environmental degradation, and population pressure representing the three objectives. Economists have since concentrated on showing the nation and the environment as a single interconnected scheme with a united appraisal method (Hamilton, 1999; Dasgupta, 2007). Intergenerational fairness can be integrated into this method, as it has become a frequent practice in the economics of climate change economics (Heal, 2009). Effective policies that are compatible with increasing human welfare have been introduced. Arrow et al. (2004) and other economists, Asheim (1999) and Pezzy (1989 and 1997) have advocated simple reasons for sustainable development. The necessity of the wealth of a society, including human capital, knowledge capital, and natural-capital (as well as produced capital), should stay the same over time. Like Barbier (2007), others argue that solid sustainability and (non-depletion) of primary forms of natural capital may be appropriate. Sustainability reflects the need for a careful balance between economic growth and environmental preservation. It means "reaching the wants of the present-day generation without compromising the needs of future generations." The traditional definition of sustainability can be defined as a sustainable development path when the stock stays high "if and only if the stock of overall capital assets stays constant or rises over numerous times.

2.3.5.1 Poverty

Most developing countries worldwide are weak, particularly nations in Sub-Sahara Africa, Latin America, and Asia. 2007 African Economic Outlook (AEO), a journal of the African Development Bank (AFDB), African nations have sustained Gross development product

growth of 5.4 percent over the past five years. However, political stability, sound economic management policies, and an improved institutional environment have catalysed the growth process in some countries. Despite these economic trends, the scourge of poverty still exerts a significant impact on the African continent.

2.3.5.2 Rapid Population

Growth This fast population growth has put much stress on Africa's ecosystem. In several of the world's poorest regions, ever-increasing populace concentration has impacted critical and quickening, damaging the reserves these growing populations depend upon for survival. Though the rate and timing of fertility decline, the eventual size of the world population will depend on the growing community. This has led to land, water, and wood (fuel), resulting in water shortages and inadequate sanitation

2.3.5.3 Rapid Urbanization/ Urban

Development The predominant growth of Africa's population is projected to happen in urban regions due to rural-urban migration. New and challenging environmental problems have accompanied this unprecedented urbanization in Africa. A substantial percentage of inner-city residents in sub-Saharan Africa live in favela environments without permanent shelter or lawful human rights to their property. At least one-quarter of African town residents need access to electrical energy. The World Health Organization (2002) described that an expected 43 percent of urban dwellers had access to piped water a decade later; a lot has stayed the same. Trash dumping poses a significant health risk in many inner inner-city regions. Current patterns of urbanization need to be more consistent. They do not desire ecologically friendly, sustainable development in Africa (Affricate, 2008). It is essential to note that rapid population increases accompanied by massive rural-urban migration have led to extraordinary urban inhabitants' growth, occasionally at double the rate of national development. Therefore, only some governments are prepared to cope with the increased strain on existing municipal water resources and public health services. The subsequent environmental illnesses create severe health risks, increasing the statistics of individuals subjected to them. Such circumstances threaten to precipitate the collapse of existing urban infrastructure and create ripe conditions for pandemics and natural well-being crises.

Overcrowding, vehicular and industrial emissions, and poorly ventilated household stoves inflate the high environmental cost. Nigeria is an agricultural country, with about 70% of its

population of 140 million individuals involved in pastoral produce. The nation is also usually gifted. With plentiful natural supplies. The revenue of more than half of the active population in Nigeria directly depends on the environment through agriculture, animal farming, staking, trawling, forestry, and hunting. This only underlines the significance of the 7th Millennium Development Goal: to guarantee environmental sustainability (Todaro & Smith). However, numerous challenges threaten progress toward sustainable development goals in Africa, especially in Nigeria. The spike in food and power costs 2008 led to a severe food catastrophe. The consequent dropping 68 power rates has dropped some of the tension on power trade in nations. Still, food costs stayed above average.

The worldwide economic and financial disaster in 2009 worsened the condition. Expansion costs are dropping, joblessness is increasing, abject poverty is increasing, starvation and hunger are rising again, and the attainment of the Millennium Development Goals is in peril. Economic sustainability in Nigeria is about sustaining and maintaining a high-level natural expansion percentage of the economy to accomplish the Development Goals (MDGs). Nigeria's economy played well in the 1960s and early 1970s but severely in the last 20 years. However, ever since the late 1990s, the country has risen.

The sustainability of improvement is delicate for two purposes. First, substantial local investments do not back up development—second, Nigeria's financial system. Despite the donations of global international businesses and two-sided and non-governmental organizations to grow in Nigeria, the more aid the nation gets, the higher the degree of abject poverty, joblessness, and dispute. The nation's population is expanding at a geometrical pace without equivalent expansion in basic structure and social facilities such as electricity, roads, clean water, well-being, and learning resources. The country's entire area is exhausted, with low consumption capability in the industrialized industry, underdeveloped farming, and transportation sectors. The towns are overcrowded due to the high rural-metropolitan movement and inadequate urban organizing. Most residents who can no longer bear the congestion have legally migrated to developed countries or sought asylum.

2.3.6 Challenges of the Nigeria Telecommunication Industry

Reports from the Nigeria Communication Commission (NCC, 2009) show that historical data and telecommunications have always created the base of human presence. Driven by this reality, humans persistently seek to enhance the timely exchange of information and

communication processes with others. The most incredible legacy that 20th-century scientists have bequeathed to humanity is that the "Information Revolution" became feasible with the rough and swift growth and innovations in telecommunications and information technology. That no modern-day economy can be sustained today without an integrated telecommunications infrastructure is widely acknowledged. The Guar Ian (2017) report shows that for every US\$20 invested in telecommunications equipment, more than US\$6 is created in economic returns by its impact on local employment and overall financial growth. Therefore, an opening into telecommunications is critical to developing all aspects of economies, including manufacturing, banking, education, agriculture, and government—increasing telecommunications and information technology in almost all facets of human work. The radio communication revolution and the internet phenomenon have recently changed how people live and transact business. The telecommunication/information technology industry has taken center stage in world affairs and will continue to do so far into the foreseeable future. A report from the chief executive of Nigeria Communication Commission (2000) states that Telecommunications and information technology, as a result, have excellent present-day prospects for the formation of unprecedented wealth for Africa. It is reaching saturation point and has shifted attention to Africa as one of the last emerging two markets.

However, African nations must plan for this, create policies, and enable the environment to enjoy the full benefits of this new scramble for Africa. Such action is necessary to tap into the information revolution's opportunities for industrialized and intermediate economics. This challenge encapsulates the telecommunications challenges for Nigeria in the 21st century. When Nigeria gained independence in 1960, it had only 18,724 telephone lines. Since then, the fitted capability has increased to about 700,000 lines. Over the past four years, the subscriber base has increased by merely 10,000 lines per annum nationwide. The situation worsens, considering only around 400,000 lines are connected to subscribers.

The picture could be better, considering that only about 400,000 lines are connected to the subscriber. In the mid-1980s, cellular service was introduced in Nigeria, and today, the number of cell lines connected is just 20,000, representing an average annual growth rate of 1,25 subscribers per annum. Presently, there are 400,000 connected subscribers, and it may be reasonable to assume that at least half of that number connects corporate and government organizations with multiple lines. This might mean that up to 200,000 individual Nigerian

family units have telephone lines on their premises based on this analysis; it is evident. Following the statement by the chief executive of the NCC report (200), Nigeria is in dire demand of telecommunications services. This insufficiency of adequate infrastructure has adversely affected the nation's economic life.

Today, credit cards are less widespread in usage than in other countries because card authentication depends on machines heavily on reliable telecommunications facilities. The streets are congested because people must travel long distances to pass on messages that could be easily communicated over the phone.

All country industries are adversely affected, including healthcare, law enforcement, education, commerce, industry, and banking; a massive investment is urgently needed to support the abovementioned sectors and ensure rapid economic development to expand the Nigerian telecommunications network. The concept was to run the company as a fully commercialized entity. Even though the network growth rate improved following the birth of NITEL, it remained too small to compensate for the population growth price. This growth did not reflect the nation's improved wealth since the 1970s and the high demand for essential telecommunications services. The chairperson also discussed the financial challenges of the current industrialization and economic growth. The Federal Government in 1992 decided to encourage private sector participation in the sector to attract investment to expand the network more rapidly.

In line with the chairperson, the NCC speech (2000) shows that the NCC has been set up by decree 75 of 1992 to control the sector. However, the NCC Panel was constituted in July 1993, which marked the beginning of the liberalization of the telecommunications industry. Since the 7-year life span of the NCC, numerous authorizations have remained distributed towards private businesses to commence various facilities as (a) fixed telephony services, (b) mobile telephony services, (c) fixed satellite services (VSAT), (d) paging services () payphone services (f) internet services and other value-added services. However, he further stated that several of these licenses were issued several years ago, and only a restricted number have initiated business in each license class. The installed telephone services certificate has documented some reasonable contributions to the nation's installed base, contributing less than 100,000 lines to the network.

Therefore, queries have been asked why, despite the numerous licenses issued, no measurable impact has been made in the subscription growth base. The aims may be perceptible to the following: - political and economic isolation of Nigeria during the past military era, which affected investor confidence. Nigeria's telecommunication is the only transporter in the system; thus, all new entrants depend on her connection to their subscriber bases around the country. Therefore, Nigeria's telecommunication must urgently make an adequate investment to be competent to hold this. If such ventures are made, there is no doubt that the private operators will patronize the carrier's services. The critical provision should be that interconnections must not be denied to any operator duly licensed by NCC. A typical case is British telecommunication in the United Kingdom, which provides.

Internet services to all subscribers. The general electricity power supply situation must improve urgently for Nigeria to enjoy the full benefits of wireless systems deployment and Power backup systems for subscriber terminals in the case of fixed wireless networks suitable for 2 to 8 hours of battery life. Our outages could stretch between twelve to forty-eight hours; sometimes, the condition can only be explained as intolerable.

The second challenge is the local limited funding to finance a massive build-out. Without a large-scale deployment, there can be no economies of size. In a low-revenue environment, the system's price per line must be correct to guarantee a reasonable return on investment. Therefore, the order must be of enough size to ensure the vendors can achieve economies of scale and guarantee affordability for a more considerable number of people profitably for the operator. In summary, telecommunications present the infrastructure of the emerging global information society when Nigeria is entering the 21st century; her challenge is growing telecommunications to rapidly support people economically. The challenge for leaders is to develop policies that will quickly increase Nigeria's economy's capacity to compete effectively with other economies. A robust telecommunications infrastructure is crucial for attracting local and foreign investments to boost Nigeria's economy, given its population of over 100 million.

Given its potential economy, Nigeria remains Africa's most important market. Nigeria must tap the full potential of this market with a good telecommunications and information technology base. For enterprises in today's highly competitive world, the strategic components of developing and maintaining a competitive edge are telecommunications and information management areas, including broadband and Internet connectivity to distance learning.

2.3.7 Current Sustainability Practice in Nigeria's Telecommunication.

Chakraborty and Nandi (2011) explored the interplay among ICT infrastructure, the diffusion of ICT, and its impact on economic growth in developing and emerging economies. Their approach involved employing a Granger causality test. Sassi and Goaiied (2013) also utilized a dynamic panel model with system estimators. The results revealed a negative direct correlation between financial development levels and economic growth changes, particularly concerning diminishing levels. However, both studies consistently demonstrated a positive relationship between ICT proxies and economic growth, which is more pronounced in emerging economies than in developing ones (Chakraborty & Nandi, 2011) (Sassi & Goaiied, 2013). Chakraborty and Nandi (2011) emphasize the significance of investing in ICT for economic growth, urging a transition to the ICT threshold to leverage a positive relationship between financial development and economic growth. Failure to diffuse ICT hampers economic growth and diminishes the effects of commercial development, urging emerging and developing economies to address this issue and bridge the digital divide locally.

Chakraborty and Nandi (2011) emphasize the pivotal role of ICT investment in fostering economic growth, advocating a shift toward the ICT threshold to capitalize on a positive correlation between financial development and economic growth. Failure to diffuse ICT restrains economic growth and weakens the impact of commercial development. Emerging and developing economies heed this call to close the digital divide, and local and foreign direct investments in ICT are increasing in emerging economies (Sassi & Goaiied, 2013).

This will impact economic growth but will also have an unintended effect on the level of electricity consumption by market participants (corporations and individuals), as evidenced in Sadorsky et al. (2012). Sadorsky (2012) evidenced a positive relationship between ICT development and electricity consumption (Sadorsky, 2012). Jayant & Gowda (2014) evidenced attempts to increase sustainability awareness among corporations in emerging and developing economies. Corporations in both developed and emerging economies have faced similar challenges in meeting shareholder maximization goals as part of their economic sustainability pillars while maintaining the same purpose-driven focus on attaining social and environmental objectives within the sustainability dilemma. Sustainability practices in developing economies such as Nigeria occur because of the scarcity of amenities and infrastructures available to companies. Currently, these practices can be categorized as follows for this research.

The state of electricity access in Nigeria, access via renewable forms as an alternative to electric power in Nigeria, and the value of human beings and natural capital. Nigeria is the largest country, both concerning population, and economy, in the sub-Saharan Africa region. It is experiencing an increasing electricity demand because of population growth and telecommunications density. As an emerging market economy, Nigeria has one of Africa's fastest and most significant savings regarding economic activity. It is argued that an intermittent electricity supply stifles Nigerian economic growth due to old infrastructure and distribution issues (Oyedepo, 2012). Three pillars for creating a stable economy with a sustainable energy development framework are proposed for Nigeria; the first is the citizens' social welfare. However, the first pillar can be attained without considering the increased productivity from ICT, leading to increased productivity and social welfare.

The increased productivity has attendant increased environmental pressures and carbon emissions. Energy access has been used interchangeably in modern energy (electricity and liquefied natural gas). Conventional energy (biomass) and various definitions of energy access exist in the international theatre of the development Programme (UNDP); Sustainable Energy Group found that energy within the African context has a nuance of being construed like; electrical energy, contemporary fuels, mechanical power, cookery fuels and better cooking stove (UNDP, 2009). In Nigeria, energy infrastructure development has not yet been able to keep up with economic development at the current infrastructure investment level (Aliyu et al., 2013). A critical perspective of this is that a lack of adequate support may hamper the pace of economic development. Most households and businesses rely on electricity generated from diesel-powered generators to meet demand.

This method of generating electricity is dirty, intermittent, inefficient, and labour-intensive, with its high carbon content. Nigeria's energy potential is one of the largest worldwide. Still, when energy potential is coupled with an understanding of access and utilization issues, a full-scale deployment and mobilization of energy access can be achieved. According to (Ouedraogo, 2012), the shortage of modern energy (electricity) services that are clean, effective, and environmentally sustainable impedes economic growth and sustainable development, poverty decrease, and attainment of the Millennium Development Goals (MDG). For Nigeria to benefit from the potential of the renewable energy mix, an understanding of the opportunities and barriers to renewably generated electricity is crucial. The issues around the plenary on sustainability remain paramount in the business world.

Different persons and organizations within the business sector have observed this trend. Sustainable business between renewable energy consumption and economic growth theory is explored in detail in the literature.

The quality of human and physical capital drives productivity, and human capital requires education, while the active development of human capital requires deploying services-based resources. These require an efficient electricity supply that is available and affordable to operate and grow. As such, the case is presented for alternatives to the inefficient and unsustainable status quo. The industrial body of manufacturers in Nigeria spends over \$11 million per week operating independent power plants using diesel-powered generators (a concept referred to as the self-generation option) (Aliyu et al., 2013). The acute electricity shortage is worsened by the low electricity capacity utilization, which, as of 2011, stood at 49%. The same deficiency affects the services industry, whose electricity consumption load requirement may be much lower than manufacturers', making a case for micro-generated electricity.

A study done in 2002 found that only 6.2% of companies depend merely on the national grid for electricity supply, while over 40% of the operational price of the extra 93% was made of the self-generating rate of electricity. There has been a 5% rise to 11% of companies dependent only on the national grid for electricity supply research (Aliyu et al., 2013). Therefore, the firm can put the practice in place to do sound corporate with an economic break-even.

2.3.8 Evaluation of Current Sustainability Practice in the Nigerian Telecommunications Industry.

The Nigerian telecommunication industry is now the fastest-increasing market in Africa, and it is among the ten fastest-rising telecommunication businesses in the world. Making a profit and reducing costs is a universal economic idea, particularly in industrial, construction, services, and services within companies. Although cutting down on costs, one of the major tasks to tackle is strategic sustainability, partially due to the present trends in CSR. Earlier studies have established that a sustainable practice within any business increases revenue growth and the business's worth. This has pushed many companies in Nigeria to implement and create sustainable chain theories and practices to lessen the total cost of procedures; between 2003 and 2015, extensive development occurred within the Nigerian telecom

subscribers' base. This development has highlighted the energy needs of service providers to distribute telecom services. Henceforth, measures to save energy and reduce GHG are among the fewer harmful ways towards sustainable business practices within the telecoms sector.

Early capital ventures in business make it extremely hard for new service providers to join the industry and prosper. In recent years, the industry has been more competitive as the old network providers search for better ways to make amends and make their rates acceptable to subscribers. This move has led telecommunication companies in Nigeria to search for methods to reduce running costs and overheads. Nigeria's energy potential is regarded as significant. Still, only when energy potential is coupled with an understanding of issues surrounding access and utilization can the full-scale deployment and mobilization of energy access be achieved.

The extent of the state literature focuses on sustainability issues in developed economies, where high levels of efficiency have been completed. Some authors have focused on emerging economies where the most substantial collective gains and knowledge progression can be made. (Jayant & Gowda, 2014) The academic perspective of sustainability is that there are dilemmas in emerging economies, Inequality in knowledge production, and the geographic dispersion of IPCC panel lead members and reviewers. Developing economies have some of the fastest uptakes of ICT in the world. As observed in earlier literature (Kanter, 2008; Sadorsky,2012), ICT is responsible for 2% of global GHG emissions; the economist claims this will increase to 8% by 2020 from the powering of servers and cloud computing. Chakraborty & Nandi (2011) and Sassi & Goaid (2013) investigated the relationship between ICT infrastructure, diffusion of ICT, and impact on economic growth in developing and emerging economies. Chakraborty and Nandi (2011) applied a Granger causality test, while Sassi and Goaid applied a dynamic panel model with system estimators.

Their findings indicate a negative direct relationship between financial development levels and economic growth changes. However, both studies evidenced a consistent relationship between ICT proxies and economic growth. The relationship was positively reinforced in situations of emerging economies more so than in developing economies (Chakraborty & Nandi, 2011) (Sassi & Goaid, 2013). Both Chakraborty and Nandi (2011) and Sassi and Goaid (2013) posit that investment in ICT is critical for economic growth, and they recommend moving to the ICT threshold to influence a positive relationship between financial

development and economic growth. Emerging and developing economies heed this call to close the digital divide, and local and foreign direct investment in ICT is increasing in emerging economies (Sassi & Goaid, 2013). This will impact economic growth but will also have an unintended consequence for the level of electricity consumed by market participants (corporations and individuals), as evidenced in (Sadorsky, 2012). Evidence of a positive relationship between ICT development and electricity consumption (Sadorsky, 2012) (Jayant & Gowda, 2014) evidenced attempts and increased sustainability awareness amongst corporations.

This is particularly relevant in emerging and developing economies like Nigeria in emerging and developing economies such as Nigeria. Corporations in both developed and emerging economies face similar challenges in meeting shareholder maximization goals as part of their economic sustainability pillar while maintaining the same purpose-driven focus on attaining social and environmental objectives within the sustainability dilemma. In Africa, based on the World Bank classification of countries into bands, it was found that telecommunications had a varying effect on different socio-economic classes, with the highest impact being on the low-income.

This was partly caused by the diffusion of mobile telecommunication rather than fixed telephone lines. Countries classified as low-income were sub-Saharan African countries. Nigeria, one of Africa's most 76 populated countries, was among the low-income classification. This has implications for social justice and equitable development (Aliyu et al., 2013). The Dow Jones Sustainability indices underscore the centrality of the three pillars of sustainability, where "best practice "has been documented for over a decade for companies Operating in various sectors. ARUP has designed the sustainability SPEAR the ISO 14000, and Equator principles are further sustainability measures and benchmarking tools. These can be modified for sustainability studies focused on the Nigerian telecommunications industry as innovative interventions, and they are a starting point in analysing the telecommunications services industry in Nigeria.

2.3.9 Benefits of sustainability practices in the telecommunication industry in Nigeria

Numerous banks offer e-financial services through mobile platforms, allowing clients to review transactions, access exchange rates, request statements, check balances, and buy mobile credits (Frimpong, 2009).

Frempong (2009) indicated that the country still needs to develop financial services based on mobile platforms despite these developments. Only a few used the services. These services suggest they could be more assertive, even in the commercial and metropolitan areas of the country. Despite this, however, he believes that it is conducive and favourable. The macro-environment and financial sector liberalization are expected to drive the introduction of comparable services, fostering economic development without a doubt. Nigeria's mobile service providers, namely MTN, Airtel, Glo, and Etisalat, have actively contributed to social and financial aspects, aiming to foster economic development (Koufie et al., 2012). As in other Sub-Saharan African nations, mobile banking is gaining prominence in Nigeria, offering convenient financial services to users.

An example of digital services via mobile phones that have moved beyond urban centers to peripheral surroundings and beyond. There has been uptake and usage in the rural areas of Nigeria. According to Ericsson (2014), such regions in Sub-Saharan Africa typically experience significantly more social challenges. For example, rural populations in Nigeria face challenges like unemployment and inadequate transportation. Mobile banking addresses these issues by providing affordable access, reducing travel demand, minimizing transaction costs, and contributing to financial inclusion (Ericsson, 2014).

As with other sub-Saharan African countries, there is a keen interest in mobile financial services. Airtel, MTN, and Glo provide mobile money transfer services in Nigeria. The support of mobile money continues to gain momentum in Nigeria, where 16 percent of adults Within the last year, individuals have utilized mobile phones for activities such as bill payments and money transfers. This invention is boosting financial inclusion at all levels of society across the region. If, as indicated by Ericsson (2014), 58 percent of mobile users in the area show interest in the usage of mobile banking and mobile wallets in the future, it is a likelihood that there will be an upsurge in this service in Nigeria, which provides significant access to financial services in the country. Companies hold significant power when it comes to influencing consumer purchasing behavior. Corporate marketing of brands and products can encourage environmentally responsible purchasing behavior among consumers.

As civic concern for the environment increases, there is an emerging trend toward incorporating environmental awareness, sustainable initiatives, and green marketing within corporations' core values and management plans. In setting out corporate sustainable development principles, the first requirement is communicating information actively and

openly to the public. Incorporating environmentally responsible design, products, and processes into one's business, coupled with openly sharing information on corporate sustainability, can help promote a positive and sustainable company image. This impacts the product allegiance amongst clients, business success, and the sustainability of the natural environment. The worldwide population has exceeded the seven billion mark and is still proliferating.

This increment and, therefore, the increasing demands of the growing population push everything towards breaking point. Environmental degradation and pollution of the ecosystems are among the foremost issues. This threatens the lives of many organisms. The heating could be more balanced. Pollutions account for many diseases and, therefore, the degradation of the quality of life in many.

Fragile areas. Property is essential to all companies and technologies. The telecommunication sector is the primary omnipresent technology sector in the world. Since the arrival of cellular communication technologies, telecommunication towers (transceivers) have been found in most areas where human settlements are located. In the regions where electricity is unavailable, energy to the towers is supplied through various sources, specifically diesel generators and battery systems. Therefore, this technology sector directly impacts the setting and the scheme the companies and technologies use.

2.3.1 MTN Telecommunication Company

Nigeria Report shows that MTN Nigeria Communication is a part of the MTN Group, one of Africa's leading mobile telecommunications businesses. The business entered Nigeria on May 16th, 2001. It made the first phone call after the internationally lauded Nigeria GSM sale, directed by the NCC. The firm set up its commercial operations in Lagos, Port Harcourt, and Abuja. It presently delivers services in 223 towns, serving over ten thousand communities. MTN annual sustainability report (2014) MTN Nigeria Communication has a numerical microwave broadcast support, a 3,400-kilometer Y'elloBahn. The facility was declared open by the president of Nigeria in January 2003 and is believed to be a costly statistical microwave broadcast structure. The Y'elloBahn has assisted the company in improving the quality of MTN. MTN's sustainability report shows that the company has an existing sustainability practice. Different approaches to sustainability practice consider the pillars of sustainability (economic, social, and environmental). MTN annual sustainability report (2017).

2.3.1. 2 How MTN ensured a sustainable impact in 2017

The company has executed a few meaningful solutions. The highlights include tackling mobile money fraud in Uganda and reducing the cost of communications in several of their markets. To improve internet accessibility and explicitly focus on the needs of various small and medium-sized enterprise customer sub-segments, these actions are carried out to support their role in creating jobs and spurring economic growth. They aim to support innovative start-ups and women and youth in businesses. The aim is to increase the number of cooperative partnerships. The company partners with local authorities, social enterprises, international agencies, and vendors to tackle environmental challenges, such as responsible electronic and electrical waste management. They have continued to listen actively to the customers and to issues raised by the stakeholders on several matters over the years to improve their impact. MTN annual sustainability report (2017).

2.3.13. Some of the key challenges that may affect MTN's sustainable impact.

There are some impediments to the growth of digital inclusion and sustainable influences rooted in structural industry constraints, such as access to enough radio spectrum to enable service rollout, energy shortages, or the cost of capital needed for infrastructure rollout. Other challenges include an increasingly uncertain regulatory, economic, and competitive environment and ensuring communication costs are more affordable to the telecommunication industry. MTN has outlined six strategic pillars, the areas needed to build the business sustainably. These include paying attention to the experiences that the customers have with MTN and enhancing the data and digital services offered while ensuring technical excellence, amongst others. MTN has a long-term commitment to collaborate with a diverse group of stakeholders. Governments, communities, international agencies, and vendors across our ecosystem – to identify and deploy innovative solutions designed to tackle broad societal challenges and improve how customers work, play, and live. The company believes in approaches that help address some of its challenges to make a sustainable impact on the environment and society. MTN believes the focus for 2018 The belief is that every individual should enjoy the advantages of a modern and connected lifestyle. Intending to ensure that the products and solutions are tailored to improve the quality of life of the diverse and unique customers, no matter where they may be. (MTN annual report on sustainability 2019) MTN actively focuses on ensuring sustainable livelihoods and healthy natural environments in the countries in which it operates. MTN Annual Sustainability Report (2017)

2.3.14 Organisational background

MTN Nigeria began operation on May 16th, 2001, from Lagos, then Port Harcourt. Lastly, Abuja, with a capital investment of \$ 285 million to get a GSM license in Nigeria in January 2001 after investing U.S. 1.8 billion in the construction of the mobile telecommunication set-up in Nigeria. MTN offers services to Nigeria's two hundred and twenty-three towns, cities, and community districts.

This has covered Nigeria's thirty-six states, including the federal capital tertiary. The company involves the basic product principles of leadership, affiliation, honesty, invention, and connecting people to family, friends, and opportunities. To improve excellent client services, MTN also launched a self-help toll-free 181 client-care lines through which subscribers can solve their often-asked queries for free. MTN increased its network power to consist of a new numbering array with the prefix 0806, making Nigeria implement a new numbering method, having sapped its original subscriber numbering of 0803. The company has over 55 million subscribers, delivering the cellular network to gain access to ICT and offer answers to millions of Nigerians, linking whole areas and the rest of the entire globe. Since its launch in 2001, MTN Nigeria has become the largest mobile machinist in Nigeria and the West.

Africa. Currently, the company is chasing new expansion openings in the data and ICT room to spin out a range of inventions and services, plus ICT products. MTNN has fifteen service bases, one hundred and forty-four link shops, and two hundred and forty-seven connect spots in every federation state. The company plans to provide the Nigerian market with a new digital world. MTNN is 75.81% owned by MTN International (Mauritius) Ltd (MTN).

Further, is 18.7% held by Nigerian shareholders through objective vehicles, 2.78% and 1.76% owned by public networks NIC B.V., and finally, 1.76% owned by Public Investment Corporation Society Ltd. MTN has stretched its level of obligation to the environment by being the first to launch bio-degradable recharge cards, which do not affect or harm the environment. They present the use of MTN- charge known as MTV Plus. This is a computerized way of topping up airtime to phones as an alternative to purchasing recharge cards; this has lessened paper use.

The MTNN is coordinated from one hundred and seventeen (117) switches across the country in the following orders: Lagos (25), Abuja (13), Asaba (15), Owerri (13), Kaduna (6), Enugu (9) and Benin.

MTN's May 2018 financial report shows an increase in the first quarter of 2018 in the subscriber base of 4.3 million subscribers. This is to peak at 54 million subscribers. By the end of March 2018, despite all the disputes the business had encountered in earlier years, The breakdown in these rises shows a net addition of 2.3 million at the end of quarter 2018 and a 2.0 million net addition in quarter 4 of 2017. This accomplishment was achieved as a rise in the sim registration mark. Another supporting element to this rise is the rollout of 2983G and 1744G sites, with the 4G operation in the top 10 towns nationwide. MTN Nigeria's methods are supported across all areas of their business. Following guidelines and approvals, related laws, and rules, the company continues to improve, and 81 supports governance constructs, policies, and procedures to help the operational environment and strategy. Regarding the corporate structure, the group board is the highest layer. The board committees under this group are social and ethics, audit, risk management and compliance, and corporate governance, followed by nominations and remuneration and human resources. The next group is the Executive Committee, and the Compliance Committee oversees the sourcing, operations, strategic talent review, treasury, and group transformation.

2.4 Conceptual framework

The key emphasis is to improve Nigeria's telecommunication industry sustainability practice using the best practices for sustainability. The literature identified some of the factors affecting sustainability practices in Nigeria telecommunications. To the authors' knowledge, there needs to be more literature on sustainability practices in Nigeria. These issues, corroborated by the empirical findings in the available research, led the researchers to conclude that there needs to be a gap in applying efficient and effective sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunication industry, which requires attention. Consequently, the researcher presents the design of an applicable method for the sustainability model for the Nigerian telecommunication industry called the Nigeria sustainability practice model (NSPM) to improve existing sustainability practices in Nigeria's telecommunication to move this forward. The situation in Nigeria showed no consistent and effective formal mechanisms for sustainability practices in the industry. It could be difficult for the researchers to conduct an objective assessment. The focus of the research underpinning this study was modified to consider the applicability of sustainability value as a medium for improving sustainability practices in Nigeria. Telecommunication. This study aims to present a critical model. The outcome of this study is a model that shows the current sustainability practice. This is

dependent on these factors: (a) the existence and applicability of sustainability value to solve problems of Nigerian telecommunication service; (b) benefits of sustainability Value; (c) an NSPM. An increasing body of evidence from existing literature points to the need for better practices in the telecommunication sector in Nigeria and other African countries. Telecommunication organizations, such as NCC, have pointed out the economic growth rate, deforestation, urban development, rapid population design of macroeconomic policies, and inadequate public sector reforms. Other reasons are weak institutions providing basic amenities such as security, electricity, and water; poor governance; and the absence of transparent democracy (Therkildsen, 2001). This study has analyzed the literature on sustainability and designed a conceptual framework with different variations to give an overall picture of this study's findings, make conceptual distinctions, and organize ideas after doing a literature review on this study. The specific variable is being identified.

This conceptual framework is built using the variables collected from the literature studied using the research objective as the reference for the construction. The study intends to answer the research questions to address the knowledge gap. The variable above is represented in a shape box describing sustainability practices in Nigeria, and this variable is thus created. Current sustainability practice in Nigeria is the first variable. This study aims to study the current sustainability practice in the Nigerian telecommunication industry. Therefore, I studied different pieces of literature to understand the current sustainability practice in the industry using the Nigerian context. This relates to research objective one, critically reviewing some literature on sustainability practices in the telecommunications industry considering Nigeria's context. Best practice initiative is the following variable.

This is the ideal base for this study; hence, the Call Nigeria sustainability practice model has been developed considering the different factors that have inhibited sustainability practices in Nigeria's telecommunication. The outcome is an improved sustainability practice in Nigeria. On the top is the existence and applicability of best practice initiatives for productivity and sustainability.

2.4 .1 Conclusion of a chapter.

This chapter presented a literature review on sustainability practices in the mobile telecommunication industry. It started by reviewing the literature on the concepts and theories of sustainability practices and their various associated components and approaches.

Business sustainability, the global telecommunication industry, and the telecommunication industry in Nigeria were all discussed. The specific areas it considered included policies and practices, current sustainability practices, and Nigeria's telecommunication industry. The literature review also examined how the telecommunication industry articulated and applied the sustainability concept. It highlighted the importance of sustainability practices and looked at the main drivers and barriers influencing MTN Communication Ltd, which is the case study presented in this and Nigeria telecommunication. The divergence of ideas debated above shows the intricacy of the concept and evidence that sustainability is vaguely defined. Thus, this research concluded that no clear and mutual understanding of sustainability exists. However, sustainability in the telecommunication and petroleum industry is viewed as a distinct concept, encompassing a dual theme of economic enhancement and preserving the biosphere and humanity. These industries recognize the importance of sustainable practices, addressing environmental concerns, economic efficiency, and societal well-being.

While they share some common goals, the approaches to achieving sustainability may differ due to each sector's unique challenges and requirements. Ultimately, both industries acknowledge the need to balance economic growth with environmental and social responsibility for the long-term benefit of society and the planet. Since the advancements in the concept of sustainability, various Sustainability programs have been executed to develop individual organizations' sustainable development (Whiteman and Cooper, 2000; Savitz and Weber, 2006).

The sustainability theory, supported by scholars like Katrinli et al. (2017), Karunasena et al. (2016), and Galpin et al. (2015), emphasizes that true sustainability requires exceptional performance in environmental, economic, and social dimensions. In supply chain management, as Song et al. (2017) outlined, sustainability entails strategically and transparently integrating and achieving social, environmental, and economic aspects. Sustainability theory rests on three pillars: environment, economy, and society. Genuine sustainability demands exceptional performance in all three dimensions—environmental, economic, and social. Sustainability, as advocated by Katrinli et al. (2017), Karunasena et al. (2016), and Galpin et al. (2015), necessitates outstanding performance across environmental, economic, and social dimensions for authentic and enduring corporate sustainability. Incorporation and attainment of social, environmental, and economic goals in

the systemic management of crucial business progressions for improving the long-term economic performance of the specific business and its supply chains."

A "triple bottom line" concept has been developed by Elkington (1997, 2004), which acclaims that the only way to become truly sustainable is to balance social, environmental, and economic aims concomitantly and uninterruptedly. In a way that progresses, affordability protects long-term survivability and considers the consequences for future generations. In addition, sustainability is about the minimization of environmental impacts and the more intelligent management of an Enterprise's strategic, operational, and organizational Savitz and Weber (2006) assert that sustainability encompasses an enterprise's strategic, operational, and organizational aspects, as argued by Álvarez et al. (2017). the idea of 'Triple Bottom Line "offers a new framework to manage sustainable plans, and its primary purpose is to enhance the economic, environmental, and social performance concurrently a to provide the recovery of the techno-sphere and natural ecosystems. Even though this research aims to tackle all sustainability issues in the Nigerian telecommunication sector, it emphasizes the environmental side of sustainability. The study prioritizes specificity, focusing on the environmental dimension, with less emphasis on the economic and social aspects for concise research objectives.

3.0 Introduction to Methodology

This chapter delineates the research philosophy, methodology, and approach to fulfil the study's objectives. It offers a comprehensive overview of the research philosophy, emphasizing the pragmatic and mixed-method approaches. Two primary data collection techniques, structured and semi-structured interviews and document analysis, are detailed, accompanied by a discussion of their advantages, disadvantages, strengths, and weaknesses. The rationale for selecting qualitative and quantitative research methodologies, interviews, and document analysis is expounded upon. The research approach for collecting qualitative data from 12 key practitioners and the method used for gathering documentary data from MTN Nigeria's annual report are outlined. The chapter concludes by reporting the findings derived from document analysis and detailing the processes, procedures, and analysis methods employed for the thesis's qualitative phase.

3.1 Research philosophy

The philosophy underpinning this research is pragmatism, which seeks to address specific research questions for this study. The philosophy underpinning pragmatism is knowledge; our social experience influences our world perception. Each person's knowledge is unique as his/her experience creates it. Thus, as a pragmatist, the core thing is to solve the research objective and collect different opinions. This study aims for practical results since certain principles lead all qualitative methods. Denscombe (2014) advised that qualitative researchers should aim for effective outcomes. Hence, rather than staying in the philosophical views of qualitative research methods, the researcher adopted flexible approaches appropriate to tackle the research questions presented. I adopted the Constant Comparison of grounded theory as a method, not a methodology, as claimed by Glaser and Strauss (1967). From a pragmatic viewpoint, I put together the Constant Comparison method with the Framework Analysis method. The former was adopted for improved data collection, while the latter was for transparent and systematic analysis.

As a pragmatic researcher, I sit with refined realism, trusting that many social realities exist but are unrealistic to obtain the complete fact. This means I disregard the idea that objectivism or subjectivism can create social reality. As A Substitute, I accept that reality works at a time; it is not centered on the 86 dualities between reality being unbiased or within the mind. That practical way of thinking and doing that leads to a pragmatic solution is agreeable.

Epistemologically, any helpful way of knowing that leads to a pragmatic solution is agreeable. Knowledge is temporary and tentative; what is known can change later under different conditions. Persons create subjective meanings of their experiences to make knowledge (Bryant & Charmaz, 2010). The author's epistemological view required the author to keep up with relevant literature throughout this research. I conducted an early literature review to create a lens of investigation and theoretical perspectives for this research.

Corbin and Strauss (2008) agreed with the significance of the initial literature review in qualitative research. However, Patton (1990) has clarified that no perfect research strategy exists. All the research designs have their weaknesses and strengths. As a researcher, I recognize that the use of Constant Comparison in traditional Grounded Theory methodology has been vastly debated, as pointed out by Strauss and Corbin (1990 & 1998). The debates focused on using the approach in other qualitative research designs rather than attaching the Approach to Ground Theory research alone. However, the choice and integration of the constant Comparison approach during the data collection and data analysis stage of this research were underpinned by pragmatism. Given that the philosophical viewpoint of this study concentrates on approaches that would best address the research problems, I flexibly combined the Grounded Theory method, the Constant Comparison method for data collection, and the Framework Analysis method for data analysis. The constant comparison method systematically connected all data in the set, facilitating the extraction of comprehensive and rich information. In contrast, the Framework Analysis Method (underpinned with pragmatism) enabled me to provide a transparent, rational, and systematic approach to data management and interpretation processes of the data collected.

The collaboration of both methods was helpful in the accomplishment of the objectives of this research. From the axiological perspective, I identify the values and views put on the Constant Comparison approach by Straus and Glaser (1967) rather than resting in any antecedent conditions of the approach. I continued to focus on amalgamating the approach to this research for practicality. From a rhetorical point of view, this study is to achieve the requirements for my Doctoral degree. Therefore, most of the fiscal responsibility and methodological decisions rested on me. Again, networking with my professional colleagues during this research put me in a position where I had an embedded experience in practice.

Therefore, in authoring this thesis and talking about this research, I used a first-person singular pronoun (I) and possessive pronouns (my) to signify myself as the primary agent in

this project. When writing this methodology chapter, I did not use a conventional qualitative research model; instead, I embraced a mixture of recommendations for an upgraded and specific methodology chapter. I adopted a flexible and systematic writing style to prove the elements of this methodology chapter. In writing, I used the simple past tense, in the active form, to differentiate the information developing from me, and I used third-person pronouns (he, she, and they) for the respondents.

Lynch (2014) advised that since qualitative research acknowledges research by a person either as the researcher or the informer, it is more suitable for a qualitative researcher to use an active verb. Voice rather than passive voice in the methodology chapter. This is to show respect to the participating human researcher for depicting the subject (Researcher) doing the action. Even though some of the methods adopted for this research are written in simple past forms, the statements written in present forms suggest standard procedures and practices currently and frequently used in the principle of qualitative research. With this philosophy, I achieved the aims of the research. This study aims to assess how sustainability is practiced in the Nigerian telecommunication industry by critically exploring and analyzing the factors driving sustainability practice globally. Hence, identify the determinant of best practice for Sustainability with MTN Nigeria as a focal point.

The underlying philosophy of this research is pragmatism, aiming to address specific research questions. Pragmatism holds those social experiences, unique to everyone, influence knowledge. The focus is on practical results, acknowledging diverse principles guiding qualitative methods. Denscombe (2014) emphasizes effective outcomes for qualitative researchers. The researcher adopts a flexible approach, combining the Constant Comparison method from grounded theory with the Framework Analysis method for data collection and analysis.

As a pragmatist, the researcher embraces refined realism, recognizing multiple social realities while acknowledging the challenge of obtaining complete facts. The study rejects the dichotomy between objectivism and subjectivism, emphasizing a practical way of thinking and doing. Epistemologically, the researcher acknowledges the temporary and tentative nature of knowledge, shaped by subjective meanings individuals assign to their experiences. An early literature review establishes a lens of investigation and theoretical perspectives. The use of Constant Comparison in grounded theory methodology is debated, but the researcher's integration is guided by pragmatism. Combining Grounded Theory, Constant

Comparison for data collection, and Framework Analysis for data analysis aligns with the pragmatic viewpoint, facilitating comprehensive and rich information extraction.

From an axiological standpoint, the researcher values the Constant Comparison approach based on the works of Straus and Glaser (1967). A rhetorical approach acknowledges the researcher's embedded experience in practice and positions the researcher as the primary agent in the project. The methodology chapter uses an active voice, respecting the participating human researcher. The study aims to assess sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunication industry, exploring global factors driving sustainability and identifying best practices with MTN Nigeria as a focal point. The research philosophy, rooted in pragmatism, guides a flexible and systematic approach to address specific objectives and achieve practical outcomes.

3.2 Research Approach

The research approach refers to a plan and procedure comprising the various steps in producing the research. The Research approach is a strategy and process that conveys the broad assumptions applied in data collection methods, analysis, and interpretation. Hence, it is based on the research problem the researcher wants to handle. The Research approach can be divided into three types: 1. Deductive approach 2. Inductive approach 3. Adductive Approach. The relevance of a hypothesis is to act as a point of distinction between the deductive and inductive approaches. The deductive approach tests the validity of assumptions (or theories/hypotheses), whereas the inductive approach adds to new theories and generalizations.

On the other hand, adductive research starts with "surprising facts" or "puzzles," and the research process is devoted to their explanation. (Bryman & Bell, 2015). There is always a decision as to which approach to study a topic. Informing this decision researcher philosophical assumptions, the researcher brings to the study. The consideration includes inquiry measures (research designs) and the research methods used for data collection, analysis, and interpretation. The role of the research approach is to plan the type of research problem or issue being addressed, apply the researchers' knowledge, and interpret research for the audiences of the study.

Thus, this study's research approaches, designs, and applied methods characterized the research, from broad constructions to narrower procedures or processes.

3.2.1 Deductive Approach

Deductive approach reasoning occurs when the conclusion is derived logically from premises. The outcome is correct when all the assumptions are confirmed true (Ketokivi & Mantere, 2010). This kind of approach works from the more general to the more detailed. It can also be termed a top-down approach involving thinking up a theory about a topic of interest and then thinning the concept down to a more specific set of observations. Deductive perceptions are narrower and are concerned with testing.

Alternatively, they are approving theories. Deductive reasoning is a basic form of a valid argument. Deductive reasoning, or deduction, starts with a general report or hypothesis and examines the potential for a precise, rational decision. The scientific technique uses deduction to research and theories. That is, the researcher predicts what the observations should be because the theory is correct. The researcher moves from general - theory – to specific theory examples, hypothesis – observation, and confirmation. Wilson. (2010) believes that the deductive approach establishes a statement built on the prevailing theories and a research strategy to test the report. Beiske (2007) proposes that the deductive research approach examines a specific theory and seeks to see if that theory applies to a recommended setting. The deductive approach follows the course of reasoning. The argument starts with theory and ends with a new assumption. This postulation is tested by making contracts with observations and finally acknowledged or disallowed (Sneider & Larner, 2009.)

3.2 .2 Inductive Approach

The approach is the opposite of deductive reasoning. Inductive reasoning creates comprehensive overviews from exact observations. This involves statistical analysis followed by forming conclusions from the data. This is called inductive. The researcher uses inductive interpretation, moving from the precise to the general. We make many observations, determine a design, make a general, and deduce an explanation or theories. This approach has its place in scientists' scientific approach to creating hypotheses and theories. Based on the inductive approach, the number of observations is specified, and one can generalize the outcome to all or some sets in the same situations and circumstances. These overviews need to be verified, and some might be tested while others may be excluded.

Therefore, all philosophies built on inductive reasoning are tentatively falsifiable. Using the induction method, the investigator, as an observer, should reliably, without any biases and preconceptions, record what they detect with a neutral mind. Then, these explanations form a foundation on which theories and rules that make up the scientific information are created. Inductive investigators also trust that one can rationally generalize observations into general and comprehensive guidelines and that the proven scientific assumptions are approved (Godfrey & Hudson, 2010). Bernard (2011) states that in an inductive method, at the end of a study, an outcome is the observations, and theories are constructed. The inductive method comprises searching for a design founded on the observations and creating a theory for those outlines over hypotheses. No theory is pragmatic at the onset of the researcher's inductive reasoning. Moreover, the researcher enjoys complete freedom in defining the progression of research, and there is typically no assumption in the researcher's research process.

The researcher is seldom particular about the type and the nature of discoveries until the researcher's conclusion on inductive reasoning; the researcher uses observations to create hypotheses or abstract to define the settings being studied. (Lodico et al., 2010). Saghafi (2014) argues that the main benefit of the inductive method is that there is no need for any prefabricated outline or model. Indeed, while philosophies are generalized, they should be proven using a reasonable method (i.e., the deductive approach). Some have criticized the inductive approach to science. The main problem with the inductive is that inductive researchers are often influenced by inadequate information about the relationship and the research facts. Some claim that induction as a belief is falsifiable because it is founded on human observations. However, the principal disadvantage of the inductive approach is that it produces general theories and conclusions based on less detailed explanations. Therefore, the dependability of research results is often called into question. However, the inductive approach. The approach does not involve any creation of hypotheses. It begins with research questions, aims, and objectives that need to be achieved during the research process, and it then follows the Observation/Test- Pattern- Theory.

3.1.3 approach employed.

The research approach that is adopted for this study is inductive. Based on this approach, I started with exact observations to produce generalized philosophies and conclusions drawn from the research. The drives for using an inductive approach are to (1) to summarise extensive and diverse new data into a bar summary format, (2) to create explicit links between

the research objectives and the summary findings resulting from the raw data, and (3) to create of model about the fundamental structure of experiences or processes which are evident in the raw data. The inductive approach reflects the styles regularly shown in qualitative data analysis. Most of these studies report a model with three to eight main categories in the findings. The general inductive approach provides an efficient method for analyzing qualitative data across various research objectives.

The analysis results may be indistinguishable from those from a grounded theory approach. Using a general inductive approach is much easier to understand than other qualitative data analysis techniques. There are numerous pieces of literature. Strauss and Corbin (1990) claim that many specific approaches include grounded theory. They are linked to research that documents the underlying assumption and procedures (e.g., van Manen, 1990), discussion analysis (e.g., Potter & Wetherall, 1994), and narrative analysis (e.g., Leiblich, 1998). However, some analytic methods are "universal" and are not recognized within one of the exact styles of a qualitative study (e.g., Ezzy, 2002; Pope, Zieblandss, & Mays, 2000; Silverman, 2000). The inductive approach is a systematic technique for analysing qualitative data where specific objectives guide the analysis. The method is most suitable for a small sample approach using qualitative data.

3.2 Research Methods

This part concerns quantitative or qualitative methods, and the design researcher decides to use them. Merriam (2002) describes qualitative research approaches as individual designs aiming to enhance the understanding of social phenomena. Such designs encompass phenomenology, grounded theory, case study, ethnography, interpretive research, and narrative analysis. Each approach contributes distinct perspectives and methodologies to illuminate the qualitative complexities of exploring social phenomena. Interpretive research and narrative analysis. This research sought to understand how government and regulatory actions have shaped the Nigerian Mobile Telecommunications Industry. To achieve these, the case study research design was applied. Eisenhard's (1989) framework has been adopted and adapted for this study to create a theory using a conceptual model. Besides, the case study research design provides flexibility and step-by-step guidelines where appropriate to facilitate adaptation for another research framework (Yin, 2014). The research questions are narrowed down to focus on best practices in developed economies and practices among Nigerian telecommunication companies. In designing the research instruments for collecting

data, the investigator used multiple data sources, including documentation from MTN. MTN Nigeria Communication's company report was also analyzed during the fieldwork. The researcher used iteration in the data collection and analysis to facilitate the identification of themes. Checking for repeated logic/themes in cases and searching for the why behind relationships is to check for validity.

The researcher compared the findings and theory based on the constructs of the agreement's theories to find differences. Internal validity is created in this way, and improving the findings' generalization ability was possible. In previous studies, they were mentioned in the report on best practices for sustainability. Hence, the researcher studies them and copies their knowledge. The development of best practices has been driven by different strategies by different companies in developed countries. Cooperating with social responsibility has been a natural part of these companies for years, developing sustainability. Conducting a study of the different strategies put in place by various telecommunication companies provides a window into best practices in telecommunication sustainability. The research is undertaken in Nigeria to create a model to improve sustainability practices in Nigeria telecommunications using data on environmental, social, and economic circumstances. Data were taken from empirical findings on sustainability practice. It was creating a conceptual framework from findings in fieldwork.

3.2.1 Quantitative research

Quantitative research involves a logical scientific examination of quantitative phenomena and their relationships. Quantitative research employs mathematical models to evaluate theories and hypotheses relating to the natural world (Creswell, 2009; Fellows and Liu, 2003). Quantitative analysis is an iterative process involving evaluating evidence, redefinition of theories, and technical advancements. It is considered a distinct research method involving the collection of numerical data, often characterized as complex data (Fellows and Liu, 2003).

This is seen as a distinct research method, and it entails collecting numerical data, often defined as complex data (Fellows and Liu, 2003). Quantitative research traditionally includes the measurement of numbers. It offers the central connection between empirical observation and the mathematical expression of quantitative relationships (Petty et al., 2012). According to Santos (2006: 290), measuring such a phenomenon helps to "explain the connections

between variables by measuring cause-effect relationships." Similarly, quantitative research highlights a deductive approach to data collection and analysis.

According to Bryman (2008), quantitative research is practical, with much emphasis on data collection and analysis. Quantitative research is collecting numerical data that generalize across groups or explain a phenomenon using a structured technique that includes websites and questionnaires. A deductive approach establishes relationships. The study prioritizes theory testing, emphasizing its primary focus on the relationship between theory and research. The positivist approach aims to infuse research practices and norms of the natural scientific framework. The opinions and views of social reality as an external and objective reality are essential.

The quantitative researcher assumes an ontological standpoint, positing that the social and natural worlds are external systems independent of human systems and actions. In this context, the researcher adopts a value-free stance (axiology) throughout the research process, aiming for objectivity in findings by maintaining independence in quantitative data collection (Fellows and Liu, 2003). Quantitative researchers frequently assert objectivity in their findings, emphasizing independence from participants in the data collection process to uphold impartiality (Fellows and Liu, 2003).

Splitting the researcher from the participants helps to remove biases, leading to better and more reliable scientific outcomes (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Many discussions supporting quantitative research within the built environment have focused on such dependability, cogency, and scientific principles as significant strengths linked to research methodology. Quantitative studies, as asserted by Petty et al. (2012), are deemed to follow distinct knowledge generation processes compared to qualitative research. While the quantitative approach provides insights into cost implications and mechanisms viewed as

While claiming to be "systems of explicit rules and procedures" (Eldabi et al., 2002: 64), the quantitative approach lacks direct answers to social complexities (Klingner and Boardman, 2011).

3.2.2 Qualitative research

Qualitative research, on the other hand, includes the examination of incidences from the participants' viewpoint. Its central objective is to understand participants' opinions, behavior,

and experiences, and it is considered the most appropriate way of discovering issues based on social phenomena (Burke, 2007). Its interactive approach to inquiry adopts an open-ended data collection approach (Bryman, 2006). The qualitative method's core is collecting primary data in a non-numerical form, meaning it does not trust a number-crunching approach to attain its objectives. Unlike the quantitative research approach that depends on measurement and mathematical models, qualitative research uses rational inductions to decipher data, usually involving a few cases. Petty et al. (2012) intimated the significant benefits linked with qualitative research. They include its ability to produce more thorough explanations of human phenomena and in-depth analyses of complex social and cultural dynamics in a way that cannot be fully developed with a numerical measurement approach.

Harrison and Reilly (2011) also underscored the strength of qualitative research, emphasizing the profound knowledge and understanding gained when researchers delve into participants' experiences within their natural settings.

Harrison and Reilly (2011) proposed that understanding and meaning attached to such human experiences are considered a seal of qualitative studies. Accordingly, conducting qualitative research can support understanding the environment in which research participants act and how the environment affects their behaviors. Authors like Plano Clark (2010) and Eldabi et al. (2002) proposed that a qualitative approach provides the advantage of observing a phenomenon within its social context. By so doing, it offers more insight into understanding and flexibility in social matters. This study's data collection techniques to gather valuable information include interviews, documentation, and focus groups (Pope et al., 2002). The conventional application of case study, phenomenology, and grounded theory methods has proven highly influential within the telecommunications industry.

Authors such as Smith (2010) and Lombardi et al. (2011) have recently utilized qualitative research approaches to investigate sustainability, yielding credible and compelling results. Therefore, for these reasons, a qualitative research approach is adopted to investigate the social and humanistic perspective of the phenomenon.

3.2.3 Mixed method

This research method is when the researcher collects quantitative and qualitative data, intending to use those in the study similarly. Data collection and analysis is termed mixed-

method research. It is a common framework that attempts to complement quantitative data with quantitative data to overcome the limitations of each method.

3.2.4 method employed.

As a researcher, I can use qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods; however, I choose to use qualitative methods because the circumstances inform this at the time of this study. The qualitative method best answers the research objective, bringing the study to a conclusion. The qualitative method offers the researcher a profound understanding challenging to obtain through closed-ended surveys.

Respondents can freely disclose their experiences, thoughts, and feelings without constraint. The qualitative method offers it straight. Hence, the researcher can follow up on respondents' answers in real time, generating valuable conversation around a subject -something that is impossible with a structured survey. For this study, the researcher has employed the qualitative method using structured and semi-structured interviews during the fieldwork.

3.3 Strategy and Procedure

The survey approach employed a range of methods to answer the research question. The survey methods include face-to-face interviews and telephone interviews. The Face-to-face interview involves the researcher approaching respondents personally by calling their office, and a rapport has been built with MTN staff regarding the study. The researcher then asked the respondents questions and noted their responses. Face-to-face interviewing is a more costly and time-consuming method than the postal survey. However, the researcher chose this method to collect data to allow more in-depth data collection and comprehensive understanding, which gives the researcher a chance to probe for an explanation of responses from the MTN staff. The actual sample of respondents is selected to balance the demographic profile of the study. After identifying the positivist paradigm as the most suitable for this research, it is essential to design the study and select the most appropriate research methodology.

The research design and methodology are closely related to the philosophical assumptions of the chosen paradigm (Collis & Hussey, 2014). Strategies of review are "types of qualitative, quantitative, and mixed method design Creswell (2009) emphasizes that philosophical frameworks guide research designs, providing explicit directions for procedures within a

research design. However, there is yet to be a preferred research strategy. Instead, the researcher must answer the research questions and objectives (Saunders et al., 2009). Within the positivist paradigm, various business research methods can be employed, including cross-sectional studies, surveys, and experimental studies (Collis & Hussey, 2014). The choice of research approach hinges on the nature of the social phenomena under investigation (Morgan & Smirch, 1980). Where methodological selection is influenced by the kind of research problem and the accessibility of resources (Gill & Johnson, 1997).

Non-random sampling is applied; hence, it is a qualitative method to collect data from the focus group in MTN and Nigeria Communication Commission; this is typically used for exploratory work. Non-random sampling deliberately targets individuals within a population. There are three main techniques. (1) Purposive sampling: a specific population is identified. Only its members are included in the survey, using MTN staff as the focus group; hence, MTN has been selected as the case study for this study after critically considering other factors of telecommunication companies in Nigeria. The company was selected based on its sustainability background after some research was conducted during the pilot study before the main study began. (2) Convenience sampling: MTN and NCC staff are used as the sample because the company is the easiest to recruit during the study. Finally, (3) snowballing: the sample is identified as the survey progresses; as one individual is surveyed, he or she is invited to recommend others within the company to be surveyed.

The data accessed in this study were from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data were collected through conducting an interview. Journals as secondary data are "collected from an existing source" (Collis & Hussey, 2014, p. 59). Primary data analysis is the analysis of data by the researcher, who participates in collecting the data. However, secondary data analysis is "the analysis of data by researchers who will not partake in the collection of these data" (Bryman & Bell, 2007, p. 313). The primary data for this research was reported from an interview conducted with MTN and Nigeria Communication Commission staff.

Furthermore, the secondary data collected for this research were the reports from MTN Group Limited and the annual sustainability report for December 2017. This is accessed while visiting the company website and searching for published reports. The company sustainability report showing MTN Nigeria's performance was obtained from the MTN Groups database. There have been variations in how firms report Sustainability (Azim et al., 2011). Corporations

are moving from locating a section on sustainability in the annual report to delivering stand-alone sustainability reports (KPMG, 2008). When firms produce a single report, they consider sustainability as vital as monetary reporting (Holland & Boon, 2003). There has been an increase in the number of companies producing separate sustainability reports, which impacts the extent and nature of disclosure in sustainability practices have been examined (Deegan, 2002; Holland & Boon Foo, 2003). As noted by Frost et al. (2005) and Branco and Rodrigues (2008a), previous investigations into sustainability practices primarily focus on disclosure within annual reports, neglecting broader aspects of sustainability engagement. However, Branco and Rodrigues (2008a) stated that, currently, companies trust other methods to disclose sustainability information. As a result of the use and availability of those other methods, questions about the importance of the annual report as the primary method for reporting on sustainability matters. Concerns regarding reliance solely on annual reports for sustainability analysis have been raised by Frost et al. (2005). Holland and Boon Foo (2003) assert that such reliance may yield imperfect or inaccurate conclusions.

Moreover, Frost (2001) argued that when associations employ alternative media to report, less information about sustainability is delivered in the annual report. Therefore, in this study, interview sessions were conducted, and documents obtained from MTN were analyzed. Concentrating only on annual reports might have meant looking at important disclosures elsewhere, and this could have provided an incomplete picture of the volume of social responsibility corporations involved (Roberts, 1991; Unerman, 2000; Holland & Boon Foo, 2003; Michelin & Parbonetti, 2012). The annual sustainability reports were collected from 2015 to 2017. This period was selected for the following reasons: first, it is the most current period for which MTN has published 96 sustainability information for stakeholders; secondly, sustainability is a relatively new topic, especially in the telecommunication industry.

3.4 Time Horizon

This part deals with a timeframe for the research. These are two options for a researcher: either cross-sectional or longitudinal.

3.4.1 Cross-sectional

This alternative presents a snapshot view of a condition from a single point in time and confines the duration of data collection and research to a brief period. This option is an observational study, which means a researcher records information about their subjects

without manipulating the study environment. The benefits of the cross-sectional study design are that researchers can simultaneously compare many different variables. However, cross-sectional studies may need specific information about the cause-and-effect relationship. This kind of study offers a picture of a single tick in time; hence, it does not consider action before and after the snapshot.

3.4.2 Longitudinal

This kind of study, like a cross-sectional one, is observational. So, when researchers refrain from meddling with their topics, investigators conduct several observations of the same subjects in a longitudinal study, occasionally lasting several years. The benefit of a longitudinal study is that researchers can identify changes or alterations in the traits of the focus populace for both the group and individual stages. The fact is that longitudinal findings extend beyond a single moment. As a result, they can establish sequences of events.

3.4.3 Time horizon employed.

In the time horizon employed for this study, the researcher adopts a cross-sectional to compare different variables simultaneously and give a snapshot of the situation at a single point in time to confine the study's duration to full completion within the period.

3.5 Data collection

There are numerous methods available for collecting data. However, selecting a data-collecting strategy may be brave and based on considering the level of information and the depth of correctness and reliability of the findings required (Fellows and Liu, 2003). According to Fellows and Liu (2003: 105), collecting data for research is a "communication process" between researchers and respondents. Data collection forms the basis for examining and accepting the phenomenon under study. It is a collaborative aspect of a research process, and when agreed upon, it helps to guarantee the cogency of the research findings (Panas & Pantouvakis, 2010).

A key factor associated with this data collection technique is the nature, type of investigation, and information needed about a setting or context (Naoum, 2007). The actual reason for collecting data is to analyze and get some findings . This allows the researcher to gather enough evidence and thus draw the interpretations required to make significant decisions about the findings (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2010). Different data collection techniques may be

appropriate for selecting data collection techniques, which hinge on the chosen research methodology and study objectives (Naoum, 2007; Fellows and Liu, 2003; Pope et al., 2002).

Nonetheless, regardless of the method and methodology, the data collection techniques must meet the study's objectives. Moreover, the method used in collecting data must be sufficient to offer the information required to address Naoum (2007).

3.5.1 Secondary data

This data has already been published in books, newspapers, magazines, journals, and online portals. Usually, plenty of data is available from these sources, irrespective of the nature of the study area. Therefore, applying a suitable set of standards to select secondary data for research is vital in increasing research validity and dependability. These principles consist of but are not limited to the reliability of data collected.

3.5.2 Primary data

Primary data is the collection method divided into two groups: quantitative and qualitative. Quantitative data collection methods are based on statistical calculations in several structures. This technique of collecting qualitative data and analysis comprises questionnaires. Quantitative methods are more affordable to apply and can be used within a shorter time than qualitative methods. However, due to an elevated level of standardization of quantitative methods, it is convenient to make comparisons of findings. Qualitative research methods, on the other hand, do not include numbers or mathematical calculations. Qualitative research is strictly linked with words, sounds, feelings, emotions, colours, and non-quantifiable elements.

Qualitative studies ensure a better understanding, and qualitative data collection procedures involve interviews, questionnaires, focus groups, observation games or role-playing, and case studies. Choosing between quantitative or qualitative data collection methods relies on the field of study and the research aims and objectives. For this study, the researcher collected secondary data through journals, articles on previous works on sustainability for telecommunication, books for literature review, and the company's website to collect a document for analysis. Therefore, a case study approach was used in primary data collection. An interview was conducted with the general manager of sustainability at MTN from the health

and safety department staff of MTN Nigeria. The senior manager of NCC was also interested in achieving the research objectives and questions.

3.6 Sampling and sample size.

What sample size is needed for a survey? There is no conclusive answer to this question: large samples with thorough selection are more effective as they will generate more precise results, but data collection and analysis will be uniformly more time-consuming and expensive. The objective sample size for a survey varies on three main factors: the resources available, the objective of the research, and the statistical quality necessary for the survey. For qualitative surveys involving interviews, a smaller sample size is appropriate. Webster (1985) defined a sample as respondents selected from a larger population for a survey, emphasizing the process of selecting a representative part to determine the characteristics of the entire population. The sampling process involves selecting an appropriate subset of a larger population to obtain relevant information about the population. In his 1996 journal article, Ma explained that qualitative researchers often employ one of three sampling strategies: convenience sampling, judgment/purposeful sampling, and theoretical sampling. Marshall (1996) explained that convenience sampling is the least rigorous technique among the three, which involves selecting the most accessible research subjects.

In contrast, purposeful sampling involves seeking the most productive sample to address the study's research questions. Coyne (1997) describes theoretical sampling as rooted in grounded theory, analyzing qualitative data to develop a theory.

Coyne (1997) explains that the last theoretical sampling procedure is soundly rooted in the grounded theory research design, focusing on analyzing qualitative data to produce a theory. For this research, purposeful sampling was applied, aligning with Marshall's (1996) notion of theoretical sampling. This intentional approach involves constructing interpretative theories from emerging data and selecting new samples to scrutinize and refine these theories. For this research, purposeful sampling was applied. This method allows for the intentional and strategic Concerns regarding reliance solely on annual reports for sustainability analysis, which have been raised by Frost et al. (2005). Holland and Boon Foo (2003) assert that such reliance may yield imperfect or inaccurate conclusions.

3.6.1 Qualitative Sample Frame and Size

The telecommunication industry focuses on MTN because it is one of Africa's biggest suppliers of communications services with an unobstructed vision to lead the delivery of bold. The study is limited due to COVID-19 to focus on one case study instead of multiple case studies. One general manager and 10 MTN staff from the health and safety department were selected for a structured and in-depth interview. The senior manager from NCC was also interviewed. The officers chose to have different titles and designations. Such as the Senior Manager of Sustainability, Senior Manager of NCC, Manager of Health and safety, and supervisor of the health and safety department. Head of health and safety department, senior Manager of Health and Safety department. Even though they all perform functions that keep the organization sustainable, the sample size chosen was small since qualitative study samples are much smaller than quantitative study samples.

According to Mason (2010), Ritchie et al. (2010) offer reasons for this by stating that there is a viewpoint of diminishing return to a qualitative sample as the research gets on; more information is needed. According to Mason (2010), one action of a piece of data or secret code is required to ensure it becomes part of the analysis framework. Frequencies are rarely relevant in a qualitative study, as one happening of the statistics is as relevant as many in understanding the process behind the topic (Ritchie et al., 2010). As Crouch and McKenzie (2006) specified, qualitative research concerns meaning and not making a generalized hypothesis. Moreover, Mason's (2010) statement is even more critical that because qualitative research is very labour-intensive, analysing plenty of samples can be time-consuming and often impractical.

3.6.2 Qualitative Sampling

A non-probability judgemental sampling method elicited the exploratory quantitative data. A judgemental sampling method is a convenience sampling method in which the population elements are picked based on the researcher's judgment. The selection of twelve participants was based on the researcher's judgment and expertise, ensuring representation of the population of interest (Malhotra, 2007). These chosen senior managers are deemed appropriate for the study because they are decision-makers in the organization and have relevant insight into the sustainability practice of the company's performance. Thus, the ten

respondents interviewed were determined by their ideas and judgment and experience (Chattananon, 2003)

3.6.3 Qualitative Data Collection

In-depth interviews, a qualitative data collection method, can employ a direct or indirect approach based on the project's actual purpose or indirect approach based on whether the project's real purpose is known to the respondents (Malhotr, 2007). A straightforward approach is not disguised. The aim of the study is revealed to respondents or is otherwise evident to them from the questions asked. Focus groups and in-depth interviews are the primary direct techniques. In contrast, research that takes an indirect approach uses the project's real purpose, and the most used is the projective technique (Malhotra, 2007). Collectively, these methods are less structured and more intensive than standardized questionnaire-based interviews.

There is a longer, more flexible relationship with the respondent, so the resulting data have more depth and more incredible richness of context, which also means a more significant potential for new insights and perspectives (Aaker et al., 2010). A direct approach was adopted by way of the in-depth interview to collect qualitative data. This method helped to deeply explore the respondent's points of view, feelings, and perspectives to yield information about the research topic (Zik und, 2003). It also provided the opportunity to diagnose the situation, screen alternative variables and themes, discover innovative ideas, and ask knowledgeable individuals about the research problem (Rubin & Rubin, 2004).

3.6.4 Conducting Interviews

The researcher sent letters to the mobile telecommunications firms requesting that individuals participate in the study (attached as Appendix A). The messages were followed up with telephone calls to schedule face-to-face interviews. Time constraints, availability of officers, convenience, and cost (Zikmund, 2003) were the primary considerations in interviewing these bus executives and technical experts. They thought leaders in their offices in Abuja, Lagos, and Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The in-depth interviews followed a semi-structured approach where the researcher had an interview guide of open-ended questions on specific topics necessary for the research study. The respondents were given flexibility regarding how they responded to the questions (In the review guide attached as Appendix B). The research objectives, questions, and literature review influenced the questions. After eliciting their

support, in-depth interviews were conducted in the respondents' offices, as recommended by Kinnera and Taylor (1996).

They intimate that as busy officials, they were more comfortable because of their tight schedules. The interview commenced with some broad questions to establish the meaning of sustainability to the respondents, the internal and external antecedents of sustainable illiteracy practice, the consequences of sustainability practice, and the relevance of sustainability in Nigeria's mobile telecommunication industry.

These questions are adapted from Jaworski and Kohli's (1993) means rement scales because of their wide acceptability in the sustainability literature 101 (Zebal, 2003; Zebal & Goodwin, 2011; Hafer & Gresham, 2008; Akomea & Yeboah, 2011; Dwairi et al., 2012) and appropriately modified to suit this study.

The next set of questions explored to check if there is a focus on sustainability in terms of implementing sustainability practices in the mobile telecommunications industry and how it is implemented. It further determined if information and intelligence are generated and how it is done. The researcher asked questions related to the mechanism put in place for sustainability and expected respondents to rate the mechanism. Each set of questions had several questions, which followed the answers given by the respondents. The three essential parts of the interview guide proposed by Guion et al. (2006) were developed.

The first part, the face sheet, was used to record the interview's time, date, and place. Specific conditions or circumstances may affect the interview and demographic information about the respondent being interviewed; the second part is interviewing questions, which were placed on the left side of the page, along with a blank space on the right side for written observations. The third part is the post-interview comment sheet, a place to write notes after the interview. These notes included feelings, interpretations, and other comments that arose during the interview. The interview procedure, with the permission of the interviewees, was tape-recorded. Each interview, with the aid of an interview guide, lasted, on average, not more than an hour and a minute as prescribed by Malhotra (2007), and the interviews with the twelve respondents were undertaken within two weeks.

3.7 Qualitative data analysis

There are various modes of qualitative data analysis. Namely, grounded theory, hermeneutic analysis, content analysis, phenomenological analysis, and thematic analysis. Each has its advantages and disadvantages to consider. They all share similarities regarding the procedure for coding themes.

3.7.1 Thematic analysis

This is used in qualitative research and focuses on examining themes within data. This method emphasizes organization and a detailed description of the data set. The thematic analysis goes beyond merely counting phrases or words in a text and identifies implicit and explicit ideas within the data. I chose to use thematic analysis because it is an excellent approach to this study. Hence, this study aims to evaluate sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunication industry; therefore, MTN and NCC staff Company data are collected to analyze their views. Using thematic analysis has helped the researcher to identify the themes, that is, the patterns in the data that are most important to the study in answering the research questions to achieve the research objective. More so, thematic analysis helps analyze interviews to enable the researcher to examine the participants' meaning of their civic participation. It is significant to their lives, from a constructionist methodological position as a researcher to the participants' social constructions. This study adopts the qualitative method; therefore, it is vital to recognize the themes discovered by the researcher. The pragmatic approach helps the researcher produce an account of the data.

3.7.2 Content

Content is a research method for studying documents and communication artifacts, such as texts of various formats, pictures, and audio. Social scientists use this kind of analysis to investigate patterns in communication in a replicable and systematic manner—one of the critical advantages of using content analysis of social phenomena.

3.7.3 Thematic content (TCA)

Thematic content is a descriptive presentation of qualitative data. Qualitative data may take the form of interview transcripts collected from research participants or other identified texts that reflect experientially on the topic of study.

3.7.4 Data analysis employed.

According to (Gioia, Corley, & Hamilton, 2013; Miles & Huberman, 1994; Strauss & Corbin, 1998.) Creating first-order codes and temporary second-order themes. Data analysis starts with coding in a reiterative style; the interview subsequently transcribes proposed practices for qualitative data analysis using NVivo Qualitative Research Software. The researcher started by linking the data with first-order code that talked about the critical topic of this study to evaluate sustainability practices in Nigeria's telecommunication industry and the factors impeding sustainability practices in Nigeria's telecommunication industry. During this stage, the researcher shifted back and forth between data analysis and the literature to help make sense of the emerging ideas and sharpen up the coding scheme. Next are common themes to link together data bits from varying but related groups created in open coding (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). This step helped me to gather the initial first-order codes into more specific yet provisional second-order themes. For example, a statement reflects the diversity of views around sustainability regarding what different authors perceive. This led the researcher to view different definitions of sustainability, not in the second-order theme encompassing these related first-order codes.

Integrating first-order codes with second-order themes. In the subsequent analysis stage, the revisited data to ensure precision across the draft second-order themes. The researcher iteratively reviewed the second-order themes over several discussions, cancelling or improving temporary themes while generating new themes for groupings arising from the evaluation. Following the finesse of present, or formation of new, second-order themes, the researcher assessed these concepts to make sure the themes correctly displayed the first-order codes. For example, first-order coding statements relating to factors inhibiting current sustainability practices in Nigerian telecom led us to a provisional second-order theme describing the degree to which the methods of sustainability practice put in place impact sustainability. This was later refined into the idea of possible benefits of improving sustainability practice in Nigeria telecommunication defined by a first-order coding statement defining sustainability as sustainable development as any development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet the r needs. Brundtland (1984).

Aggregating the theoretical dimensions.

Concluding these second-order themes, the researcher investigated the fundamental theoretical aspects to understand how different themes related to and linked to one another

within a larger setting. For example, some themes suggested informers' own experiences of unjust status gain (e.g., sustainability is also health and safety.). In contrast, others resemble informers' responses to their unearned status gain (e.g., sustainability is also local partners, host communities, and regulatory agencies).

The researcher assessed numerous conceptual models to understand how second-order themes fit together, integrating present organizational theory whenever possible. The researcher analysed potential models against the data to establish how well the emergent theoretical understanding explained the research setting (e.g., Becker, 1970; Glaser & Strauss, 1967; Locke, 2001). Figure 6 is the conceptual framework, showing the first-order codes, code-order themes, and aggregate theoretical elements that best explain informers' experience of, and response to, their received status gain. In the following sections, the researcher lays out the findings that emerged inductively in four steps. First, the researcher defines sustainability.

Second, the researcher details the factors impeding sustainability practice in Nigeria's telecommunication industry differences that emerged from the data on how the degree of the extent the methods of sustainability practice put in place impact sustainability. I describe how respondents' perceptions of factors impeding sustainability practice. In contrast, the informants' idea of possible benefits of improving sustainability practices in Nigeria's telecommunication responded in three distinct ways: perspective-taking, status rationalization, and status stability appraisal. Third, I describe how sustainability methods are implemented to impact sustainability. Finally, I propose a general model of unearned status gain, which we lay out with corresponding testable propositions.

3.8 Ethical consideration

As Malhotra (2007) proposed, data were obtained and analysed strictly following ethical considerations. According to Cooper and Schindler (2001), the ethical treatment of respondents is the most important ethical issue to ensure that rights are not compromised. Cooper and Schindler (2001) advise that researchers must judge what activities are inappropriate and what activities must be undertaken to ensure that no one will be disadvantaged because the research was a primary ethical consideration. Questions asked were not intended to invade respondents' privacy or cause them undue stress. This was

achieved by making it clear to the respondents that they were not obligated to answer any question that could make them uncomfortable at the beginning of the interview.

This ensured that deceptions were eliminated because, as Zikmund (2003) stated, deception occurs when the researcher disguises the real purpose of the research that could be harmful to the respondents or any other party. Furthermore, appropriate scales were used to obtain the data needed to answer the research questions. Scales that exhibited reasonable reliability, validity, and generalizability were used. All detailed info was taken to ensure that the scales were not so biased to slant the findings in any direction. Thus, balanced scales with relative positive and negative descriptors were used. The integrity of the data collection process was ensured. Respondents were made to feel as comfortable as possible by addressing their apprehensions. This is done by supplying them with adequate information about the study.

The research aims to address their questions and clearly state the responsibilities and expectations at the start of the interviews. A cover letter was prepared that described the nature and purpose of the study. Also, 104 respondents were told they were not obligated to answer questions that needed clarification. They could terminate the interview at any point should they experience any discomfort, as advised by various researchers (Leary, 1995; Furlong et al., 2000).

The respondents' privacy, feelings, and dignity were respected. It ensured the respondents had a positive and pleasant experience to enhance goodwill and future cooperation. The sampling design was appropriate for controlling the sampling, and there were no sampling errors in the sampling process. It ensured that when non-probability was used, an effort was made to obtain a representative sample. While checking, editing, coding, transcribing, and cleaning during the data presentation and analysis, the researcher tried to understand the data quality. The analysis was undertaken only after identifying unsatisfactory respondents. The procedure used to identify adequate respondents and the number of respondents discarded were disclosed. This ensured that lofty standards were maintained, and the data obtained was accurate as prescribed by Zikmund (2003). The research reporting process was mainly used to ensure that the data was collected, analysed, and interpreted honestly and that accurate research findings were presented as specified (Kinnear & Taylor, 1996).

3.9 Quality criteria

This is based on the philosophical and methodological assessment of the research, coupled with an attempt to create knowledge firmly grounded in theory and relevant to practice in the telecommunication industry in Nigeria. The adoption of objective pragmatism as the philosophy of this study influences the quality criteria selected. The quality criteria are based on validity, credibility, relevance to practice, reliability, and replicability. The subsections below discuss these quality criteria.

3.9.1 Validity

Various researchers have recognized the meanings of validity. The three elements of validity are internal validity, external validity, and construct validity. Firstly, Yin (2014) described internal validity as the degree to which a researcher can understand a causal relationship when certain situations or conditions lead to others, which is different from false relationships. Secondly, external validity is a situation where the study's findings can be oversimplified beyond the current situation under study (Voss et al., 2002). The final element is constructed validity, where a researcher determines the correct operational measures for the prevailing content under study (Voss et al., 2002).

3.9.2 Credibility and relevance to practice

The triangulation of the data collection methods for this research helps to reduce the effect of the shortcomings of the research while also increasing its credibility and importance to practice. Strauss and Corbin (1998) view that the qualitative method is helpful for research that seeks to explore significant areas of which the researcher has little knowledge but can gain a different understanding. Combining these contributions from qualitative and content analysis methods is considered in identifying the research objective, which seeks to improve sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunication industry towards best practices. The credibility and relevance to practice are essential despite considering the other quality criteria, such as validity, reliability, and replicability. Miles and Huberman (1994) argued that it is vital for the research to examine what it does for its stakeholders, even if the research findings are valid, dependable, and replicable. To depict the practical importance of this research, the researcher empirically evaluated the study area in three phases: case studies and field survey one (interviews from MTN Nigeria and NCC).

3.9.3. reliability

Replicability: the reliability of a study is the capability of the study, experiment, or test to be replicated correctly by another person working on similar research but independently. Also, Bauer (2000) thought that reliability involves a situation where efforts are doubled, considering where the same person or two or more people may make a second understanding of the same matter after some time break to determine the matter's stability, consistency, and reliability. Reliability was displayed in this study by the research supervisors' continuous review of the study and the research institutes' submission to the ethics panel to determine whether the questions asked were meaningful, ethical, and thorough.

Replicability refers to the success rates achieved by performing continual studies or experiments by either another researcher or the same researcher. It is also a gauge of the difference to measure a study by the same individual, on the same thing, and under the same conditions. However, the researcher maintains that, based on the nature of being and taking awareness of the nature of social science, it is unlikely to be competent in completely replicating the conditions under which data are collected. Replicability is a desirable target but less likely to be fully achieved. This made the researcher adopt quality control approaches for reliability and replicability (Miles and Huberman, 1994). The summary of the assessment for the study based on the quality criteria (validity, credibility, relevance to practice, reliability, and replicability) is shown in Table 5.

3.10 Conclusion

The Chapter presented the research philosophy, method, and methodology adopted to meet the aims and objectives identified. It provided a comprehensive account of the research philosophy, pragmatic research methodology, quantitative and qualitative research method, and the two main data collection methods, the semi-structured interview approach. It outlined the pros and cons, strengths, and weaknesses of the two research approaches: qualitative and quantitative methods.

Qualitative and quantitative. The two data collection methods defended the reasons for adopting this study. Furthermore, it sets out the research approach followed to collect qualitative data from 12 critical officials for the qualitative phase of the study. Finally, the Chapter outlined the processes, procedures, and analysis methods adopted for the

qualitative research and presented the model for this thesis. The next Chapter discusses the findings of the analysis.

Chapter four

Data analysis and finding

4.0 Introduction

This chapter discusses all the findings of the qualitative –in-depth interviews based on information collected from the twelve staff of MTN Nigeria and the senior manager from NCC. A judgemental sample method was used to select the sample, so this study focuses on one of the telecommunication companies in Nigeria; due to the COVID-19 pandemic, researchers could not study more than one company. This has been discussed in the recommendation for further study. The interview questions sought to answer questions on sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunication industry with specifications that meet the research objectives.

This includes the respondents' understanding of sustainability practices, how the company conceptualizes sustainability, and how the company implements sustainability. Other areas include the policies that have been put in place, the factors within and outside the organization that inhibit sustainability practices, and the factors that facilitate sustainability practices in the organization. Additional questions focus on organizational policies for sustainability practice. Specific questions were pitched to explore the opportunities available to organizations to support sustainability practices, the factors constraining sustainability practices in the telecommunications industry, and the difference they make in sustainability practices.

Thematic analysis is used to analyse the findings, which are presented transparently and systematically, reflecting the data collected and the insights derived from the information obtained. A new dimension around sustainability practices as perceived by the respondents. The data collected came from MTN. NCC interview documents from NCC, MTN is one of Nigeria's telecommunications players.

4.1 Profile of respondents

The result of this qualitative study is based on interviews with twelve participants from two different organizations. All the respondents willingly took part in the study, and the twelve participants in this study are enrolled from MTN Nigeria and NCC. Each participant is

interviewed face to face. Face-to-face interviews also allowed for convenient transcriptions of recorded interviews and the transcription of interviews. Interviews were transcribed between 30th June -15th and July 2018. An interview with an international participant was conducted through Skype video conferencing after multiple attempts to talk by phone failed. The researcher took thorough field notes but could transcribe the Skype interview verbatim. Although the interviews were conducted at a time convenient to the participants, the duration varied. The researcher also took field notes during each interview, and all interviews were conducted between March and April 2018. The names of all twelve research participants have they have been anonymized to protect participant confidentiality.

They are thus named P1 (Participant 1) to P12. The respondents' profile in Table 3 shows that 70% have worked with their organization for over ten years, while 30% have worked for between 9-10 years. The findings show respondents have been associated with their firm for a reasonable time. Most have senior positions and are well-placed to respond to questions about the dimensions of sustainability practice. Although there were twelve interviewees, eleven respondents were from the telecommunication communications sector, and one was from a regulatory body NCC.

Table 3 Profile of respondents

Serial	Codes for respondents	Designation	Year of experience	Qualification
1.	P1	Group manager sustainability MTN	24	Degree
2.	P2	Manager MTN Health and Safety	16	
De 3	P3	Supervisor health and safety	10	Degree
4	P4	Head of dept health and safety	14	Degree
5	P5	Senior manager health and safety	18	Degree

6	P6	Member health and safety	9	Degree
7	P7	Tower manager MTN	14	Degree
8	P8	Team leader Health and Safety MTN	12	Degree
9	P9	Member health and safety MTN	9	Degree
10	P10	Member health and safety MTN	10	Degree
11	P11	Member health and safety MTN	10	Degree
12	P12	Senior manager NCC	15	Masters

4.2 Research Results

4.2.1 RQ 1 - Sustainability in the mobile telecommunication industry

Table 5 below shows the diversity of views around sustainability regarding what different authors perceive. Brundtland (1984) defined sustainable development as any development that meets the present's needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs. Although some of the definitions may appear divergent from the traditional definition of sustainability, all the definitions converge on economic, social, and environmental issues. While some define sustainability in a social context, others see it in terms of investment value. Local partners and regulatory agencies are often emphasized, and social and economic aspects are typically underscored.

Furthermore, some see sustainability from a health and safety angle, and there is less emphasis on the environment. The three pillars are identified, and sustainability is clearly defined. Interestingly, a document collected from MTN states that.

'For MTN, sustainability is about value creation consisting of the three pillars economic, social, and environment. M TN vision for sustainability is to protect and create shared value for our company and shareholders through environmental and socially responsible core business practices. (2017).

The above statements from a Nigerian telecommunication industry player indicate that sustainability is increasingly recognised. The above assertions find support in the most accepted definition in the UK that sees sustainability as any development that meets the present's needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet the needs of the present. Establishments are gradually more inclined to integrate society's expectations into their business policies, not only to respond to increasing pressure from customers, employees, and other shareholders but also to explore opportunities for creating competitive advantage (Bielak, Bonini, & Oppenheim, 2007; Bonini, Mendonça, & Oppenheim, 2006). To this end, management researchers seek to identify factors that can facilitate the effective integration of sustainability into organisational practices. This finding supports the idea of sustainability in mobile telecommunications.

The findings affirm the literature on sustainability practices. The interview findings and documents answer the first question concerning sustainability in the mobile telecommunications industry. The following section focuses on the factors that inhibit sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunication industry.

Table 4 Views of Sustainability.

Views of sustainability	Observation
Sustainability is economic, environmental, and social	<p><i>P2 defines sustainability as mainly a means of improving customer experience. Sustainability is also about protecting and creating shared value for MTN and its stakeholders via environmentally and socially responsible core business practices.</i></p> <p><i>P1 states that for MTN, sustainability is about value creation consisting of the three pillars: economic, social, and environment. MTN's vision for sustainability is to protect and</i></p>

<p>Sustainability is something else, customer experience.</p>	<p><i>Create shared value for our company and shareholders through environmental and socially responsible core business practices.</i></p> <p><i>P3 sees this as mainly a means of improving the customer experience. Sustainability is also about protecting and creating shared value for MTN and its stakeholders via environmentally and socially responsible core business practices. Co-operation and partnerships help MTN accelerate the pace.</i></p>
<p>Sustainability is also health and safety</p>	<p><i>P4 suggested that MTN has a good understanding of sustainability, considering the environmental aspects. The company also considers health and safety issues can be equated with sustainability from a broad perspective. Regarding the social pillar, the company is concerned about human rights and the economy.</i></p> <p><i>One respondent talked about health and safety. and as a broad perspective</i></p>
	<p><i>considers health and safety issues can be equated with sustainability from a broad perspective. In terms of the social pillar, the company is concerned about human rights and then the economy.</i></p> <p><i>One respondent talked about health and safety. and as a broad perspective</i></p>
<p>Sustainability is also local partners, host communities, and regulatory agencies</p>	<p><i>P7's opinion is based on the interest of monitoring bodies and host areas. He notes that MTN has the expertise, infrastructure, investments, and relationships that can support programs that enhance people's living environments and socio-economic status. For us, sustainability is about protecting and creating shared value for MTN and our stakeholders via</i></p>

	<i>environmentally and socially responsible core business practices and ready for improvement in sustainability practices.</i>
Sustainability is also an essential matter in telecommunication and involved energy and human rights.	<i>P7 believes that sustainability is vital and includes the usage of energy. In his words, MTN has a good understanding of what sustainability is considering the environmental focus of the company. Health and safety issues are also related to sustainability from a broad perspective. In terms of the social</i>
Sustainability is also an essential matter in telecommunication and involved energy and human rights.	<i>pillar, the company is concerned about human rights and then the economy P12's Nigeria telecommunication looks at best practice for sustainability based on copying standard global best practice from developed countries through the implementation of some policies and projects such as the collation of base. stations</i>

4.2.2 RQ 2 - Factors inhibiting current sustainability practices in Nigerian telecoms.

As shown in Table 5 below, cross-cutting factors inhibit the adoption of best practices. Thus, cutting factors due to industrial constraints, shortages of energy, and the cost of capital and sustainability policies are expected. Electricity is a primary concern in Nigerian business today. MTN powers its equipment using renewable energy/ solar hybrid standalone power plants in partnership with Nigeria energy companies due to high solar irradiation rates in Nigeria. This technology brings energy to companies at a prohibitive cost; However, it reduces noise pollution to the environment, another clear-cut factor inhibiting sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry is the dynamic of policies and security challenges. Location or country-specific policies on sustainability are relevant, and group sustainability policies apply to organizations and partners in all countries of operation.

These findings imply that the same policies are applicable in all countries where they are in operation. In contrast, the regulation of NCC (the regulatory body in Nigeria) is unstable. More so, it changes at short notice, creating immense challenges to the Telecommunication service providers in keeping abreast of such changes. Security challenges to the telecommunication

network have been a matter of concern to local and international communities within the two decades. The telecommunications infrastructure provides the necessary backbone for information exchange such as voice, video, data, and internet connectivity, and these are particularly vulnerable to various forms of attack. Cross-cutting factors that inhibit the Nigerian telecommunication industry from adopting best practices often relate to taxation. The telecommunications industry is a significant source of tax revenue for the Nigerian government. MTN Nigeria claims to have paid over two trillion naira to the Nigerian government since 2001. Securing the infrastructure and equipment is an inherent challenge, and the affordability of services to subscribers is hotly debated. Taxes in the telecommunication industry should be aligned with other sectors in line with international best practices. Uncertainties over taxes and levies affect investment, and the anticipated taxes and expected levies are built into the cost of services and products and passed to subscribers who are the clients.

Table 5 views the factors inhibiting sustainability practice.

Views of factors inhibiting sustainability	Observation
Factors inhibiting sustainability practice are industrial constraints, shortages of energy and the of capital as well as sustainability policy	<p><i>Factors inhibiting sustainability practice are industrial constraints, shortages of energy and lack of capital, and sustainability policy.</i></p> <p><i>P8, pointed out challenges the industry faces that affect the rollout of services and lack of energy.</i></p> <p><i>These affect capital costs. Sustainability policies also affect sustainability practices. He stated: Some of the challenges MTN faces in implementing sustainability practice is the dynamics of politics and security challenges pose a threat to sustainability and implementation cost more.</i></p>
Factors inhibiting sustainability practice is dynamic of policies and security challenges	<p><i>P2 in his words stated that Some of the challenges MTN face in implementing sustainability practice are the dynamics of politics and security challenges pose a threat to sustainability and implementation cost more.</i></p>

	<p><i>P 11's response was this is always a tricky question as some impediments to the growth of digital inclusion, and sustainable impacts are rooted in structural industry constraints. Examples include access to a sufficient radio spectrum for service rollout, energy shortages, or the cost of capital needed for infrastructure rollout.</i></p>
<p>Factors inhibiting sustainability practice are the Different policies of sustainability and increase in taxation often</p>	<p><i>Factors inhibiting sustainability practice are the Different policies of sustainability and the increase in taxation P5 stated that most of the constraints that impact sustainability practices in the company are externally levied by the government, and policies change often.</i></p> <p><i>The company spends lots of money putting policies in place, but NCC can simply change its policies at short notice with implications for company budgets.</i></p> <p><i>P6 said one of the factors that affects sustainability practices is taxation increasing all the time. I am unable to discuss this part of the company policy.</i></p> <p><i>P9 responded that other challenges include an increasingly uncertain regulatory, economic, and competitive environment, and the need to ensure communication costs are more affordable</i></p>
<p>Factors inhibiting sustainability is that the company powers its equipment with diesel</p>	<p><i>P8 responded that MTN does not have a direct sustainability policy but a group sustainability policy that covers the whole company. The dynamics of politics and security challenges are a threat to sustainability and implementation. costs within MTN.</i></p>

Factors inhibiting sustainability is that the company does not have a base station	<i>P7 suggests MTN as a telecommunications company does not have its base station site. However, as discussed earlier, I explained the fact that tower management companies own our network base station sites, and that we are a tenant on these sites.</i>
Factors inhibiting sustainability practice is that there are no sustainability practice indicators in NCC	<i>P10 responded by noting that NCC, the governing body for telecommunication, does not have a sustainability department; hence it cannot monitor the sustainability practices of the industry.</i>

4.2.3 RQ 3 - To what degree do the methods of sustainability practices put in place impact sustainability?

As outlined in Table 6 below, there is a need for sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry to be able to adopt best practices for sustainability standards. MTN considers the three pillars (economic, social, and environment). The company tries to consider the environment, including the health and safety issues that can arise. It looks at sustainability more from the point of view of the social pillar. MTN is concerned about human rights and protecting the investment of the economic component. MTN has structured policies that regulate sustainability practices, and this has a positive impact on sustainability. The responses from organizations indicate that regular staff training is in place to enable them to meet ever-changing customer demands and incorporate staff views in the company's decision-making processes to improve its services by extension. Since MTN does not have a direct sustainability department, its health and safety department monitor its compliance policies.

The most interesting part of these findings is that MTN has a command of sustainability, which has kept the company solvent this long. They have created sustainable economic value and have developed the internet of things (LoT) to transform the natural, economic, and social environment. In partnership with a government regulatory body called Neasal, MTN Nigeria took responsibility for their environmental impact. They work with tower managers to collocate a base station to reduce costs and control carbon emissions by sharing a network site. In this

way, strong sustainability leadership can be created. Nigeria's sustainability policies with the telecommunications industry are functional. The environmental and social pillars of sustainability require attention to the impact on the lives of individuals where the company has base sites.

The findings from MTN about the impact of sustainability practices can be found in the (appendix 4) MTN sustainability report (2017). Henceforth, measures to save energy and reduce GHG are fewer harmful ways to create sustainable business practices within the telecoms sector. This move has led the telecommunication companies in Nigeria to search for methods to reduce running costs and overheads. Nigeria's energy potential is regarded as significant. Still, only when energy potential is intermixed with access issues and utilization can the full-scale deployment and mobilization of energy access be achieved. The literature on evaluating current sustainability practices in Nigeria validates this finding. The finding answers research question three and objective three since it analyses the possible benefits of developing improved sustainability practices.

Table 6 - Impact of sustainability practices

Views of factors inhibiting sustainability	Observation
Factors inhibiting sustainability practice are industrial constraints, shortages of energy and the of capital as well as sustainability policy.	<p><i>P8 pointed out challenges the industry faces that affect the rollout of services and lack of energy. These affect capital costs. Sustainability policies also affect sustainability practices.</i></p> <p><i>He stated: Some of the challenges MTN faces in implementing sustainability practice is the dynamics of politics and security challenges pose a threat to sustainability and implementation cost more.</i></p>
Factors inhibiting sustainability practice is dynamic of policies and security challenges	<p><i>Factors inhibiting sustainability practice are the dynamic of policies and security challenges.</i></p> <p><i>P2 in his words stated that Some of the challenges MTN face in implementing sustainability practice are the dynamics of politics and security challenges pose a threat to sustainability and implementation costs more.</i></p>

	<p><i>P 11's response was this is always a tricky question as some impediments to the growth of digital inclusion, and sustainable impacts are rooted in structural industry constraints. Examples include access to a sufficient radio spectrum to enable service rollout, energy</i></p>
<p>Factors inhibiting sustainability practice are the Different policies of sustainability and increase in taxation often</p>	<p><i>P5 stated that most of the constraints that impact sustainability practices in the company are externally levied by government, and policies change often. The company spends lots of money putting policies in place, but NCC can simply change its policies at short notice with implications for company budgets.</i></p> <p><i>P6 said one of the factors that affects sustainability practices is taxation increasing all the time. I am unable to discuss this part of the company policy.</i></p> <p><i>P9 responded that other challenges include an increasingly uncertain regulatory, economic, and competitive environment, and the need to ensure communication costs are more affordable.</i></p>
<p>Factors inhibiting sustainability is that the company powers its equipment with diesel</p>	<p><i>P8 responded that MTN does not have a direct sustainability policy but a group sustainability policy that covers the whole company. The dynamics of politics and security challenges threaten sustainability and implementation. costs within MTN</i></p>
<p>Factors inhibiting sustainability is that the company does not have a base station.</p>	<p><i>P7 suggests MTN as a telecommunications company does not have its base station site. However, as discussed earlier, I explained the fact that tower management companies own our network base station sites and that we are a tenant on these sites.</i></p>

<p>Factors inhibiting sustainability practice is that there are no sustainability practice indicators in NCC</p>	<p><i>P10 responded by noting that NCC, the governing body for telecommunication, does not have a sustainability department; hence it cannot monitor the industry's sustainability practices</i></p>
<p>The degree of sustainability practice impact is high since the company considers environmental, economic, and social issue</p>	<p><i>P3 responded that MTN has put in place policies and regulations to incorporate staff members into the decisions of the company; this improves the network and revenue the company generates. This action helps to improve sustainability.</i></p> <p><i>P4 also responded that MTN has policies for compliance regulations, which are always updated to follow the right practices in the company; this is monitored by the health and The safety department of the company</i></p>
	<p><i>Three of the interviewees agree that MTN has structured policies that regulate sustainability practices in the company and update staff through training in relation to sustainability</i></p>
<p>The degree of impact can be value creation and corporate social responsibilities.</p>	<p><i>P7 responded that MTN tried to ensure a remarkable sustainable impact in the previous year 2017. It increased its number of partnerships with local authorities and agencies. This was done to be able to tackle the environmental challenges such as the responsible management of electronic and electric waste to improve sustainability.</i></p>
<p>The degree of impact is that the thrust of sustainability practice is high</p>	<p><i>P5 responded that MTN has survived this long because of (1) creating sustainable economic value, (2) Developing the Internet of things as solutions that transform natural, economic, and social environments. (3) Taking responsibility for environmental impacts</i></p>
<p>The degree of impact is that the thrust of sustainability practice is high</p>	<p><i>P5 responded that MTN has survived this long because of (1) creating sustainable economic value, (2) Developing the Internet of things as solutions that transform natural, economic, and social environments. (3) Taking responsibility for environmental impacts</i></p>

<p>The degree of impact could be a partnership with local authorities is medium.</p>	<p><i>P6 said that MTN has a partnership with host communities to manage environmental issues. Thus, MTN tried to ensure a remarkable sustainable impact in the previous year 2017. It increased the number of partnerships with local authorities and agencies to tackle environmental challenges such as the responsible management of electronic and electric waste to improve sustainability.</i></p>
<p>The degree of impact on recycling waste products is medium</p>	<p><i>P1 provided information on the way MTN recycles its waste products considering both the environmental and economic pillars of sustainability thus the response was. I think we discussed that earlier when I explained the fact that tower management companies own our network base station sites, and that we are a</i></p>
	<p><i>tenant on these sites. The asset owner supplies the power needed. On recycling, there are two aspects. 1. Supplier take-back schemes, for example, where we contract with the original supplier or asset manufacturer to take back (for recycling or refurbishment, etc.) old network equipment that has reached the end of its useful life. Or 2. We plan to work on e-waste management in partnership with many stakeholders, under the NESREA EPRON initiative.</i></p>
<p>The degree of impact of sustainability practice is medium; the three pillars need improvement</p>	<p><i>P12 noted that sustainability policies in Nigeria mobile telecommunication system are functional. The environmental pillar of sustainability needs more sensitization to demonstrate the level of danger, as well as the policy for mask fixing and collaborating with agencies to enable good practice.</i></p> <p><i>Both the environmental and social pillars of sustainability require more effort so as not to impact the lives of the individuals where the companies have base sites. I will, therefore, rate this as a medium-priority improvement.</i></p>

4.2.4 RQ 4 - Possible benefits of improving sustainability in Nigerian telecommunications.

There are different views on the benefits of improving sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry, as shown in Table 9. This is because the respondents gave different views on improving sustainability practices, including structured implementation and staff engagement in decision-making. MTN has in place structured implementation policies, and efforts are made to adopt a material-based approach. This has allowed the company to create sustainable economic value, take responsibility for its environmental impact, and contribute to vibrant and thriving communities in the market by addressing matters of good governance and ethics. The company also engages staff members in decision making to improve its network and revenue.

The benefits of improved sustainability practices can also be the mechanism that is put in place for a sustainability practice to monitor and evaluate the foundation that manages the design and implementation of the organizational-wide control and evaluation system for MTN. There are also opportunities for MTN to improve its sustainability practices. Nigerian telecommunications are open to learning new knowledge to improve sustainability practices and gain more understanding from other developed countries regarding best sustainability practices. Examples include introducing monitoring techniques for sustainability practices in the telecommunications industry in Nigeria. Lastly, there is a need to create a standard measure for sustainability practice. For instance, the Nigerian telecommunications industry does not have any standard measure to monitor and measure the sustainability practices of telecommunication companies. An intermittent electricity supply impinges on Nigerian economic growth due to its obsolete infrastructure and distribution issues.

The three pillars for creating a stable economy with a sustainable energy development framework are recommended for Nigeria. The first pillar is vital and will ensure the social welfare of citizens. However, the first pillar cannot be achieved without consideration of the increased productivity of ICT, which can lead to increased productivity and social welfare. Increased productivity has increased regarding environmental pressures and carbon emissions as ICT has contributed to economic growth and social empowerment. Unfortunately, this is not the case as the incremental diffusion of ICT comes at a negative

cost to the environment due to the unique multiplicity of issues that exist within emerging and developing economies and at a global level. However, for companies to attain standard practices in the telecommunication sector, such as in the developed world, there must be a continuous process and close monitoring of sustainability practices in the industry. The literature studied affirms the findings collected. This finding also answers research question four and objective four, which was to develop a model for improved sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunication industry.

Table .7 – Benefits of improved Sustainability Practices.

Views of the benefits of improved sustainability practices.	Observation
The benefits of improving sustainability practices could mean structured implementation and staff engagement in decision-making	<i>Two interviewees reported that the benefits of sustainability are structured implementation, and MTN’s vision impacts on the three pillars of sustainability. Also, getting staff involved often in decision making has improved sustainability. One respondent noted:</i>
	<p><i>P2 The company carries staff members along in making decisions to improve the network and revenue.</i></p> <p><i>P3 MTN has put in place policies and regulations to incorporate staff members into the decisions of the company; this improves the network and revenue the company generates. This action helps to improve sustainability.</i></p>
Benefits of Improved sustainability practice can also be MTN policies and regulations.	<i>P5 also noted that the mechanism in place is a process of monitoring and evaluating the foundation that manages the design and implementation of the organizational-wide monitoring and evaluation system.</i>
The benefits of improving practice mean putting a mechanism in place.	<i>P5 also noted that the mechanism in place is a process of monitoring and evaluating the</i>

	<p><i>foundation that manages the design and implementation of the organizational-wide monitoring and evaluation system.</i></p>
	<p><i>P1 noted that to achieve this vision, MTN has a structured implementation plan and has made efforts to adopt a materiality-based approach.</i></p> <p><i>This allows us to follow our efforts in the following ways (a) creating sustainable economic value (b) taking responsibility for our environmental impact (c) contributing to vibrant, thriving communities in our market by addressing matters of good governance and ethics</i></p>
	<p><i>Another respondent suggested that MTN has in place some tools that have helped with sustainability practices, considering the social, economic, and environmental pillars of sustainability</i></p>
<p>The benefits of improved sustainability practices can also be opportunities available to gain new knowledge as to how to improve sustainability practices</p>	<p><i>Two of the respondents noted that there are lots of opportunities available for MTN to improve. knowledge as to how to improve sustainability practices sustainability practices. The responses below are relevant:</i></p> <p><i>P8 MTN does not have direct sustainability policy but has a group sustainability policy which covers the company. Furthermore, the dynamics of politics and security challenges are a threat to sustainability and implementation costs within MTN.</i></p> <p><i>However, for the company to be able to attain standard practices in the telecommunication sector, there should be a continuous process of tracking policies, processes, and updates when</i></p>

	<p><i>and where necessary to accommodate new needs.</i></p> <p><i>P11 My view is that I think there should be some improvements to Nigeria's sustainability practices. For instance, sustainability practices in the industry do not bear relation to any standard measure to access the practices of the different telecommunications industries in the country. So MTN needs to some improvements, especially in terms of the environment.</i></p>
<p>The benefits of improved sustainability practice could mean creating a standard measure for sustainability practice</p>	<p><i>The benefits of improved sustainability practice could mean creating a standard measure for sustainability practice.</i></p> <p><i>P 9 noted that, for MTN, I see many opportunities available to improve the sustainability practice already in place.</i></p> <p><i>P10 responded Yes, 'the industry needs some improvement considering the challenges MTN faces in implementing sustainability practices in Nigeria and to compare ourselves to our other partner countries.</i></p> <p><i>P12 noted that Nigerian telecommunications is open to learning to improve its sustainability practices and to gain more knowledge from other developed countries on best practices in terms of sustainability.</i></p> <p><i>An example might be introducing monitoring techniques on sustainability practices in the telecommunications industry in Nigeria.</i></p>

4.2,5

RQ 5 – Model for improved sustainability practice in Nigeria telecommunication.

The joining of environmentally responsible design, products, and processes into one's business, combined with a wide distribution of information on corporate sustainability, can help promote a positive and sustainable company image. This, in turn, influences brand loyalty amongst consumers, profitability for the company, and sustainability in the natural environment. At a global level, the human population includes people who have beaten the seven billion mark and are still growing significantly. This increase, and therefore, the rising population's increasing demands, pushes everything towards breaking point. Environmental degradation and pollution of the ecosystems are among the foremost issues. Such damage threatens the lives of many organisms. The heating is hugely unbalanced. Pollution accounts for many diseases and, therefore, the quality of life in many fragile areas.

Property is so vital for all companies, as are technologies. The telecommunications sector is the primary omnipresent technology sector within the world. Therefore, it needs to improve when it comes to sustainability. The government is a significant stakeholder when it comes to the job of telecommunications regulation. The policies and laws implemented by the Commission have been prepared and enacted into law by the government for the good of society. The government's interest in the process is also diverse. The government is interested in the services provided to the people in a timely, qualitative, and affordable manner. Activities in the sector are conducted in a legal and orderly manner. The government is also interested in creating an enabling environment that could continue to attract investment to meet its desires for the people.

A commission, in all its activities, is, therefore, mindful of the need to protect, preserve, and implement actions and programs that meet the expectations and objectives of the government. They envisage a regulator that will not be arbitrary in its decision-making and will control by the principles as it is in existence in the agreement on license and provisions of the laws and regulations. The findings reported here suggest that sustainability practices in Nigerian telecommunications need to be improved. Companies should prioritize their sustainability goals based on current and expected shareholder demands and industry trends. MTN's current focus is on shareholder value and customer experience. However, these companies should also focus on other significant issues, such as reducing energy

consumption. Introducing measures for sustainability, however, can only be effective if the governing body is fully committed.

Moreover, there are benefits to adopting best practices in sustainability in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. There is some urgency to improve Nigerian sustainability practices in the telecommunications industry using a best-practice approach. This is dependent on such factors as (a) the existence and applicability of sustainability practices to address the problems of Nigerian telecommunications, (b) creating best practice initiatives in the industry, and (3) recognising the benefits of best practices for sustainability. Hence, a model has been created called the NPSM to enhance and enforce sustainability practices in Nigeria's telecommunications sector after a careful evaluation was carried out during the study. The literature review affirms the findings, and this finding has also answered research objective five, which is to develop a model to improve sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. This theory is discussed further in chapter 5 of the thesis,

4.3 Emergent themes.

A total of four main themes were generated with the use of Braun and Clarke's (2006) six phases of thematic analysis. As a group of approaches for collecting and analysing data, qualitative research intends to offer an in-depth, socio-contextual, and explanatory description and interpretation of the research topic. Such a method covers a broad range of approaches with wide variations in the concepts, assumptions, and analytic rules. Thematic analysis is the steps of finding themes using qualitative methodology. Braun & Clarke (2006) believe that it is the first qualitative method that should be learned as it offers core skills that will be beneficial for conducting many analysis' (p.78). A further advantage, particularly from the uniqueness of thematic analysis in learning and teaching lies in its nature as a method rather than a methodology, making it versatile across various epistemological and theoretical perspectives. it is not tied to an epistemological or theoretical perspective. This makes it a very flexible method, with considerable advantages given the diversity of work in learning and teaching.

Furthermore, Braun & Clarke (2006) differentiate between two levels of themes: semantic and latent. Semantic themes pertain to the explicit or surface meanings of data, focusing solely on participants' statements or written content. The analysis in this illustrative example uncovers themes at the semantic level, which is indicative of many learning and teaching

studies. The analysis moves beyond describing what is said to focus on interpreting and explaining what is said. In contrast, the latent level looks beyond what has been said and begins to explore the underlying ideas, assumptions, and conceptualizations – including ideologies – theorized to form or inform the semantic content of the data." as forming or informing the semantic content of data' (p.84).

Table 8 hierarchy of emergent themes

Main Themes	Description
1. What is sustainability	An understanding of sustainability is crucial to all telecommunication players.
2. The Inhibitors of sustainability	Identification of a factor that inhibits sustainability in the telecommunication industry is essential to this study.
3. The degree of the impact of sustainability practice	Sustainability practice has a different effect on companies in the telecommunication industry measured as high, medium, and low.
4. The significance and benefits of improved sustainability practice	Evidence from findings in the study indicates some benefits and importance of sustainability practices in the telecommunication industry

Themes 1 answered research question one: i.e., what is sustainability in the mobile telecommunication industry? These two answered the research question: What factors inhibit current sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry? Theme three addressed research question three: to what degree do the methods of practice impact sustainability levels in the Nigerian telecommunications industry? Theme four addressed the fourth research question: what is the significance of the possible benefits of improved sustainability practice in the Nigerian telecommunications industry? Theme four addressed the fourth research question: What model can be developed to improve sustainability practices in Nigeria based on a case study of MTN Nigeria? Each theme is discussed in further detail below.

4.3.1 Theme one –

Some of the sustainability Interviewees were asked about their perceptions of sustainability in the organizational context. One of the critical answers by the group manager of MTN was that MTN tries to consider the environment, the economy, and social issues, which are the pillars of sustainability. In terms of the environment, the company considers health and safety issues by looking at sustainability from a broad perspective. Regarding the social pillar, the company is concerned about human rights and the economy. In the words of the group manager of sustainability:

'For MTN, sustainability is about value creation consisting of the three economic, social, and environmental pillars. MTN's vision for sustainability is to protect and create shared value for our company and shareholders through environmentally and socially responsible core business practices.'

Understanding sustainability is critical to all telecommunication players. Eleven out of the twelve participants in this study understood sustainability. They highlighted the importance of sustainability practice as vital for telecommunication business, and this incorporated the three pillars of sustainability. Unsurprisingly, a lack of best practices for sustainability was identified as the most significant barrier to the thriving telecommunications industry in Nigeria. A further view of sustainability practice in Nigeria systems was provided by the senior manager of NCC, who said

'From my perspective, I see the industry as reliable and efficient but needs more reinforcement to improve.'

Another MTN staff member was interviewed and asked what sustainability practices mean to MTN, mainly to improve the customer experience. The interviewee believed sustainability is about protecting and creating shared value for MTN and its stakeholders via environmentally and socially responsible core business 126 practices. Co-operation and partnerships help

MTN accelerate the pace. MTN's annual sustainability report (2017) states that its sustainability practice has several broad-based functions that focus on MTN Nigeria's efforts in CSR ideas to reduce poverty and foster sustainable development in Nigeria. It was created in September 2004 after stakeholder meetings to empower education, health, and the economy. MTN, Nigeria, has implemented sustainability through the launch of the MTN Foundation. They have remained committed to improving individual and communal lives through social investment projects that nurture people's inherent abilities. These activities care for, and respect people's dignity and help create economic value in their lives (Group Manager MTN sustainability). Their understanding of best practice is evident as one of the interviewees commented:

'Nigeria telecommunication is looking out for best practices for sustainability, copying the standard global best practices from the developed country through implementing some policies and projects such as the collation of base stations.' This makes sustainability the overarching theme that reappears throughout this study. There appears to be an elevated consensus between the remaining participants that sustainability practices are essential for any telecommunications company to remain in business.

4.3.2 Theme 2 Inhibitors of Sustainability

The factors inhibiting sustainability practices in the company were also discussed. Some interviewees commented on the varied factors affecting the practice of sustainability. Another significant factor inhibiting sustainability practice in the company was mentioned, as one of the interviewees commented.

Some impediments to the growth of digital inclusion and sustainable impacts are rooted in structural industry constraints such as access to enough radio spectrum to enable service rollout, energy shortage, or the cost of capital needed for infrastructural rollout. Some of the challenges MTN is facing in implementing practice are the dynamics of politics and security challenges that pose a threat to sustainability and implementation.

One of the interviewees noted that MTN does not have a direct sustainability policy and that NCC, the governing body, does not have an existing telecommunications department to monitor industry sustainability practices. Another interviewee said, "MTN has policies put in place for compliance of all environmental regulations which supports sustainability practices in the company.' Many interviewees commented that the factors inhibiting sustainability practice are changes that often occur to sustainability policies and increases in taxation. This affects the cost of running the company and its sustainability practices. The grouping of stories was linked to the industry, suggesting that some factors inhibit sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunication industry. An improved sustainability practice will facilitate best practices for sustainability in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. Identifying the factors that impede sustainability in the telecommunication industry is essential to this study.

4.3.3 Theme 3 - degrees of the impact of sustainability practice.

Nigeria's telecommunication industry has different players with different degrees of impact on sustainability practices. The current state of sustainability practices in the telecommunications industry. Nigeria, this is a vital question that needs to be answered during data collection. NCC is the regulatory body responsible for monitoring Nigerian telecommunications. Hence, the first question was put to the senior manager of NCC to address current sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. In his own words.

The telecommunication industry is dynamic, and power taxation, the telecommunication sector needs to experience long-term growth and sustainability, which means it needs to focus on innovative business practices. Nigeria's telecommunication industry is growing amazingly fast in the market.

The telecommunications industry in Nigeria has embraced sustainability practices in several ways, using many methods. The industry searches for best practices for sustainability. The industry is dynamic, making room for improvements to facilitate sustainability practices and learn from other developed nations. The group manager of sustainability recalled the degree of sustainability.

'As a group manager in sustainability, I will speak from the top generally regarding sustainability. The company considers the environment, economy, and social pillars of sustainability. From the environmental aspect, the company believes that health and safety issues can arise; looking at sustainability at border length for the social pillar, the company is concerned about human rights and then the economy; from my view, I would say MTN's sustainability practice is rated medium due to some constraints the company faces in trying to implement some of the practices.'

Although many interviewees pointed out different views on sustainability practices and their impact, there was a clear consensus amongst participants that sustainability is essential as it can sustain businesses. Commenting on best practices around sustainability in the industry, the group manager noted that the Nigerian telecommunications industry needs to improve its sustainability practices. This will also increase the degree of impact in some practice areas, which again links to the overarching theme: what is sustainability? Sustainability is defined in the literature as the ability to focus on the desires of the present without compromising future generations' capacity to meet their wants. The significance and benefits of sustainability practice are discussed next.

4.3.4 Theme 4 - Significance and benefits of sustainability practices

Nigeria Communication Commission is the regulatory body responsible for the telecommunications industry in Nigeria. Based on the study's findings, the NCC needs a sustainability department that monitors and measures sustainability practices. This compares to other developed nations with commissions and health and safety departments that oversee activities conducted by the different telecommunications companies. The manager of NCC was asked about the best way to facilitate the implementation of sustainability practices in mobile telecommunications in Nigeria. He responded that:

'From my point of view, I will advise the environmental pillar of sustainability. It should be looked more into to prove that the level of danger to nearby residents is being considered. The mask fixing policies and collaboration with agencies are established and functional.' He also said that "...from my point of view, the criteria to be considered necessary for sustainable development in Nigeria should be a continuous review of the policy already on the ground for sustainability and copying from other developed countries.

MTN staff were also interviewed to learn more about the Nigerian telecommunications regulatory authority and sustainability. One interviewee replied:

'We do not have a direct sustainability policy for MTN Nigeria, but that organization has a group sustainability policy. You can read from the journal I inbox on your MTN group, which can be found on the social and ethical statement of the 2017 sustainability report.'

Another of the interviewees responded by saying that the dynamics of politics and security challenges threaten sustainability. In terms of the implementation costs within MTN, however, to attain standard practices in the telecommunications sector, there must be a continuous process of tracking policies, methods, and updates, when and where necessary, to accommodate new needs. Another MTN staff member noted that, in terms of implementing sustainability practices, the aim is to upgrade to meet the ever-changing demands of customers more efficiently. The group manager of MTN Sustainability shared some thoughts on the regulatory and sustainability challenges, including the increasingly uncertain regulation and economic and competitive environment in which the organization continues to trade.

'P12 commented, 'Nigeria telecommunication is open to learning new knowledge to improve sustainability practice and to gain more understanding from other developed countries on best practices in sustainability, such as introducing motoring techniques on sustainability practices in the telecommunication industry in Nigeria.'

If P11 suggests the sector is open to learning, then this signifies improved sustainability practice so that companies will benefit from sustainability practice.

'From my point of view, there should be some improvement in Nigeria's sustainability practice. For instance, the sustainability practice in the industry does not have any standard measure to access the practices of the different telecommunication industries in the country. So MTN needs some improvement, especially in the environmental aspect. The industry needs some improvement, considering the challenges MTN faces in implementing sustainability practices in Nigeria compared to our other partner countries.'

Another interviewee from MTN stated that I see many opportunities available to improve the sustainability practice already in place. After examining the above quotations, the interviewees' statements have one thing in common. Both participants mentioned improvements in the telecommunication industry. Therefore, regarding the telecommunications operators and governing body, what is the significance of the possible benefits to improve sustainability practices in Nigerian Telecoms?

Nevertheless, P9 noted That the company manages to carry staff members along in making decisions to improve the network and revenue. The focus here for this respondent is evidence of staff involvement in decision-making to improve revenue (i.e., the economic pillar.).

4.4 Summary of Chapter

This chapter presents the essential findings and analysis of in-depth interviews undertaken with significant decision-makers regarding sustainability in Nigeria's mobile telecommunications industry. The interviews sought to establish what MTN and NCC understood by the term "sustainability." Furthermore, the interviewees sought to determine if mobile telecom firms operating in Nigeria were undertaking specific policies. In that regard, questions were asked about their focus on sustainability and the need to improve sustainability in the industry by adopting sustainability performance indicators. The results reveal that MTN, one of Nigeria's leading mobile telecommunications businesses, understands sustainability practice as a critical need in business, even though this was variously stated and explained.

Furthermore, they recognized some factors that impede sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry, such as leadership, environmental impacts, the dynamics of policies, and security challenges, which are threats to sustainability and carry implementation costs. Despite varying degrees of recognition, they also acknowledged that best practices for sustainability would enable them to be competitive, profitable, and gain customer loyalty. It can be inferred that by ignoring sustainability practices, the company will become less competitive, make less profit, and, ultimately, go out of business. These results suggest that MTN and Airtel are engaged in sustainability activities.

However, the nature and character of specific sustainability activities vary from organization to organization. However, MTN's customer focus emphasizes environmental, economic, and social impacts at individual locations. To an extent, MTN has a sustainable business plan,

even with negligible impact. The results in this chapter indicate that telecommunications companies understand sustainability practices. However, the Nigerian telecommunications industry needs to see improved sustainability practices. The next chapter, therefore, discusses the outcome of the findings section.

Chapter five

Discussion of findings

5.0 introduction

This chapter comprises six sections. Section 5.0 introduces the chapter, while section 5.1 presents the outcome. Subsequently, Section 5.2 reveals the different findings about sustainability in the telecommunications industry, while Section 5.3 discusses the results of data analysis. Section 5.4 focuses on best practice models for sustainability in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. The sixth section (5.5) provides a summary of the chapter. This study aimed to evaluate sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunication industry using MTN Nigeria as the focal point of study. In doing so, the consistency of findings in the various sections with existing literature is also discussed; the research aims were to evaluate sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry.

One of the key findings of the thematic analysis is that Nigeria needs to adopt best practices to achieve sustainability in its telecommunications industry. Some gaps were identified in the existing literature, leading to the conceptual framework that is the study's outcome. Analyses of empirical studies suggest that telecommunication companies are aware of best practices, and their interpretation conforms to the multidimensional nature of the best practice concept. However, for several reasons, most felt that best practices could be more far-reaching in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. Nevertheless, many felt that best practices could be applicable if the constraints to the telecommunications industry were resolved. From the evaluation of the common issues across the survey and focus group, it can be concluded that the responses shared similarities, corroborating the findings' credibility. An assessment of the perception of best practices suggests that the core issue to focus on is the attainment of best practices.

5.1 Triangulation and participants' profile.

This section of the study compares qualitative results to sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunication industry based on MTN Nigeria telecommunications and NCC data. Documents were collected from the MTN website to establish the consistency or otherwise of responses and the extent to which the findings agree with earlier studies.

5.2 Sustainability in the Telecommunication Industry.

Comprehensively, as reflected in our predictions above, I posit that, in our data, attributing status gains to chance serves as the central mechanism leading to responses associated with the meaning of sustainability in business, recognizing that sustainability is more than just acknowledging the relevance and need to respond to social and environmental concerns as well as economic interests. Business sustainability means expanding shareholders' perceptions and following a triple-bottom-line method. Value creation goes beyond shareholder value and comprises social and environmental benefits. Businesses create value not just as a side-effect of their business but as the outcome of purposely defined aims and programs addressed at exact sustainability matters or shareholders.

These values are not only deliberated through specific programs but are also measured and reported. This view of business sustainability is well encapsulated by the definition of business sustainability used by the Network for Business Sustainability (2012): "Business sustainability is often defined as managing the triple bottom line. A process by which companies manage their economic, social, and environmental risks, obligations, and prospects.

These three influences are sometimes called "people, planet, and profits." Business sustainability is more ambitious and represents a committed approach to making sustainability an essential and unified business matter. It allows businesses to respond to concerns and addresses several fundamental values. Hence, a few economic, environmental, and social concerns form the triple bottom-line values of sustainability. Genuinely sustainable companies involve various levels of action to raise their sustainability impact and to ease struggles between financial demands and societal needs. If they act on an individual company level, they can invent their processes and products or improve their systems of governance and transparency. The impact and reach of their activities, however, will remain limited. Businesses can change their standard approaches and practices across the sector or along supply chains when engaging on an industry or cross-sectorial level. They can create transparency, share best practices, define standard rules, and set ethics. These corporate partnerships will increase the impact and outreach of sustainability strategies.

The researcher uses Braun and Clarke's (2006) six phases of thematic analysis to create the themes for this thesis. Qualitative research gathers and analyses data to offer an in-depth,

socio-contextual, comprehensive description and understanding of the research topic. Various methods are implicated with variations to the concepts, assumptions, and analytic rules applied.

Thematic analysis is the process of recognizing outlines or themes within qualitative data. Braun & Clarke (2006) propose that it is the first qualitative method to be learned as it offers essential skills that will be beneficial when conducting many other types of analysis (p.78). From the viewpoint of knowledge and teaching, a further benefit is that thematic analysis is a method rather than a methodology (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Clarke & Braun, 2013). This means that, unlike many qualitative methods, it is not wedded to an epistemological or theoretical viewpoint, which makes it a very flexible approach to application. Braun & Clarke (2006) differentiate between the two stages of themes, which are semantic and latent. Semantic themes look at the explicit or surface meanings of data and analysis without looking for anything beyond what participants say or what has been written. (p.84).

The analysis in this worked example identifies themes at the semantic level and is illustrative of a great deal of learning and teaching work. The report moves beyond reflecting what was said to emphasize explanations and interpretations. In contrast, the latent level looks beyond what has been said. It begins to classify or scrutinize underlying ideas, assumptions, conceptualizations, and ideologies theorized to form the semantic content of the data.

5.3 Research questions

5.3.1 What is sustainability (Theme 1)

To discuss theme one, the researcher first considers research question one. What is sustainability in the mobile telecommunications industry? Existing literature offers different definitions of sustainability with various interpretations, thereby making sustainability ambiguous. Sustainability is a problematic concept, and interpretations vary. It is defined variously depending on the context in which it is used. Some have defined sustainability as man's capability to preserve available natural resources. From different perspectives, however, two crucial issues are prominent. Sustainability practice consists of a TBL, sometimes called the pillars of sustainability. The TBL concept gained prominence in the 1990s at the Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro, where it was articulated using 27 principles (UN, 1995; Markley & Davis, 2007; Gopalakrishnan et al., 2012). As John Elkington proposed, the concept of TBL states that business and investors should measure their performance

against a new set of metrics - capturing economic, social, and environmental value-added during wealth creation. The data from the NCC reveals that, although sustainability is a priority for mobile telecommunications in Nigeria, further improvement is required for the industry to remain reliable.

Secondly, MTN sustainability practices are customer-centered around shareholder value, with due consideration given to the three pillars of sustainability practice. This primarily involves a method of enhancing customer experiences. Sustainability is also about protecting and creating shared value for MTN and its stakeholders via environmentally and socially responsible core business practices. Cooperation and partnerships help MTN accelerate the pace of change. Other strategies include involvement in decision-making, such as engaging staff in regular meetings with management to pool knowledge around sustainability practices. Furthermore, from a broad perspective and in the context of MTN, the responses reveal that environmental issues regarding health and safety are considered relative to sustainability.

According to the data, cooperation and partnerships help MTN accelerate. The outcome of this study reveals that MTN's staff emphasize the tenets of sustainability in their practices. The fact that sustainability is increasingly recognized in the company. However, this research evaluates sustainability practices in Nigeria's telecommunication sector; MTN Nigeria has been the focal point. In a business-to-business context, the findings relate to empirical findings that Slaper and Hall (2011) advanced. The interviews and document analysis reveal that telecommunications companies in Nigeria recognize sustainability. Upon closer examination, the indicators of best practice in a sustainable, business-to-business context provide evidence of sustainability practice. This latter point suggests that the finding is consistent with that of Gallotta (2016) and Hubbard (2009). These authors note that some businesses have handled the challenge of quantifying their TBL environmental performance by adopting internationally recognized industry-certified EMS.

These schemes help them develop, implement, and communicate environmental rules. They allow them to set objectives and goals to decrease environmental impacts, and they can observe performance against these goals. (Kolk et al.,2008). While telecommunications firms are themselves shareholders, their response and purposes can be viewed as corporate schemes in a capitalist environment regarding climate capitalism, organizational ecology, corporate citizenship, or corporate omnipotence, depending on whose views prevail. Newel & Paterson (2010), Jayant & Gowda (2014), Wright and Nyberg (2014).

A second related finding shows that the origin of the problem of sustainability lies in unsustainable economic growth and the idea that we have lived unsustainably for the past two centuries. Scientists concur that by practicing business as usual, humanity faces about unprecedented crises, including global economic failure, prevalent disease, hunger, and violence. (Martin & Schouten, 2012). Some argue that we have been consuming the planet's resources, particularly fossil fuels, at a rate that makes it impossible for them to be replaced. The two major culprits responsible for the current unsustainable economic activity are 1) a continual decline in natural resources and ecosystem services and 2) a continuous increase in the demand for resources and services. (Martin & Schouten, 2012).

Thirdly, the business sector is solely responsible for these problems since corporations are powerful economic production instruments accountable for the global use of natural resources. The irreparable damage inflicted on the ecosystem by higher than reasonable amounts of greenhouse gases, solid waste, water, and soil pollution, among others, through business activities has forced organizations to respond. In other words, this damage is primarily an economic cost to society that should be returned to shareholders as value.

Fourthly, corporations needed to be faster to embrace the concept of the environment and were unwilling to incorporate sustainability practices into their product strategies. Sustainability and 'going green' were the inherent enemies of profit due to the extra costs imposed on businesses. This negative mindset resulted from a need for more innovative strategies to manage solid waste and gas emissions and create advantages for the company. In the last two decades or so, with a greater focus on global environmental concerns, major companies have been forced to take a more sustainable approach to stakeholder demands. Over the years, however, they have also realized that innovative environmental strategies can lead to profit and make them more competitive while fulfilling consumer demands. This realization has convinced even the most ardent supporters of the profit-only approach to embracing the concept of sustainability and the value of 'going green.'

Gary (2010) defines sustainability as an administration created to protect the environment. However, applying the approach to anything other than the environment and our species is complex. Aras and Crowther (2008) argue that sustainability is primarily based on efficiency and variation. Academics define sustainability using various temporal and spatial scales (Kates et al., 2005). The preceding arguments confirm the environmental, social, and economic interconnectedness.

The effect of these findings on the relevant research questions has been discussed in chapter one. The critical finding in terms of the meaning of sustainability is that companies, to be sustainable, must ensure that they meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Companies continue to devote time to sustainability in the present corporate world. As a result, various terms have emerged that have come to be embraced, such as corporate social responsibility and sustainability.

In the telecommunications industry, as in many other businesses, the development of CR can be observed through the different mechanisms corporations use to manage matters of responsibility towards shareholders. Indeed, companies are motivated to proceed sustainably due to current developments in the industry. In the telecommunications industry, as in many other businesses, the development of CR can be observed through the different mechanisms corporations use to manage matters of responsibility towards shareholders. Indeed, companies are motivated to proceed sustainably due to current developments in the industry.

The main facets investigated are concerned with the governance structures introduced by telecommunications companies. As such, sustainability management is understood to take place at three organizational levels. First, it takes place at the corporate governance level, primarily concerned with the company's persons, departments, or boards dealing with sustainability issues. The second level defines the areas addressed in the company's strategy, i.e., employees, customers, and the environment. Lastly, the third level refers to the specific tools and programs launched by MTN Nigeria, which have been the focal point of this study.

The main facets investigated are concerned with the governance structures introduced by telecommunications companies. As such, sustainability management is understood to take place at three organizational levels. First, it takes place at the corporate governance level, primarily concerned with the company's persons, departments, or boards dealing with sustainability issues. The second level defines the areas addressed in the company's strategy, i.e., employees, customers, and the environment. Lastly, the third level refers to the specific tools and programs launched by MTN Nigeria, which have been the focal point of this study. By recycling waste products, MTN's sustainability practices also preserve natural resources for future generations.

This result might suggest that MTN believes in sustainability. However, based on findings from similar studies, a more plausible explanation is that the company believes sustainability is about preserving available natural resources, thus recycling used products. This study finds that MTN, one of the mobile telecommunications companies in Nigeria, has sustainability practices in place practice. Therefore, this study's first objective and research question have been met. Based on these findings, the following aspects of the conceptual framework proposed in Chapter 2 (Figure 3) can be illustrated in Figure 6, which depicts that mobile telecommunications firms in Nigeria exhibit the three pillars of sustainability (economic, social, and environmental). The outcome is the new conceptual model (NSPM). The last finding concerning this theme (i.e., what is sustainability) is that sustainability exists across three pillars, specifically the economic, social, and environmental pillars.

Fig 4 Pillars of sustainability

MTN seeks to develop its sustainability practices by dedicating attention to matters of social and environmental engagement, as suggested by Crane and Matten (2004). Sustainability has been an important conceptual tool for assessing economic and social development and business activity more generally. This finding reveals much about MTN's sustainability practices. The corporate documents that were examined also contain information on MTN 's approach to sustainability on page 5 of the MTN 2017 sustainability report. These findings were essential to the study since they shed light on the approach MTN applies to sustainability practice. The relevant part of the report has this to say.

Sustainability is about value creation consisting of three economic, social, and environmental pillars. MTN's vision for sustainability is to protect and create shared value for our company and shareholders through environmentally and socially responsible business practices. We structure our implementation efforts by adopting the materiality-based approach to achieve this vision. This allows us to follow our efforts in the following ways: (a) creating sustainable economic value, (b) taking responsibility for our environmental Impact, and (c) contributing to vibrant, thriving communities in our market by addressing matters of good governance and

ethics. The digital world transforms lives as the leading player in many of our markets. (MTN sustainability report, 2019).

To summarize, it can be said that organizations try to meet their responsibilities towards society and the environment by sharing the values encapsulated by terms like corporate social responsibility and sustainability. These values are communicated to internal and external shareholders. These can be practically incorporated into the core business through various initiatives and measurements. The preceding discussion of the main findings reveals how vital sustainability is to telecommunications.

5.3.2 Inhibitors of sustainability (Theme two)

Research question two focuses on identifying the factors that inhibit current sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. An important finding from this theme is that cross-cutting - factors inhibit the adoption of best practices. These cross-cutting factors encompass industrial constraints, shortages of energy, and high capital costs. Electricity is a primary concern in Nigerian business today. Due to a continued lack of energy companies, telecommunication companies energize their equipment mainly through renewable energy/ solar hybrid standalone power plants. Irrespective of the expansion of different sustainability strategies, risks arise from various telecommunications industry activities. These are seldom significantly reduced because many challenges beset sustainability implementation (Muduli et al., 2012).

The following inhibitors of sustainability implementation were identified: 1. industrial constraints, shortages of energy and high capital costs, and sustainability policy. 2. political dynamics and security challenges. 3. Different strategies of sustainability and increases in taxation. 4. There is low environmental awareness amongst employees and high running costs. 5. NCC, the governing body, does not have a sustainability department or tools to measure company sustainability practices. 6. shortages of sustainability information and related costs. Nevertheless, relevant environmental information is necessary to translate sustainability strategies into real action (Clark, 2000). Highly educated employees easily understand environmental issues and can find appropriate solutions for related problems.

Therefore, the lack of experts to monitor sustainability problems in the telecommunication industry is a critical obstacle that inhibits telecommunications companies from undertaking sustainability activities (Hillary, 2004). The causes of these problems could be related to NCC's lack of sufficient benchmarking data to monitor sustainability indicators for best practices. The causes of these problems could be related to the fact that NCC lacks the benchmarks to monitor sustainability best practices. Although this research evaluates sustainability practices in Nigerian telecommunications, the study also explains why Nigerian telecommunications businesses have not adopted best practices. There are several reasons behind this. Poor sustainability practices in developing economies such as Nigeria occur because of the scarcity of amenities and poor infrastructure.

These practices are aggravated by low access to energy in Nigeria and poor access to renewable energy as an alternative to electric power. The value of human beings and natural capital also exacerbates them. It is argued that an intermittent electricity supply stifles economic growth in Nigeria due to its outdated infrastructure and distribution issues (Oyedepo, 2012).

Three pillars for creating a stable economy with a sustainable energy development framework are proposed for Nigeria. The first pillar is the social welfare of citizens. However, the first pillar can only be attained without considering the increased productivity from ICT, which can lead to increased productivity and social welfare.

Also noteworthy here are the increased environmental pressures and carbon emissions. Energy access has been used interchangeably in modern energy (electricity and liquefied natural gas). Conventional energy (biomass) and various definitions of energy access exist in the international research theatre. Research by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) Sustainable Energy Group found that energy in Africa comprises electrical energy, contemporary fuels, mechanical power, cookery fuels, and better cooking stoves (UNDP, 2009).

The above result is corroborated by the interviews for this research with the eleven MTN team members. The MTN group manager noted some impediments to the growth of digital inclusion and sustainable impacts rooted in structural industry constraints, such as access to sufficient radio spectrums to enable service rollout. She also spoke of energy shortages and the cost of capital needed for infrastructure rollout.

This reflects the state of sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications sector. This finding is consistent with Oyedepo's (2012) work, which posits that a shortage of electric power is a common challenge faced by corporations in emerging economies. Lack of electricity increases energy costs within a carbon-constrained global economy. Emerging economies present their unique issues, such as scarcity of power supplies. Other issues are the standard practice of supplementing energy via self-generated heat and diesel-powered generators and increased carbon emissions that necessitate higher operating costs.

The third significant finding in this theme is related to energy savings. It has been evident from many research studies that energy-saving and sustainability are among the most common research areas in the modern era. Increases in energy costs and the environmental impact of generating electricity make it necessary to save energy. There is a need to take global ecological protection seriously, ensuring that "green integration" can be achieved. This involves a set of solutions that contribute to environmental protection regarding energy systems design, architectural and building design, and energy management. Currently, global attention is on green energy, which includes renewable energy and power generation sources like solar, hydroelectric, wind, and biogas/biomass power.

These are the standard environmentally friendly and non-polluting energy sources that can be used effectively for energy-saving purposes. Green or renewable energy is the best alternative to traditional power and associated high costs. Energy-saving is a means to minimize the use of some forms of energy sources like gas and electricity for environmental, cost, and socio-economic reasons. Energy savings are linked to the amount of saved energy determined by measuring and estimating consumption before and after implementing an energy efficiency improvement measure while ensuring normalization for external conditions that affect energy consumption. Energy savings have been in use in the world's developed nations for some decades.

The concept is now spreading to developing countries, given the recent patterns of rapid industrialization that have accompanied additional energy requirements. Energy savings are a new approach to maintaining a suitable environment and controlling greenhouse gas emissions released because of power generation through fossil fuels. As mentioned in the literature review, environmental degradation damages the biosphere due to human activity. Environmental degradation happens when nature's resources (such as trees, habitat, earth, water, and air) are consumed faster than nature can replenish them.

This occurs when pollution results in irreparable environmental damage or human beings destroy or damage ecosystems in development. Nigeria's industrialization is entirely unsustainable to the environment. Ecological degradation can take many forms and halts the extraction of natural resources. It is defined by deforestation and desertification—removal and radioactivity. The leading causes of such degradation include overpopulation, urban sprawl, industrial pollution, waste dumping, intensive farming, overfishing, industrialization, invasive species, and environmental regulations. Environmental sustainability aims to minimize these and other causes and to halt and, ideally, reverse the processes they lead. An unsustainable situation occurs when natural capital (the sum of nature's resources) is used up faster to replenish. Sustainability requires little human activity and the use of nature's resources at a rate that can be filled naturally; the findings from this theme illuminate the current state of sustainability in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. Making the most of profit and cutting costs is an ideal global economic perception, especially in manufacturing, production, services, and utilities. While reducing costs, one of the significant challenges is that of strategic sustainability design. This is partly due to the current CSR state.

An improved sustainability practice in the Nigerian telecommunications industry will be beneficial to the industry. The result from this study can be further investigated to copy practices twice as has been indicated in developed countries in using Dow Jones sustainability indices underscoring the centrality of the three pillars of sustainability. The analysis reveals the state of sustainability practices in Nigeria and the challenges the sector faces in implementing sustainability practices. Furthermore, these findings indicate the importance of sustainability.

These findings contribute to the achievement of the study's second objective and respond to research question two, which sought to identify the factors that inhibit current sustainability practices in Nigeria telecommunications. Internally, factors such as a shortage of energy, sustainability policy, uncertainty, and changes in taxation all positively impact sustainability practice. Developed countries like the United Kingdom have indicators to measure sustainability practices. Nigeria's telecommunication industry requires a governing body that should be responsible for such action. Indicators can indicate each telecommunication industry's technology, governance, and social performance.

These should be ranked accordingly. Sustainability policies in the Nigerian telecommunications industry must be addressed since these are a barrier to best practices

in sustainability. Taxation frequently changes, which means companies incur more capital costs. Analysis suggests that some factors inhibit sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. Adopting best practices for sustainability will drive sustainability practices for MTN and other telecommunications companies in Nigeria.

These findings correspond with the literature, revealing that the telecommunication sector is probably the primary technology sector in the world. Since the arrival of cellular communication technologies, telecommunication towers (transceivers) have cropped up in areas where human settlements are located. In regions without electricity, energy is supplied to towers through different sources. Specifically, these are diesel generators and battery systems. Therefore, Newig and Monstadt (2008) posit that the technology sector directly impacts the settings and the scheme of technologies used.

We are amid a fast-changing and exciting digital revolution. This era of disruption only depends on which side of the fence we choose to sit on. Every day, people worldwide are working together, harnessing the power of digital technology to generate ideas and innovative solutions that address some of the world's most significant challenges, including access to food and water, climate change, health, poverty, quality education, and unemployment. Daily, we wake up to the news of incredible technological breakthroughs and ideas that can lead to exponential growth and progress.

Concepts such as cryptocurrencies, crowdsourced innovations, 3D printing, artificial intelligence, big data, and the Internet of Things (IoT) are particularly inspiring for us at MTN, as these open a world of excellent new opportunities for industrial and economic ecosystems and human development. As the digital economy evolves, these opportunities are also forcing new ways of thinking about how people's spaces and assets are used, how people interact, and what talents are needed in the data age. Transformative developments are exciting but also bring about social and regulatory uncertainty. We are witnessing increased barriers and digital 'borders' created around the internet. Growing cybersecurity and other risks have spurred authorities to enhance oversight and governance of the internet, which places their position at odds with society's demands for online freedoms. (MTN, 2017).

Sustainability practices in developing economies such as Nigeria occur because of the scarcity of amenities and infrastructures available to companies. Currently, these practices

can be a result of the poor state of energy access in Nigeria. They are also a consequence of access to renewable energy as an alternative to electric power and the value of human beings and natural capital.

Fig 5 Determinant of sustainability practice

From the preceding discussion, the findings reveal that the factors inhibiting sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry are significant. The findings of question three are discussed below.

5.3.3 Degree of the Impact of Sustainability Practice (Theme three)

Research question three seeks to establish the methods of practice put in place and how these impact sustainability levels in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. An essential finding about this theme is the degree of the impact of sustainability practices in Nigeria's telecommunication companies. The two critical issues observed from the findings of the thematic analysis relate to the significance and benefits of sustainability practices. Analysis suggests that telecommunications companies in Nigeria understand sustainability practices. Consequently, they undertake the necessary actions concerning sustainability practices based on various policies in place. The level of sustainability practices in the telecommunications industry, however, must be improved because NCC does not have an indicator to assess the performance of its companies in terms of sustainability.

Secondly, there should be more transparency regarding the governance structure of each company. It is impossible to make clear statements about how sustainability is managed internally and how the initiatives launched by firms are initiated. This lack of transparency impedes several analytical aspects. The distance between sustainability departments/boards

and top management cannot be determined, and this aspect helps determine whether sustainability issues are approached as decentralized or centralized. Furthermore, the degree of the impact of sustainability practices cannot be determined. However, the data collected provides insights into the degree of the effects of sustainability on MTN's policies that regulate sustainability practices. The company tries to organize regular training for staff to enable them to meet customer demands. Furthermore, they incorporate staff into the decision-making of the company to improve their networks and revenue.

This finding is consistent with that of Mann et al. (2010), Carter and Easton (2011), Walker and Jones (2012), and Gopalakrishnan et al. (2012). This is because the drivers of sustainability are multiple and complex. At the heart of these are ecological motives: conserving energy, conserving resources, and reducing pollution and wastage, which are key considerations in the context of implementing sustainability. Two of these drivers, preserving energy and resources, involve processes and decisions at the production system's input end. The other two occur at the output end of the production processes.

The drivers of sustainability were also reported to be economically motivated. Indeed, companies are often determined to implement sustainability because of their revenue enrichment and cost-reducing potential (Stead and Stead, 2005). The drivers of sustainability include environmental advocacy pressures and a desire to conserve energy. The urge to reduce carbon footprints, pollution reduction, and a willingness to enhance revenue are also crucial. Companies adopt sustainability because of marketing, investor pressures, and a desire to reduce costs.

The drivers of sustainability are a combination of economic and environmental motives. (Moduli et al., 2012). The literature review highlighted that the Nigerian telecommunications industry is now the fastest-increasing market in Africa, and it is among the ten fastest-rising telecommunications businesses in the world. Making a profit and reducing costs are obvious economic ideas, particularly in industrial construction services and services within companies. However, when it comes to cutting down on costs, one of the major tasks to tackle is the strategy that strategic sustainability is partially effective because of present trends in CSR.

Earlier studies have established that sustainable practices within any business can increase revenue growth and business worth. Henceforth, measures to save energy and reduce GHG

could be one way to sustain business practices within the telecoms sector. Corporations in both developed and emerging economies face similar challenges in meeting the maximization of goals as part of economic sustainability while maintaining the same purpose-driven focus on attaining social and environmental objectives. A second and related finding is the Dow Jones Sustainability Index, which underscores the centrality of the three pillars of sustainability, whereby best practices have been documented for over a decade for companies operating in various sectors. These are also considered helpful sustainability measures and benchmarking tools. Another significant finding under this theme is evidence that the Nigerian telecommunications industry requires reformation. It has been argued that the NCC Act of 2003 is outdated. It should be based on competition in the industry to bring about efficiency, productivity, and economic development. These findings imply that Nigeria is still undergoing sustainability development and requires more improvements. However, the industry needs to be ready to embrace best practices in sustainability to learn from other developed nations. Many studies have been carried out to look at best sustainability practices.

These can be applied to the Nigerian situation to drive sustainability. Energy savings have been in use in the world's industrialized countries for years, and the idea is just starting to spread to emerging nations such as Nigeria. However, such ambitions create additional demand for energy. The above strategies are helpful for the Nigerian telecommunications industry to improve its sustainability practices. The third significant finding under this theme is that best practices for sustainability are adopted in developed countries in the telecommunications industry. This finding reiterates that best practices for sustainability in telecommunications are vital. However, Nigeria's sustainability practices need to be improved to adopt best practices in terms of sustainability. These findings are consistent with previous research (Dow Jones, 2014),

The existing state literature predominantly focuses on sustainability issues in developed economies where high levels of efficiency have been achieved, and some authors have started focusing on emerging economies where the most significant collective gains are salient. Previous research (Jayant & Gowda, 2014) on inequalities in knowledge production and IPCC's geographic dispersion has informed several stakeholders' views. Developing economies have some of the fastest uptakes of ICT and, as observed in earlier literature (Sadorsky, 2012) and (Kanter, 2008) (Sadorsky, 2012), the ICT industry is responsible for

2% of global GHG emissions. Economists claim this will increase to 8% by 2020, mainly from the powering of servers and cloud computing (World Economic Forum, 2009).

A fourth related finding concerns value creation for shareholders and corporate social responsibilities to customers. MTN sustainability practices have different functions which are broad in scope. One of the activities is the MTN Foundation Ltd, which focuses on MTN Nigeria's corporate social responsibility initiatives to reduce poverty and foster sustainable development.

The most exciting aspect of these findings is that MTN's fundamental grasp of sustainability has kept the company floating this long. They have created sustainable economic value and have developed IoT solutions that have transformed the natural, economic, and social environment, and they have taken responsibility for their environmental impacts.

This study has identified that MTN partners with local authorities to facilitate sustainability practices in the company. MTN Nigeria partners with a government regulatory research body call Nesael. They work with tower managers to collocate the base station to reduce costs and control carbon emissions by sharing network sites. This enhances strong sustainability leadership. These findings suggest that, in general, sustainability policy is concerned with health and safety, and waste products should be appropriately recycled. MTN recycles its waste products through network-based sites owned by tower management companies that are rented. However, MTN still recycles waste products through two other channels.

One is a supplier take-back scheme whereby the company contracts with the original supplier. The second is the asset manufacturer, which supports recycling or refurbishing old network equipment at the end of its useful life. The second channel is the ongoing plan to work on e-waste management in partnership with many stakeholders under the NESREA EPRON initiative. Nigeria's sustainability policies for the telecommunications industry are functional. However, regarding the environment, there is a need for more sensitization to demonstrate the level of danger and policies for mask fixing in host communities. This will enable many businesses to collaborate with agencies to promote good practice. Both the environmental and social pillars of sustainability require more efforts to impact the lives of individuals in spaces where the company has based its sites.

The last finding concerning this theme (the degree of impact of sustainability practice) is that sustainability practice has some degree of influence in Nigerian telecommunications. These findings indicate that MTN understands sustainability practices in business and has created different policies and monitoring bodies within the company to ensure best practice is carried out. MTN is customer-centered regarding sustainability; therefore, it prioritizes stakeholder value creation. MTN Nigeria has no direct sustainability policy and tends to align with the broader group's guidelines. This is because NCC, the governing body, has not created a sustainability indicator to monitor sustainability practices in the industry.

Evidence from the documents analyzed shows that the company focuses more on the environmental pillar of sustainability to create positive impacts. Every company, therefore, has different sets of policies baked into its operations. Despite that level of impact, MTN's sustainability practices still face some challenges, so the sector needs to improve its sustainability practices. Previous findings suggest that sustainable practices within any business can raise revenue growth and increase the worth of the company.

This has pushed many businesses in Nigeria towards implementing and creating sustainable chain theories and practices to reduce the total cost of procedures. This was particularly the case between the years 2003 and 2015. For Nigeria to adopt best sustainability practices, there must be a high degree of sustainability impact on the industry. To summarize, this thematic finding supports the achievement of the third objective and third research question, which sought to establish the degree of methods of practice put in place that impact sustainability in Nigeria. Internally, as far as organizational systems are concerned, these factors can be said to have a relationship with sustainability in Nigeria's mobile telecommunications industry. Based on these findings, none of the aspects of the conceptual model proposed in Chapter 4 (Figure 5) suggest that organizational systems have a positive relationship with sustainability practices. However, the commitment offered by companies is often insufficient. However, adequate performance measurements need to be created to verify satisfactory levels of standards and to determine whether companies fulfill these standards. While one can find various approaches for measuring performance, a

A breakthrough approach is not yet available. Hence, the development of a model for Nigerian sustainability practice is critical. The findings about the degree of impact of sustainability

practice on the Nigerian telecommunication industry are significant. In this sense, new knowledge has been created.

5.3.4 Significance and Benefits of Sustainability Practices (Theme four)

Research question four aimed to examine the significance of the possible benefits of improving sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. An essential finding from this study is that sustainable practices within any industry improve profit maximization and create a brand image. This has directed many industries to adopt and design sustainable chain models and methods that aim to reduce the overall cost of operations. This finding is consistent with that of Zhang (2014). This is undoubtedly true of the past thirteen years, from 2003- 2015, during which there has been enormous development within the Nigerian telecoms subscribers' base.

This has led to increased average energy demands by service providers to deliver telecommunications services. Two crucial issues should be noted. First, energy-saving procedures and decreasing greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) are the surest methods for sustainable business practices within the telecoms industry. This has encouraged telecommunications companies in Nigeria to start looking for ways to reduce their running costs and general expenses.

The Nigerian telecommunications sector is currently the fastest-growing market in Africa, and it is amongst the ten highest-growth telecommunications industries in the world. However, indicators for measuring sustainability practices in developed countries can be copied to ascertain sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. Secondly, energy savings are a new method to keep the environment fit and to control greenhouse gas emissions as by-products of fossil fuel power generation in Nigeria. The development of energy infrastructure has not and will not be able to keep up with economic growth at the current level of investment in infrastructure (Aliyu et al., 2013). One crucial perspective of this is that a lack of adequate support may hamper the pace of economic development. Most households and businesses rely on electricity generated from diesel-powered generators to meet demand. This method of generating electricity is dirty, intermittent, inefficient, and labor-intensive, producing significant carbon at higher running costs. A related finding is that a sustainable business must look for ways to embrace best practices, make a profit, and stay in business. This study sheds light on contemporary energy-saving ideas, which will enhance

sustainability and efficacy within the telecoms industry in Nigeria. This allows for further consolidation of Nigeria's industrial sector and provides broader knowledge of sustainable management and energy savings. The findings also show how telecom operators approach cell site base station management. Renewable energy technology can power the base stations, and according to the findings of this research, these are environmentally friendly energy sources.

The findings also clarify several energy-saving concepts related to sustainability and the effectiveness of sustainability efforts within Nigeria's telecoms industries. This will add to the literature on sustainability, given broader knowledge of sustainability management and energy-saving towards improving business productivity, most notably in telecommunication. The third significant finding under this theme is that an intermittent electricity supply stifles Nigerian economic growth due to obsolete infrastructure and distribution issues (Oyedepo, 2012).

Three pillars for creating a stable economy with a sustainable energy development framework are recommended for Nigeria. However, the first pillar, which is economic, can be achieved without due consideration of increased productivity from ICT, which could lead to increased productivity and social welfare. Productivity has grown in terms of environmental pressures and carbon emissions. Research by Lin (2014) looked at some methods of cutting energy costs, which also caused reductions in CO₂ emissions. This was achieved by encouraging low energy consumption.

Factors such as the price of energy, industry structure, profit margin, and technology were added to the industry to analyze energy intensity to create a better result. There have been some financial impacts in other economies, such as the finance industry, due to more general growth within the telecoms sector. For instance, Satya Shah et al. (2017) note that the telecom industry increases and facilitates improved performance levels within banking services through operations and service provision. This is achieved via ATM services, general banking transactions, money transfers, electronic banking, and other eCommerce-based banking transactions. The same is true for different industries such as advertising, media, and the broader service sectors due to the substantial growth within the telecoms industry. This study presents comprehensive research on the cost of running telecommunications cell sites. It also looks at practices in terms of cell site management and ways of effecting reductions by network providers to create better alternative power sources

and management practices. Some sustainability indicators are considered valid (Evans, 2009), such as measuring the cost and availability of electricity from government grids, measuring the costs of generating energy, and estimating the maintenance and running costs required for greenhouse emissions and social impacts such as noise pollution, security, and hazards.

In pursuing sustainability, the Nigerian telecommunications industry could emulate developed countries in terms of their practices to remain sustainable. The sector is dynamic and has created room for facilitating sustainability practices. Sustainability and energy savings are some of the more common research areas within developing countries due to the uprising of sustainable practices within domestic and commercial usage. ICT has been shown to contribute to economic growth and social empowerment, yet it is not clear if this means that the environmental effects of ICT are nullified.

This notion is unlikely as the incremental diffusion of ICT comes at a negative cost to the environment due to the unique diversity of existing issues. Indeed, these issues exist not only within emerging and developing economies but globally. A comparative study based on sustainability best practices could address the gap in the literature in terms of sustainability practices and opportunities and barriers for sustainability gains in the Nigerian context.

A fourth related finding is the significance of these findings in the context of the Nigerian telecommunications industry. Again, these observations resonate with earlier findings (see Slaper & Hall, 2011). Businesses generally follow the principles of the TBL framework by John Elkington as a new measure of corporate performance to teach environmental and social concerns. TBL is an accounting framework incorporating three performance dimensions: social, environmental, and financial. This differs from traditional reporting frameworks, including ecological (or environmental) and social measures that can be difficult to assign appropriately to the eight measurement means. The TBL dimensions are called the three Ps: people, planet, and profits. These findings add to the literature on sustainability practices in Nigerian telecommunications. Studies by Zhang (2014) and Ehnert et al. (2016) on Nigerian telecoms underscore several benefits concerning sustainability practices. These authors highlight the key benefits of best practices in sustainability, such as improving brand image and competitive advantage, increasing productivity, reducing cost, and increasing the ability of a business to comply with the regulation. Other benefits include the ability to attract

employees and investors, the ability to reduce waste, and the ability to make shareholders happy.

In this way, brand image and competitive advantage can be improved to favor companies that actively support communities. Increased productivity and reduced costs can herald the development of sustainable practices, which lends itself to an efficient operation that streamlines efforts and conserves resources. Reducing waste is most likely the simplest and most obvious way to engage in sustainable practices. Based on an empirical survey of Nigerian telecommunications, the industry's benefits from effectively implementing best practices are manifold. As previously highlighted, half of the respondents felt that many benefits could be achieved, and 28% were quite specific that quality reductions in waste and increased productivity could reduce costs.

The remaining 14.9% cited other advantages of best practices in sustainability, such as service efficiency, increased productivity, increased employment, and poverty reduction. Indeed, the focus group responses summarise that Nigeria will significantly benefit when best sustainability practices are implemented fully. Some suggested that if the best practice for sustainability is in place, this will reduce the cost of production. For instance, MTN spends money operating its machines and must hire its base station, which comes at a higher price. In Nigeria, the benefits of sustainability cannot be overemphasized. The existing literature asserts that adopting best practices for sustainability initiatives could reduce environmental and social destruction (Moffatt, I., 2000; Baumgärtner et al., 2008; 153 Hardin, 1993; Goodland, 1995; Robertson,2017). Previous research has been committed to the historical development of sustainability (Kidd, 1992; Wheeler (2004);). Hugé et al. (2013).

Others spoke about how sustainability leads to increases in the market value of company stocks (Bose and Pal, 2012). Some other researchers have focused on the drivers and barriers of sustainability (Mann et al., 2010; Barve & Muduli,2013; Dashore and Sohani, 2013). Others have written about green/sustainable supply chain management (Carte and Rogers, 2007; Linton et al., 2007; Wagner, 2010; Carter and Easton, 2011; Gopalakrishnan et al., 2012). The literature has also focussed on sustainability integration into companies and the benefits of increased awareness of the environmental impacts of industrial growth. There has been a further focus on resource-supply reductions and changes in consumer behavior,

which have led to the development of sustainability practices in telecommunications companies (Wagner and Svensson, 2010; Carter & Puck,2010). Bukoye and Peter (2014) suggest that the applicability of best value in the Nigerian public sector could improve public sector policies and practices in the context of public sector organizations.

They discuss the relationships between environment, economics, and social performance within the telecommunications sector. These findings ensure the achievement of the fourth objective of the study and the fourth research, which sought to examine the significance of the possible benefits of improved sustainability in Nigerian telecommunications. Specifically relating to sustainability, it has been established that best practice results in repeated sustainability satisfaction. Based on these findings, some aspects of the conceptual model proposed in Chapter 4 (Figure 5) are confirmed in Figure 10, which depicts that improved sustainability practices in Nigeria's mobile telecommunications industry can positively influence Nigeria's telecommunications.

Fig 8 Best practice

To summarize, the central finding relates to sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications markets and whether there is a specific common trend with best practices. Finally, analysis suggests that Nigeria is ready to embrace best practices in sustainability. The study reveals that adopting best practices for sustainability in Nigerian telecommunications could lead to more outstanding quality and customer satisfaction. This claim to new knowledge is discussed in the section below.

5.4 How the themes were created.

Themes were created from the research question to achieve all research objectives.

Theme 1 is sustainability; this theme was created to understand sustainability and its vital role in the telecommunication industry. Theme 2 was created to identify the factors that inhibit sustainability in the telecommunication industry. Theme 3 was made to understand the

sector's sustainability degree after critical analysis. Theme 4 was designed to prove the significance and benefits of sustainability practice; in this last theme, I understand the benefits in the industry.

5.5 Conceptual model.

A conceptual model based on the literature reviewed in chapter two is formulated in this chapter. Figure 6 shows the sustainability practice model proposed by this study. The model discusses the factors that inhibit the adoption of best practices for sustainability based on an assessment of sustainability practices. The Nigeria Sustainability Practice Model (NSPM) model was developed based on the research gaps identified in the literature review and empirical findings. As a result, two research questions were addressed as follows:

1. What factors inhibit current sustainability practices in Nigerian telecommunications?
2. What is the significance of the possible benefits of improving sustainability in telecommunications? This process can be undertaken by several companies operating in Nigeria. Telecommunications can embrace policies (Dolowitz and Marsh, 1996; 2000; Evans and Davies, 1999). Horowitz and Marsh (2000, page 13) suggest that, although these factors lead to various forms of transfer, four different degrees of transfer can be identified: copying, emulation, combinations, and inspiration. This definition, coupled with previous research advanced by Dolowitz and Marsh (2000), suggests an urgent need to implement best practices to improve sustainability in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. This provides a significant impetus for the conceptual framework introduced in this chapter. The researcher-maintained objectivity in the review process through the principles of benchmarking for identifying organizational sustainability best practices. Schalock et al. (2016) note that sustainability practices/initiatives/programs can be benchmarked if these fall within the framework of the principles of benchmarking.

Figure 7 Qualitative principles for identifying the sustainability best practices of organizations.

The authors further argue that best practices are always clearly articulated and carry supporting evidence of value creation. The principles of benchmarking are superior to other frameworks used for identifying organizational best practices (such as the European Foundation for Quality Management model). There are two main reasons: (1) the principles are derived from the organizational sustainability literature and hence are more relevant to this study; and (2) the principles, in contrast to other frameworks, are flexible and do not limit the focus of the reviewer to specific organizational functions. Based on the findings of Schalock et al. (2016), only the organizational practices considered for counting as best practices offer enough information about sustainability goals and outcomes.

These practices conform to the principles of benchmarking. Analysis suggests

four main themes that could help telecommunications companies in Nigeria with sustainability. Each theme corresponds to a functional area and type of best practice. The themes are (1) What is sustainability? (2) Inhibitors of sustainability (3) The degree of the impact of sustainability practice. (4) The significance and benefits of sustainability practice.

The above analysis has led to developing a content framework (CF) for the telecommunication industry in Nigeria based on four sustainability themes and 12 themes relating to the Nigerian context. Nevertheless, the sustainability themes outlined in this work must not be considered in isolation since organizational operations are usually interlinked.

Therefore, advancing a holistic approach to using CM in practice and research is essential. The present study was designed to evaluate sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. Evidence from findings was used to create four themes to use as indicators for the model developed for the Nigerian telecommunications industry. These themes address the research questions and central aim of the study. Analyses from these studies suggest that telecommunications companies are aware of the best sustainability practices, and their interpretation conforms to the multidimensional nature of the best practice concept. However, most of them felt that best practices for sustainability do not exist in the Nigerian telecommunications industry for various reasons. Nevertheless, they mostly felt that best practices are applicable in Nigeria if the constraints to sustainability practices are resolved. From evaluating common issues across the survey and focus group, these analyses enhance the credibility of the findings.

The findings identified are, therefore, an accurate representation of the needs of these companies. An evaluation of the organization's understanding of best practices for sustainability identifies that sustainability policy is the core issue to focus on for attaining best practices for sustainability. In summary, the NSPM is primarily built upon the triple bottom line, which involves best practices' economic, social, and environmental attributes. Furthermore, to some extent, sustainability practices in Nigeria telecommunication have overcome these negative company perceptions of Nigerian sustainability practices, and the

twelve issues identified have had a role to play. This NSPM, therefore, provides a helpful tool for the telecommunications sector and companies in delivering their services. The model could also assist telecommunications operators by acting as a prompt list to prevent any issues from being overlooked while also working as a benefit to the industry by ensuring all the critical problems have been identified and provided solutions.

5.6 Benefits of Improved Sustainability Practice.

The findings from this study resonate with the definition of sustainable development offered by the Brundtland's Commission Commission's (1987) report, which accepts the possibility of improved sustainability practice leading to a better quality of life for everyone, now and for generations to come. It offers a vision of progress that integrates immediate and longer-term needs, locally and globally. It regards social, economic, and environmental needs as inseparable and interdependent components of human program.

5.7 Summary of chapter.

This chapter has triangulated qualitative and documentary findings with sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications sector. It has presented an analysis of qualitative responses from staff and document analysis, which has corroborated the fieldwork data. The discussion above has shown the different themes that emerged from the finding. This finding has advised me on the four themes that were created and used to develop the model. The findings in this respect indicate that mobile telecommunications companies in Nigeria practice sustainability. It can be argued that firms in Nigeria's mobile telecommunications industry are sustainability oriented. The findings with sustainability practices have informed the conceptual framework that is presented in this chapter.

The only internal antecedent of top management emphasis was a powerful positive understanding of sustainability practices in Nigeria. The study, however, reveals that the sustainability practice of mobile telecommunication companies in Nigeria significantly determines the economic, social, and environmental performance of businesses. The initial outcomes for the mobile telecommunication industry in Nigeria appear significant if best practices embraced.

The model formation is developed based on the conceptual framework, which discusses the current sustainability practice in Nigeria telecommunication, best practice benefits and improved model for the benefits of best practice in Nigeria telecommunication. However, the empirical findings from the field also informed the researcher in developing the model. Based on the evidence collected, Nigeria telecommunication industry will benefit from an improved sustainability practice using this model developed as a guide.

The model is developed with one of the themes as the pillars of sustainability, which is also known as the triple bottom line looking at sustainability coined by Elkington 1994 which highlights that business performance may be measured in several ways about its finances, the environmental impact and socially its response in relation of the employee. The four themes represent the research questions which has informed the researcher on answering the research objectives. Lastly, the variables that form the empirical finding each represent the three pillars as it affects the community regarding sustainability practice in the Nigeria telecommunication industry. The originality of this study is the conceptual framework that has informed the researcher on developing a model to advise the policymakers and practitioners on sustainability best practices in the industry.

Chapter 6

Conclusions, Implications, and Recommendations.

6.0 Introduction

This chapter aims to draw and present a conclusion of the findings; it then outlines the study's contribution to knowledge and presents a general conclusion. It starts with a review of the research process and presents an overview of the objectives and findings in the previous chapters. The chapter shall also proffer suggestions as a way forward for the Nigerian Telecommunication Industry towards achieving the best sustainability practice in their businesses. Furthermore, recommendations for further research and studies on sustainability best practices for Nigerian telecommunications in Nigeria shall be provided. The limitations experienced during this study shall also be presented in the hope that they could be used as guides in future research.

The above has therefore been summarized into the following four parts.

Conclusions of findings considering research questions and how the aims and objectives of the research have been met. It further discusses the conclusions that have been reached, bearing in mind the extent of the contents of the relevant available literature that have been reviewed.

v Discussion of the contribution to knowledge by the study.

v Discusses future research and concludes with recommendations for the Mobile Telecommunication industry in Nigeria and suggestions for further research.

v Statement of the limitations that were experienced during the study.

The primary research aims to assess the extent to which sustainability is practiced in Nigeria's Telecommunication Industry, evaluate the opportunities available for best practice with a significant focus on MTN Nigeria, and develop a model known as the Nigeria sustainability practice model. (NSPM) which will further enhance best practices for doing better business. As shown in the previous chapters, the factors that drive best practices for sustainability at the global level were explored and critically studied during this research; the inhibitors of sustainability practice in the industry were identified using the relevant available data.

6.1 Have the Aims and Objectives of this Study been met?

The aims and objectives of this study, as were outlined at the onset of chapter one, have been achieved. These were shown in the discussions in the chapters that followed throughout the study. The table below is a shot of all chapter's housing discussions of aims and objectives, which are presented in summary following the table.

Table 9 Objectives achieved and Chapters.

Objectives	Chapter
Objective one	Chapter one and two
Objective two	Chapter two, four, and five
Objective three	Four, five and six
Objective four	Four, five and six

Summary of outcomes to address Objective One

The study found that certain conditions must be present within the telecommunication industry where the aim is to achieve the best sustainability practice. These are known as the Triple Bottom Line (TBL), viz.

v Profit v People v Planet

John Elkington coined this framework in 1994 for performance measurement in corporate organizations. The theory proposes that businesses should be committed to sustainability to the same extent that they are committed to profit. This will mitigate the impact they have on the environment over time. However, the term sustainable development was perceived variously by the respondents in the survey carried out for this research.

For example, the Group Manager of MTN is worried about human rights and the economy in terms of sustainability practices, as these affect the geographical environment based on health and safety matters. The Group Manager of MTN further

expressed that the company is aware that sustainability practices are mostly client-based (people and planet). However, stakeholders (profits) also refine customer experiences while protecting and making shares worthwhile for investors via environmentally and socially responsible core business practices. They have accelerated the pace of change with the help of cooperation and partnerships with the mother company in South Africa. This resonates with the literature reviewed earlier in the study. On the other hand, several research gaps for implementing best practices for sustainability in developing countries have been identified based on a critical literature analysis. These arguments were analyzed in chapters One and Two.

Objective 2: To evaluate the factors impeding sustainability in Nigerian Telecommunications.

Question asked to achieve the chapter; What factors inhibit current sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry?

Summary of outcomes to address Objective.

Two pieces of Evidence from the literature review shows that sustainability and best practice amongst Telecommunications industries in developed countries rely on the Dow Jones (2014) index to measure sustainability practices. The Dow Jones used this index as a measure of sustainability to rank telecommunications industries in the UK. This study has relied on the same index to measure sustainability practices amongst telecommunication operators in Nigeria. However, as this was not achieved due to the availability of the indicator and time constraints to study, more than one company in the telecommunication industry. Nevertheless, the study shows. Some underlying factors inhibit sustainability practices in the sector, making it difficult for the sector to adopt best practices for sustainability. The findings with these points were presented and discussed in chapters Two and Four. These are summarised as follows:

There is a shortage of or a complete lack of energy. This makes telecommunications companies in Nigeria rely primarily on diesel to power their equipment, which increases capital costs. Such costs are, in turn, passed on to consumers through service charges, which results in higher costs for products. Social and cybersecurity challenges are experienced because the internet in Nigeria is highly vulnerable to cyber-attacks by hackers. MTN provides other businesses with 162 video and voice

services to deliver services to various customers, but such goods and services are often stolen.

v Uncertainty in sustainability policies. v Unstable fiscal policies affect tax rates.

v Lack of sustainability practice indicators.

Suggestions for achieving this best practice:

v Renewable energy can be an alternative to power supplies to address the issue of shortages of electricity

Objective 3: To analyze the possible benefits of developing improved sustainability practices in Nigeria.

Question asked to achieve the objective: To what degree do the methods of practice put in place

impact on sustainability levels in the Nigerian telecommunications industry?

Summary of outcomes to address Objective Three:

The findings from this study indicate the presence of sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry; however, these practices fall below the required standard, and there is a need to adopt best practices to raise the bar. Based on the interview with MTN, this company has considered the issues and has created rules that regulate sustainability to develop best practices in the following ways

- By consistently training staff to meet ever-changing client demands and needs.
- By integrating staff into the decisions of the firm to advance the network and revenue that the company generates.
- Since MTN does not have a direct sustainability policy section, compliance policies are monitored by the health and safety team.

Previous studies have recognized that sustainable practice within any business raises the income level and the value of business rates. Therefore, efforts to save energy to decrease GHG are one of the least harmful ways to develop sustainable business practices within the telecoms industry. This finding confirms the views in the literature

that developing an improved sustainability model for best sustainability practices can benefit the Nigerian telecommunications industry. These issues were reported in chapters Two and Five of this work.

Suggestion for achieving best practice:

- An improved model for sustainability practice should be adopted for best practice in the Nigerian telecommunications industry.

Objective 4: To develop a model for improving sustainability practice in Nigeria based on the case of MTN Nigeria.

Question asked to achieve the objective:

What is the significance of the possible benefits of improving sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry?

A survey for this study shows that the current state of sustainability practice in Nigeria is influenced by many factors that impinge on companies that attempt to adopt best sustainability practices. An indicator such as the Dow Jones Sustainability Index comprising the three pillars can be used best practice.

tool in several sectors as an indicator of principles that can be used in all sustainability procedures and benchmarking tools. These models and interventions are currently in their initial stage of development in terms of their efficacy in investigating how they can be used as indicators of ground-breaking sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications sector with the recommendation to study further. The acknowledgment and acceptance of best-practice initiatives confirm the usefulness of adopting an improved model to enhance sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. Suggestions for achieving this best practice,

Based on the findings of this research, the Nigerian telecommunications industry needs to adopt a new model to improve its sustainability practices in many companies. Hence a new model has been developed because of this research known as the Nigerian Sustainability Model (NSPM). This model

can serve as an indicator of sustainability practice. This point is elaborated upon towards the end of this research. Linking environmentally liable plans, products, and procedures into a business and combining these with the flexible delivery of information about business sustainability will, in turn, benefit and encourage a positive and sustainable business image. This will impact brand loyalty amongst consumers and will have implications for the sustainability of the natural environment.

Summary of outcomes to address Objective Four.

To ensure that best practice for sustainability in the telecommunication industry is delivered, the socioeconomic and environmental sustainability benefits must be viewed as important. Hence, there is a need for the adequate involvement of all critical stakeholders in delivery. Sustainability is vital, as is close collaboration between policymakers, telecommunication operators, and other stakeholders. This also calls for a need to review the policy of the NCC of 2002, which is currently employed to procure and engage key stakeholders and practitioners in delivery. Legislation should be introduced to drive telecommunications operators to adapt and implement socioeconomic and environmental sustainability into their practices. Enforcing compliance using such legislation will enable operators to promote socioeconomic and environmental sustainability practices.

Policymakers and regulatory bodies must encourage or even make it mandatory for telecommunications operators to adopt a systematic and well-structured evaluation process to evaluate their sustainability practices to rate a best practice based on global benchmarks. The importance of the impact of best practices for sustainability on business performance in Nigeria's mobile telecommunications industry suggests there is a need for a better understanding of the organizational forces that determine the direction of sustainable business operations within the firm. Mobile telecommunications operators who want to outperform similar or competing operators can do so by adopting best practices for sustainability. They should, therefore, monitor and improve how they gather, disseminate, and respond to sustainability. This is an example of how best practices for sustainability in mobile telecommunications could occur to connect with the market, customers, and employees. The aim must improve organizational growth and profitability, which are required for competitiveness and survival.

Objective four of the Study

Set out to develop a model for improved sustainability practices in Nigeria (see item 3 of the key findings above). This serves as a guide for evaluating various socioeconomic sustainability benefits of sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. The basis for the model has its roots in the literature review (Chapter Two), the semi/ structured interviews, and the data collected and analyzed in Chapters Four and Five. The model is subsequently tested through a validation process with MTN Nigeria Communication (see Chapter Five). The model incorporates an evaluation of inputs, including Nigeria's sustainability policy drivers, its organizational drivers and barriers, and various social, economic, and environmental sustainability factors. Information gathering, stakeholder consultation, factor identification, data collection and analysis, and finding presentation guide the telecommunications industry.

6. 1. 2 Conclusions to the Aim of Study

This research investigates existing sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. A new model for best sustainability practice has been the outcome. To identify the determinants of best sustainability practices in telecommunications, the study critically explored and analyzed the factors driving global sustainability practices compared to Nigeria's practices. Several gaps in best practice were identified, as set out in previous chapters. The adoption of best practices will lead to improved sustainability practices for the industry. Nevertheless, this can only be realized if the Nigerian communications commission is fully dedicated to the cause. The priority must be to improve Nigeria's sustainability practices in telecommunications using best practice methods that rely on the following influences.

The presence and applicability of sustainability practice to discuss the difficulties faced by the Nigerian telecommunications sector • Generating best practice ingenuities in the sector. Profits of best practices for sustainability. This study also relied on documents from Airtel, another Nigerian-based Telecommunication Company. Its governing body has not incorporated any sustainability practices within its policy statements. Without a straightforward sustainability policy, there are very few indicators of sustainability performance. However, the same company acknowledges and appreciates that best practices are essential for sustainability to enable

competitiveness and profitability and win customer loyalty. On the other hand, the lack of best practices could mean the company stops making a profit and even leads to business failure. However, the nature and character of specific sustainability activities vary from organization to organization, depending on many underlying factors that may be peculiar to them.

6.2. Conclusion of the result of the study

The study results highlight a few issues with adopting best practices in Nigeria's telecommunications sector. It has become necessary to adopt and put in place a holistic method and approach to improve and enhance the current method, which illuminates many inhibiting factors that affect performance. The dynamic nature of the business world exposes firms to a diversity of problems, and the inability of many companies to assess and overcome such challenges has often resulted in their failure to achieve business aims. In some cases, this has foreshadowed their collapse. This study has revealed that MTN, one of Nigeria's critical mobile telecommunications businesses, recognizes sustainability practices as vital to good business. This is clearly stated and clarified in the company's policy statement. The company is also familiar with and acknowledges the existence of certain factors that inhibit sustainability practices in the sector. Such factors are familiar and include leadership, ecological influence, mercurial policies, and security problems. These all create costs for companies as they strive to implement sustainable practices.

6.3 Implications of the Study.

The study has evaluated the sustainability practices of the Nigerian telecommunications industry, intending to look beyond an assessment of historical facts and underlying mobile telephony issues. Instead, the aim has been to assess the industry based on several relevant features that define the current trading environment and sustainability practices. Theories of sustainability have been used as guidelines to accurately determine the best practices most suitable to Nigeria's mobile telecommunications industry. The first interview question posed to participants sought not only to justify the industry's focus but also to draw attention to the far-reaching consequences of the conclusion of this research. The responses to this question reveal just how important sustainability is to the telecommunications industry, considering its significant contribution to national GDP. Its positive impact on all other

sectors of the economy and its contribution to overall employment became evident during the interviews. Nigeria, as a nation, would not be where it is today without this growing industry and its commitments. NCC is the policymaking and regulatory body, and it prioritizes sustainability practices in the telecommunications sector. However, there are no clear indicators to measure sustainability practices. Authorities. Thus, the time has come for NCC to perform the duties it was appointed for in the first place. 166 In summary, this research analysed sustainability practices within the mobile telecommunications industry over the last few years using the case of MTN Nigeria. The research has described where the industry is and why it is there, and it has suggested ways to improve its practices. These ideas are all encapsulated in the model that has been proposed.

6.3.1 Implication for Theory

Specific knowledge gaps were identified from the literature review, which provided an opportunity to develop new research. It was observed that most methodological approaches are outdated and do not conform to today's changing conditions and technological advancements. Previous approaches have been dominated by surveys and quantitative methods with little or no evidence of exploratory, participant observation, and ethnographic-based research. This research has deployed a qualitative method to analyze data, addressing several knowledge gaps. The findings have implications for telecommunications businesses and other stakeholders in Nigeria. This research also generally serves to broaden the knowledge of operators and stakeholders of telecommunications businesses in Nigeria around best practices for sustainability in the sector. The research also looked at how best sustainability practices in developed countries can be applied to a developing country like Nigeria.

Another significant contribution to the literature on best practices is the finding concerning the consequences of avoiding best practices for sustainability within the context of Nigeria's mobile telecommunications industry. Furthermore, it is significant that this study can identify the antecedents that endanger the telecommunications industry because of the benefits that companies can accrue if adopting a best-practice approach to sustainability. Gaps in knowledge in terms of best practices in sustainability in

the telecommunications industry in Nigeria were also identified based on interviews with the staff from MTN and NCC. Compared with the MTN management staff, analysis reveals some consistency between the responses and the documents available on MTN's website about best practices.

Knowledge transfer is priceless; hence knowledge of the existence of The Dow Jones index report (2014) is key to the Nigerian telecommunications industry when it comes to sustainability practice. Therefore, where best practice industry blueprints exist, knowledge transfer should be a by-product since it provides an opportunity to adapt best practices for sustainability from developed countries to developing countries. Gaps in practice seem to be a logical basis for formulating strategies to enhance best practices for sustainability in the Nigerian telecommunication industry.

6.3.2 Implication to Policy and Practice

The study's first objective is to critically review the literature on sustainability practices in the Nigerian telecommunications industry, focusing mainly on MTN Nigeria. The research process began with an initial literature review in Chapter One to establish the critical issues for this research. A review of the literature in Chapter Two explored vital issues relating to sustainable development and concepts and policies on sustainable practice in telecommunications in developed countries. Based on the literature review, data were collected through semi/structured interviews to obtain an in-depth understanding of the issues concerned. The findings of the semi-structured interviews further provided the basis for the qualitative data for this study.

The literature reviewed also offered helpful information to underpin the analysis of various issues explored in this study. Relevant findings were revealed from the literature that can be used for further studies on sustainability. The second objective is concerned with the evaluation of factors impacting sustainability practices in Nigerian telecommunications. To achieve this objective, relevant literature has been reviewed (see chapter 2), which was followed by a semi/structured interview with MTN staff to collect data. From the perspective of the economic and social construct, incremental economic development from telecommunications diffusions comes at a negative cost to the environment, and this adverse effect may be countered to some extent by best practice. If best practices are adopted, a nullification effect can be experienced from the contribution to economic development and social welfare

generated by the telecommunications industry. Sustainability can be viewed across three constructs. Efficient sustainability by corporate organizations in developing economies can be challenging because of the backdrop of increasing energy costs (economic construct), the carbon-constrained global economy, and the number of associated implications for climate change (environment construct). Corporations' base green decisions on an economic rationale with social consequences for how they engage with their host country (social construct, creating a sustainability model for the industry further offers valuable knowledge and corrective measures for those interested in seeing the industry blossom and who ultimately seek to see continuous development in all areas.

As asserted by British Telecom (2011), this study paradoxically reveals that innovative intervention strategies and approaches have been designed by telecommunication companies in developed economies, operating under stringent regulations while receiving active scrutiny to reduce energy consumption and GHG emissions. Such companies recognize and adopt best practices in sustainability. Therefore, the methods and instruments used in this study could thus be utilized by telecommunications companies in Nigeria. Investors in the telecommunications industry could analyze to monitor and measure their firm's sustainability practices and performance. The study also fulfils an established need for a comparative evaluation of best practices for sustainability in mobile telecommunications. This has implications for management in the industry.

Mobile telecommunications owners in Nigeria will thus be motivated to accept best practices in sustainability as an instrument to help them achieve their business objectives and commit resources to remain sustainable in business. Furthermore, the study significantly contributes to how businesses in Nigeria's mobile telecommunications industry perceive the pillars of sustainability and the antecedents and consequences of sustainability. The study suggests how they can respond to these issues in their organizations. Many benefits can be achieved by adopting best practice activities that can be replicated, even at lower uptake levels in emerging economies like Nigeria. In such countries, the current levels of sustainability best practices are modest. This makes a case for a cross- comparative study since sustainability practices can reduce costs and financial performance.

Furthermore, sustainability practices can increase shareholder wealth through increased productivity and living standards, as evidenced in BT Groups' sustainability awards.

Therefore, the telecommunications industry can adopt the practice of sustainability more widely. Best practices can be mapped out and shared through knowledge exchange from this research. The issue of social duality and plurality can become less of a priority for corporations in developing economies.

Environmental and social sustainability interventions will lead to better economic performance in the telecommunications industry if correctly practiced. To identify best practice industry blueprints, Jayanti and Gowda (2014) refer to Leadership in Energy & Environmental Design (LEED) rankings and the Dow Jones Sustainability Indices as signposts for corporations in terms of their peers doing well. Such an approach creates an ideology around sustainability and financial performance (Jayant & Gowda, 2014); sustainability Measurement indicators can be modified for sustainability studies focused on the Nigerian telecommunications industry as innovative interventions.

These represent a starting point for the telecommunications services industry in Nigeria. The above deliberations underpin the rationale for adopting Nigeria as an ideal case study, and further Evidence is provided in the gaps in the literature in support of this approach. A triage of sorts is applied in selecting the focus for this research, which looks at opportunities for increased levels of sustainability in the Nigerian telecommunications industry. In this way, the study adds to the knowledge of best practices. The third objective set by this research was to analyze the possible benefits of developing improved sustainability practices in telecommunications in Nigeria.

The essential organizational social and economic sustainability drivers for sustainable business in Nigeria have thus been denied. The literature review in Chapter Two and the semi/structured interviews and document analysis in chapter Five revealed several significant socioeconomic sustainability factors that drive sustainability in the telecommunications industry in its quest to deliver sustainable business in Nigeria. The mechanisms put in place by the company were first explored with MTN staff through semi-structured interviews, followed by a document analysis of MTN's sustainability report in 2014.

6.3.3 Implication for methods

The study is significant in terms of the analysis method adopted. While most significant studies have been undertaken in developed countries, few have been produced in developing countries such as Nigeria. Many have applied MANOVA and ANOVA in their analyses. This study adopts thematic analysis as a critical method to identify themes to make sense of the data collected. None of the other methods was designed to produce themes to capture what has been learned from the data.

6.4 Key contributions to the study

- 1) Adoption of best practices in sustainability is essential hence this will affect capital costs which is one of the factors inhibiting sustainability in Nigeria's telecommunications industry
- 2) Nigeria's communications commission has policies to comply with all environmental regulations that support sustainability practices. However, this is not a helpful indicator to measure and monitor sustainability practices in the industry.
- 3) Adopting and implementing the proposed conceptual framework and the Nigerian Sustainability Practice Model (NSPM) could improve Nigeria's sustainability practices. This finding equally adds to the knowledge of best practices in other telecommunications companies in Nigeria.

6.5 Way Forward for Best Practice

Having carefully considered a summary of the conclusions of the study, the following suggestions are provided for the attention of the Nigerian telecommunications industry to achieve the best sustainability practice: According to Kester et al. (2019), access to modern energy as a renewable energy source has proven to be more efficient, leading to financial savings and reducing carbon emissions and assets in shareholder wealth. This has served as a guide for sustainability best practices for the telecommunications industry in Nigeria. Practitioners should endeavor to acquire adequate knowledge to enhance their understanding and skills in sustainability practices, considering the three construct pillars of sustainability through regular attendance at sustainability seminars, workshops, and other sustainability training programs. Studying the literature in this area is also advised.

NCC should gain a good understanding of what developed countries like the UK have done around the policy regarding sustainability practices for the telecommunications industry. This would enable them to focus their policies and practices on economic, social, and environmental sustainability factors to deliver the core objective of this policy initiative to embrace best practices. There must be an adequate and genuine level of commitment from telecommunications owners to promote critical social, economic, and environmental sustainability principles in their organizations through sustainable policies and practices. This should occur willingly and without pressure.

The NCC is the governing body for telecommunications and the policymaker and regulatory authority. They should implement sustainability training programs to enable telecommunications companies to acquire and enhance their sustainability knowledge and skills to equip them to adequately deal with socioeconomic and environmental sustainability issues in their business to remain sustainable. Clients in both the public and private sectors should also be encouraged to participate in such training programs to enhance their knowledge and awareness of the main components of sustainability practice. This will equip them adequately with the right skills and could change their mindsets and attitudes toward adopting and implementing socioeconomic and environmental sustainability in their company.

6.6 Recommendations

Recommendations for sustainability practitioners.

In recommendation, Telecommunication operators should prioritize their sustainability goals based on current and expected stakeholder demands and industry trends. Telecommunication's current focus should be on reducing energy consumed by their products during the use phase since it constitutes a significant chunk of the overall carbon dioxide emissions (approximately 85%). This is true for the telecommunication companies discussed in the thesis, i.e., energy consumption in the use phase constitutes most of their emissions and is on top of their priority list for 'going green. However, these companies have focused on other significant issues, such as supply chain and reporting, and have achieved a certain level of sustainability in all other departments. Telecommunication companies, therefore, should pay more attention to

other departments, supply chains, and reporting to ensure that their sustainability drive is comprehensive. However, introducing measures for sustainability can only be effective if the top management is fully committed to it. This is evident in the statements and comments given by sustainability managers in books and scientific papers on the issue and annual reports of companies. This commitment requirement might not appear in theories and frameworks. However, it is necessary as any other steps taken by the organization since the manager sets the goal for the rest of the employees. Telecommunication companies in Nigeria, or any other company, need to keep this essential aspect in mind while attempting to become environmentally friendly since it plays a vital role in the effectiveness of policies.

Recommendation for policy makers.

Sustainability-related practices, policies, and procedures support should endeavor that all executives take sustainability issues, considering the risks and opportunities and integrating them into their decision-making process. The disclosure of such practices, policies, and procedures is intended to promote consistency, comparability, and reliability in disclosure, which, as discussed in Chapter 2, will help prevent greenwashing at the asset manager level.

Future Research

Some critical future research can also be suggested to improve future works (practice, policy, and research) about sustainability practices in mobile telecommunications in Nigeria. This proposed future research is based on the overall findings of the present study, and these are as follows. Future studies could also explore how the framework can be adapted or adopted for application in different contexts and countries for sustainability. There is scope for further studies to be carried out to explore, in more depth, telecommunication operators' levels of involvement in the delivery of sustainable business.

There is particularly a need to consider the three main pillars of sustainability. The present study focuses on the scope of the socio, economic and environmental pillars of sustainability, and it identifies the benefits of best practices for sustainability in Nigeria's telecommunication industry.

The research methodology adopted for the present study could be employed to study how the socio, economic and environmental pillars of sustainability benefits can be deployed in different contexts in different countries. The study has advocated for innovative intervention strategies and approaches that have been designed by telecommunications companies in developed economies. Telecommunications businesses in developed countries operate under stringent regulations, and they receive active scrutiny to reduce their energy consumption and GHG emissions. They recognize and adopt best practices associated with sustainability (British Telecom BT, 2011).

6.7 Limitations of the Study

A vital shortfall of the study was that it only triangulated qualitative findings from staff and from documents in terms of sustainability practice. It used the three pillars of sustainability to examine the extent to which they corroborate each other, leaving out the antecedents and consequences.

Subsequent studies can, therefore, explore both qualitative and quantitative research approaches, not only on sustainability but also in terms of their antecedents and outcomes for comparison. The size of the performance and the consequences for Nigeria's mobile telecommunications industry were not taken into consideration, and performance data such as annual reports or other documentary sources of data such as trade and allied publications were not reviewed. It relied solely on perceived data.

Future research can make use of performance data or other such data to measure the performance of firms. The sample size for the study was based on MTN communication and documents from the website.

This limited the size of the data that could have been used for robust testing and analyses. A reasonable sample has been used for this study. However, more data could have been collected for more interviews; this was hampered because of two, most importantly, the covid19 pandemic. Obtaining a strong sample size for interviews was a challenge. Content analysis is subjective (Guthrie & Abeysekera, 2006), and it involves "working on documents which have been written for some objectives other than for the research" (Robson, 2002; p.358).

This study collected data on the sustainability practices of MTN. These data represent what these businesses communicate about their sustainability practices and what was reported may vary from the actual practices that are applied. To overcome this limitation, some other data sources, such as interviews with more staff, could be carried out to corroborate the findings (Robson, 2002). This study treated the 12-member staff as a unified unit, which left room for further studies to compare the results between individual jurisdictions. Eleven MTN staff were approached as a single population, and no account was taken of the number of telecommunications businesses in each country within the sample. At the level of generalisability, the strategy used in this study only demonstrated the sustainability practices of MTN as a telecommunications operator in Nigeria. However, many other arrangements may exist, so the finding might not be representative of other telecommunications operators.

The unit of analysis for this study focused on telecommunications sustainability practices in Nigeria. Therefore, further studies could focus on other sectors as a unit of analysis. Future studies could also adopt a case study research approach for the entire Nigerian telecommunications industry based on more than one company.

It would have been appropriate to examine the responses of all telecommunications operators in Nigeria because staff in other telecommunications businesses may have highlighted issues from a different perspective depending on their proximity to the leadership of their organizations. Operators chosen from MTN are likely to be different from other operators. It is therefore proposed that future research should consider incorporating views from the staff at other telecommunications operators.

Future studies could classify sustainability strategies into more than two types. Indeed, future studies could widen this out to include other types of telecommunications companies, such as Globalcom Ltd. Moreover, the study was conducted on publicly listed telecommunications holding companies that produce sustainability reports. Hence, it overlooked other types of operators. Further research should seek to examine the sustainability practices of other telecommunications operators. Also, a comparison between the sustainability practices of two or more operator types is desirable. In this regard, the sustainability index developed to capture sustainability scopes in the telecommunications sector could be refined. Due to limitations in the

time available to carry out fieldwork, the data gathered were not sufficiently detailed to make a comparison between telecommunications operators, such as the Dow Jones index, for the assessment of sustainability practice.

Finally, Nigeria has been facing an energy crisis, with power generation problems often appearing in the headlines. This is limiting for many reasons. According to anecdotal evidence, power rationing has affected service delivery in general and the performance of the mobile telecommunications industry specifically. The mobile telecommunications industry thrives on regular, consistent, and available power to ensure that its masts are operating at maximum capacity. Power rationing coupled with irregular power supplies means there is some likelihood of a lack of control affecting service delivery in general, which in turn can affect the responses of both owners of telecommunications companies and the staff. It would be interesting to find out what the reactions of staff and operators would be like in 'normal' times when the crisis has ended. This can form the basis for future research. These limitations are, however, not considered significant enough to minimize the value of the findings of this study.

6.8 Summary of the Chapter and Conclusion of the Study.

This study has triangulated qualitative document analysis and interviews in relation to sustainability practices amongst Nigerian telecommunications businesses. The two approaches together mean that the findings are accurate. Indeed, the findings indicate that, although mobile telecommunications companies in Nigeria practice sustainability, some elements are swallowed up by other government policies, and this makes it difficult to identify sustainability within policies. Unstable taxation and irregularities in sustainability policies meant that firms in Nigeria are sustainably oriented.

The findings show that MTN is concerned with customers, stakeholders, and value creation. Other factors inhibiting sustainability practices in the company include industrial constraints, a shortage of energy, and the cost of capital, as well as unclear sustainability policies. Other issues inhibiting the ability of businesses to embrace best practices include the ever-rising rate of taxation at widespread intervals, as well as various security challenges. One of the managers that responded associated struggles with sustainability with fluctuations in foreign currency exchange rates. Another significant finding in this study is the lack of a dedicated unit to monitor the practice of

sustainability. In addition, there is no measure or indicator for best sustainability practice. The study, however, reveals that the sustainability practices of mobile telecommunications firms in Nigeria significantly determine both the economic, social, and environmental performance of a business with implications for the industry should best practice in sustainability be adopted.

The Nigerian Sustainability Practice Model (NSPC) is key in this sense. The benefits of this model are an envisaged reduction in the capital cost of mobile telecommunications operators. Overall, best practices in sustainability could bring about a significant impact on economic business performance as well as social and environmental progress in Nigeria's mobile telecommunications industry's advanced brand image and competitive advantage. The rise in output and reduced cost. The upsurge in the capacity of businesses to obey guidelines and the ability to attract staff and stakeholders.

The ability to decrease waste and make investors happy. Thus, the findings reveal that best practice for sustainability is the most appropriate strategic option to run a business and make a profit while still recognizing the three pillars of sustainability. From the discussion of findings, it can be concluded that aside from some differences in the views of sustainability, Nigeria's current state of practice will benefit best practice adaptation in terms of sustainability practices in Nigeria's telecommunication industry.

The framework indicates the effectiveness of the use of best practices for sustainability in Nigeria's mobile telecommunication sector. Most of the findings of this study are consistent with previous sustainability studies in developed countries with implications for the appropriateness of the application of the conceptual sustainability framework (Chapter 2, Figure .6).

The usefulness of this framework is confirmed by this research, despite inconsistencies with some factors that inhibit sustainability. The findings of the study generally resonate with the results of Oyegoke & Norrington's (2014) model and Zhang's (2014) analysis, which have led to many industries adopting and designing sustainable chain models and methods that aim to reduce the overall cost of their operations. Furthermore, sustainability practice, as indicated by Michael (2016), provides mobile telecommunications firms in Nigeria with ways to reduce costs and

make profits while working sustainably to remain competitive and survive. The discussion in this chapter has discussed the following

Appropriate conclusions.

- The significance of the study
- The limitations of the study
- Suggestions for the telecommunications industry
- Recommendations and directions for future research

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Appendix

Participant Information Sheet

Title of Study

Evaluating sustainability practices in the Nigeria Mobile Telecommunication. A case of Nigeria's Mobile Telecommunication Industry.

My name is Akoche Veronica Ekeh, and I am conducting this research as a student of a Doctorate in Business administration at the University of West Scotland (London Campus) in the United Kingdom. The purpose of this study is to be able to identify and evaluate opportunities and barriers to sustainability practices within the region of Nigeria using a case study of the Mobile telecommunication services industry in Nigeria. You have been approached because the study requires information from people who work in MTN Nigeria for data collection for the research purpose. You do not have to take part, it's entirely up to you to decide whether you take part. If you decide you would like to take part, you would be asked to take part in an interview with the principal investigator. The information you provide is confidential. The data collected for this study will be stored securely, and only the researchers conducting this study will have access to this data:

- o Audio recordings will be destroyed and deleted once the project has been submitted for publication/examined
- o The files on the computer will be encrypted (that is no-one other than the researcher will be able to access them), and the computer itself password-protected for ten years before it is destroyed.

The printed version of your interview will be made anonymous by removing any identifying information, including your name. Anonymized direct quotations from your interview may be used in the reports or publications from the study, so your name will not be attached to them

All your data will be confidential and will be kept separately from your interview responses. There are some limits to confidentiality: if what is said in the interview makes me think that you, or someone else, is at a significant risk of harm, I will have to break confidentiality and speak to a member of staff about this. If possible, I will tell you if I must. The results will be summarised and reported in a thesis and will be submitted for publication in an academic setting. There are no risks anticipated by participating in this study. However, if you experience any distress following

participation, you are encouraged to inform the researcher and contact the resources provided at the end. Although you may find participating interesting, there are no direct benefits to taking part. This study has been reviewed by the Business School Research Ethics Committee and approved by the University Research Ethics Committee at the University of West Scotland. If you have any questions about the study, please contact the primary researcher:

Akoche Veronica Ekeh DBA University of West Scotland (London Campus). Email address [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

DBA Director of Studies Business and Enterprise

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

If you wish to make a complaint or raise concerns about any aspect of this study and do not want to speak to the researcher, you can contact:

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

University of West Scotland Thank you for taking the time to read this information sheet.

CONSENT FORM FOR INTERVIEW

Name of Researcher:

Akoche Veronica Ejeh Research Title:

Evaluating sustainability practices in the Nigeria Mobile Telecommunication industry.
A case of MTN Nigeria Ltd.

Study Number: B00312270

Please initial the box. (1) I consent that I have read and understood the participant information sheet dated 3rd April 2018 for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

(2) I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason, without my employment care or legal rights being affected.

(3) I understand that the content of any employment notes may be looked at by responsible individuals or regulatory where it is relevant to my participating in the research. I permit those individuals to have access.

(4) I agree to take part in the above study. Name of the participant. Signature. Ejeh Av Date. 30th June 2018.

Name of researcher Akoche Veronica Eje Signature Eje AV

Date 3 rd. April 2018

A copy was issued to the participant, and the researcher retained a copy.

Appendix 4

you could please review pages 1, 3, and 4 of the latest Group Sustainability Report available online <https://www.mtn.com/en/mtn-group/sustainability/cases-andlibrary/Pages/Reports.aspx>,

Interview template 1.

1. Introduction about the research /consent form

The Research Topic: Evaluating Sustainability Practices in Nigeria Mobile Telecommunication. A case of Nigeria's Mobile Telecommunication Industry

please you will kindly sign the consent letter for me after I must have gone through it with you. - Thank you for agreeing to participate in the interview –

I am a Doctorate degree student in Business administration with the university of the West Scotland. –

The researcher will go through the consent form with the interviewed – The Researcher will allow room for questions from the participants.

2. Management staff MTN Nigeria and NCC Details

A. Demographic Details Gender: M F

Age: 30 -40 40 – 41 50-60

Education qualification

(a) degree (b) MSc (c) PhD B.

B. Work Experience

What is your present position in the company?

What are your years of experience doing this job and previous job? What are your working arrangements?

Full Time /Part-Time

Can you tell me a little bit about your career progression since joining your organisation?

3. Interview Questions

1. What does sustainability mean to your company?
2. Could you tell me about MTN sustainability practices?
3. How does MTN Nigeria conceptualise sustainability
4. How has MTN implemented sustainability and what are the mechanisms put in place
5. What factors do you think inhibit sustainability practices in the company
6. What factors facilitate sustainability practices in the company
7. What are the drivers of MTN sustainability policy?
8. How does MTN recycle its used products?
9. What opportunity exist in the company that can support sustainability
10. What are the constraints and challenges MTN faces in sustainability practice?
11. In terms of sustainability what you will do different to attain standard practice in telecommunication.
12. Does NCC consider sustainability as a priority for mobile telecommunication regulatory
13. How will you describe sustainability practice in Nigeria mobile telecommunication system?
14. How relevant do you think sustainability practice is to Nigeria